

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

**THE IMPACT OF CULTURAL DIVERSITY AS A TOOL TO DEVELOP
COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE IN THE NIGERIAN BANKING INDUSTRY**

Prepared By:

CYNTHIA OLUCHI UGWU

B00315288

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this thesis to my darling husband for all his love and support, not minding the distance barrier but always encouraging me to be better, no matter the circumstances (Mr. Okechukwu Jeffery Nwobi), to my beloved father for his constant love, always inspiring and making sure I achieve all my goals (Sir. Cosmas Amaechi Ugwu), to my caring father-in-law in whom I am well pleased for all his affection and huge backing up (Rev. Canon. Dr. Okechukwu Nwobi), to my sweet mother-in-law for all her prayers and positive advice (Lady Nnenna Nwobi) and to my wonderful siblings for always reassuring me (Mrs. Genevieve Uche, Mrs. Esther Unamba-Opara, Miss Philpa Ugwu, Master Cosmas E Ugwu).

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DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis is my original work except proven otherwise and it has certainly not been presented to any institution for any degree award.

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ABSTRACT

Globalization has made the working environment a very culturally diverse place. Cultural diversity and its role in firm performance have become an important issue in the workplace. The study examined the effect of cultural diversity on competitive advantage in the Nigerian banking industry. In particular, the study focused on the elements of cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry; how cultural diversity influences competitive advantage; the relationship between cultural diversity and competitive advantage; and how issues of cultural diversity are managed. To achieve the objectives of the study, quantitative and qualitative data were used. Quantitative data were obtained from 305 employees from six (6) selected banks using a combination of simple random and convenience sampling techniques, respectively. Qualitative data was obtained via phone interviews with 24 respondents. The quantitative data was analysed using structural equation modeling while the qualitative data was based on thematic content analysis. The results revealed that cultural diversity affects the competitiveness of Nigerian banks by promoting management and innovation. The study also provided some theoretical and managerial contributions. The study makes some contributions to theory, such as confirming the stance of the cognitive diversity theory, which argues that various points of view coming from cultural differences between individuals in an organization bring about creative problem solving and innovation. This leads to a competitive advantage and member diversity is seen as a resource, capability, or competence, affirming the marketing-based view (MBV), the resource-based view (RBV), knowledge-based view (KBV), capability-based view, and the relational view of strategy theories. Concerning managerial contribution, the study provided a 2-stage approach to managing cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry. The pre-stage approach is referred to as the first stage. Therefore, before an organization decides to diversify, first the process, structure, and operational philosophy should align to support the diversity of the workforce; second, management training programs for top-level management are necessary because it must start from the top if it is to be successful. The idea must then be presented to current employees so that they can put it into practice. Following implementation, success must be ensured through monitoring, measurement, assessment, and reward.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

CBN	Central Bank of Nigeria
KBV	Knowledge-based view
MBV	Marketing-based view
RBV	Resource-based view
SAP	Structural Adjustment Program

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The rapid pace of globalization, propelled by socioeconomic shifts, has altered the number and composition of people who work for organizations, and this has increased the amount of interaction between people of diverse cultural backgrounds and beliefs. (Mazur, 2010). As a result, how managers manage cultural differences such as language, culture, ethnicity, age, gender, or religion (Grin, 2004; Köppel, 2008; Amadeo, 2013), and how effective diversity management has been used as a support and a defense against discrimination (Shen, Chanda, D'Netto and Monga, 2009; Roberson, 2019), as well as how cultural diversity affects performance, have become interesting research in the workplace. Within a business, workforce diversity refers to the considerable contrasts and similarities that exist among personnel (Griffin and Moorhead, 2014). According to Nwinami (2014), it represents an individual's distinctiveness, which encompasses personality, age, gender, ethnicity, race, religion, marital status, income, work experience, and all those perspectives that assume and preserve an organization's fundamental value. It similarly refers to organizations that are becoming more diverse in terms of their worker makeup, based on factors such as age, ethnicity, competence, and so on (Robbins and Judge, 2013). Both good and negative outcomes have been associated with cultural diversity (Nkwoka, 2003). Cultural diversity, for example, brings a variety of perspectives and expertise, but it also comes with costs like tuition and outsourcing. As a result, most businesses now have to cope with the challenges of cultural diversity. When variations are recognised as resources for organizational success (Joubert, 2012), effective diversity management occurs, resulting in increased organizational health and well-being (Fisher, 2010). Successful approaches to managing diversity among workers may be influenced by the work environment (Findler, Wind, and Mor Barak, 2007).

Scholars (Hewlett, Marshall, and Sherbin, 2013; Østergaard, Timmermans, and Kristinsson, 2011) have argued that diversity in language, culture, age, gender, religion, or ethnicity may be associated with diversity in skill sets that drive innovation. Consulting Group (BCG) undertook a survey of 1,700 American businesses of all sizes and locations to assess their innovative

potential. As a measure of innovation, BCG looked at the percentage of a company's revenue that came from products and services launched in the previous three years. Organizations with above-average diversity generated a higher proportion of revenue from innovation (45%) than companies with below-average diversity, according to BCG (26 percent). Surprisingly, the 19% advantage in terms of innovation has translated into increased overall financial success. Researchers also discovered that the composition of innovation teams has a substantial impact on the role of diversity in creativity. According to a 2013 study by the Center for Talent Innovation, if a member of the innovation team shares the same ethnicity as a client, the team is 150 percent more likely to understand the client's needs, a situation that can mean the difference between winning and losing new business. As a company's diversity increases, so does its capacity to obtain new clients and expand into new markets. Furthermore, the claim that diversity can be an important strategy for innovation is supported by the cognitive diversity theory, which claims that physical diversity characteristics positively affect performance since members of the team make a unique cognitive attribute based on their demographic background and experiences (Horwitz and Horwitz, 2007).

Firms that want to improve performance and stay competitive need to invest in innovation (Hewlett, Marshall, and Sherbin, 2013; Gompers and Wang, 2017; Post, De Lia, DiTomaso, Tirpak, and Borwankar, 2009). According to Victorino Verma, Plaschka, and Dev (2005), the benefit is obvious for service organizations like banks since innovation improves service differentiation and generates financial rewards. According to McDermott and Prajogo (2012), service innovation has resulted in the greatest level of growth and dynamism in terms of economic activity during the last several years. As a result, you cannot browse through the websites of most major banks today without encountering a section on “diversity” (Manning, 2019). Given the importance of innovation to service organizations like banks, it could be argued that diversity within the industry is required to improve innovativeness as most banks offer the same services. Yet, the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) noted that despite hard work toward diversity management, the rate of change is still painfully slow (Tank, 2020). Hence, it is important to explore diversity expression and management as perceived by employees of banks, given that, historically, banks are one of the financial institutions that operate at an international level and have hired people from different cultural backgrounds.

Market liberalisation has resulted in increased ethnic diversity in Sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in Nigeria. A large number of ethnic minorities are reflected in firms, and the amount of multicultural employment is progressively leading to a culturally diverse workforce. Nigeria is renowned as Africa's giant, with a population of over 180 million people, including more than half of the working-age population (Akinnusi, Sonubi, and Oyewunmi, 2017). The growth of the Nigerian economy, the surge in Nigeria's international trade, and the entry of foreign companies into the market have brought about cultural diversity to the fore. Nigeria's banking industry is one of the most culturally diverse, given the presence of foreign banks in the country and also the existence of Nigerian banks in other countries. As a result, there is a wide pool of talent from which businesses can draw to fulfill their objectives. Managers have devised diversity policies to manage the workforce in accordance with the Labour Act and other laws in place to protect all types of employees from discrimination based on their social classification (Ugwuzor, 2011). However, according to Foma (2014), some organizations pretend to embrace diversity rather than demonstrate a genuine desire for it by demonstrating a true commitment to the principles of diversity and inclusion to avoid lawsuits or other legal actions and to put on a public show that helps them gain a good corporate image. Furthermore, the nature of the background of the country's level of diversity has an impact on workplace diversity management in Nigeria (Adeleye et al. 2014). The current weak structure in Nigeria necessitates the establishment of an effective legal regulatory system that is linked to the social framework for diversity management (Adeleye, Aja-Nwachukwu and Fawehinmi, 2012; Akobo, 2016).

According to Ugwuzor (2011), tribalism, regional identities, nepotism, and discrimination appear to exist in both governmental and private organizations in Nigeria. Ethnic bias and other forms of discrimination still occur in the workplace during recruiting, promotion, and other aspects of the employer-employee relationship. Individuals are drawn to those who share similar attitudes, according to the similarity attraction paradigm (Ma, Paek, Kim, and Liu, 2022). According to the similarity-attraction paradigm, employees who work in different work units become less attached, miss work more frequently, and are more likely to quit (Froehlich, Beausaert, and Segers, 2021). As a result, management faces a significant problem in managing its diverse staff as well as ensuring that conflicts of interest in policy and practice implementation are minimized

(Akinnusi, Sonubi, and Oyewunmi, 2017). Diversity in the workplace will always be an issue, according to Nwinami (2014), as long as people with different backgrounds work in the same area. Although our characteristics can foster creativity and innovation at work, they can also be a source of conflict and unhappiness within groups (Mullins, 2010). The argument that there is a link between variety and conflict is supported by Study Mode's (2013) research, which found animosity and confrontations among Nigeria's ethnic groupings. Whatever the case may be, the country continues to be divided along ethnic lines. Lack of trust and discrimination has regularly characterized the relationships between all ethnic groups in the country, threatening the country's unity, peace, and stability. Nigeria has experienced a slew of ethnic crises and violence, including the Igbo-Hausa crisis in Kano; Hausa-Yoruba crises in Lagos and Ogun States; Zagon-Kataf in Kaduna State; Jukun-Tiv in Taraba State; Birom-Hausa in Plateau State; and many more, all of which have threatened the country's unity and well-being (Study Mode, 2013). Furthermore, Ayub and Jehn (2006:181) noted that "research on diversity, in general, has found that diverse groups often prove ineffective at capitalizing on the potential benefits of their diversity for a variety of reasons, such as lack of social integration and high turnover, conflict, competition, and demographic differences."

Consequently, performance is affected when managers fail to understand diversity and are not skilled enough to manage issues of diversity (Assefa, 2014). As a result, management of issues of cultural diversity is vital to the growth of the industry. Therefore, this study aimed to explore diversity expression and management as perceived by management and employees of selected Nigerian banks.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Given that most Nigerian banks offer essentially the same suite of services, differentiating oneself from the competition is challenging. So, customers might switch banks or even have many banks to meet their diverse needs. As a result, banks should expect a decline in customer loyalty and retention (Mahmoud et al. 2011). As a result of this realization, banks have begun to think about service innovation as a way to differentiate itself to stand out. However, the vast majority of innovation studies have focused on manufacturing technology innovation, reflecting

the fact that innovation theory was developed during a period when manufacturing was the primary economic activity (Drejer, 2002; Wen, Qualls and Zeng, 2021).

Additionally, due to the competitive nature of the banking industry and globalisation, many banks in Nigeria have nowadays expanded their businesses abroad, with some banks also entering the Nigerian market. It is more difficult to run a business in multiple countries than it is to run a business in a single market. Nonetheless, “cultural diversity can provide a source of experience and innovative thinking if it is effectively managed” (Shaw and Barrett-Power, 1998). Many companies are currently realizing the necessity of harnessing the qualities and abilities of all their employees through work teams to improve organizational competitiveness, according to Sun et al. (2017). As a result, efforts to integrate people of diverse ages, genders, and races are more likely to succeed if they are conducted with a better understanding of the effects of demographic diversity on team performance. Consequently, when cultural differences within an organization are properly handled, they can provide a competitive advantage for the company while still fostering long-term and strong internal relationships. However, previous research on cultural diversity and its impact on team performance has produced mixed results (Tshetshema and Chan, 2020), as the effects of gender, age, tenure, or other forms of diversity on outcomes have varied (Sobral and Bisseling, 2012). Hence, not all companies believe that these benefits of cultural diversity are necessary to accept in day-to-day managerial transactions (Kundu, 2001). When operating a company in various countries, cultural differences are a significant aspect to consider. However, there is no unified way to handle cultural diversity. Even for a country like Nigeria, given that it is one of the largest countries in the world with people from diverse backgrounds. Cultural diversity, if not managed well, can limit contact, which could lead to workplace discontent and hinder employees' ability to adapt to one another. Unhappy employees would have a negative impact on results (Montagliani and Giacalone, 1998). The structure of how work is organized within an organization must be understood and may need to be changed to facilitate effectiveness (Sherwood, 2003). Understanding how and why people behave and act in various ways across cultures will help to reduce the likelihood of misunderstandings.

Furthermore, there are a limited number of cited research works that have examined the association between diversity and innovation (Jones, Chace, and Wright, 2020; Tshetshema, and

Chan, 2020). This could be because service innovation research is still in its infancy, with methodologies that apply traditional industrial logic to service innovation coexisting with approaches that view services as a distinct activity. A reasonable next step is to develop a methodology that takes into account the blurring of manufacturing and service borders and thereby applies an innovative perspective that is not limited to the old manufacturing-service dichotomy. Such a synthesis approach to service innovation research (Coombs and Miles, 2000; Drejer, 2002) can help bring to the fore aspects of innovation that have hitherto been disregarded in the context of manufacturing innovation but are critical to service organizations. Because services are unique, it is important to look at the characteristics of innovation from the point of view of services. Most researchers have looked at innovation from a traditional, technology-based manufacturing perspective.

Additionally, prior studies on diversity have focused on developed country contexts and have also looked at performance in terms of profit, board effectiveness (Zheng, 2020; Luo, Lim, Qu and Zhang, 2021); issues relating to corporate governance (El-Bassiouny and El-Bassiouny, 2019; Bhalla and Bhagavatula, 2019); and intergroup relations (Verkuyten and Yogeewaran, 2020; Grigoryan and Schwartz, 2020). Therefore, to address these issues, the current study examines the influence of cultural diversity as a tool for service innovation and performance enhancement in the banking industry.

1.3 Objectives of the Research

The main objective of this study is to examine the management of cultural diversity and its influence on service innovation and performance in the Nigerian banking industry.

Specifically, the study seeks;

- i. To examine the influence of diversity on performance in the Nigerian banking industry.
- ii. To assess the influence of service innovation on the relationship between diversity and performance in the Nigerian banking industry.
- iii. To explore the nature of cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry.

- iv. To understand how cultural diversity results in competitive advantage.
- v. To understand how Nigerian banks, manage cultural diversity.

1.4 Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between diversity and performance in the Nigerian banking industry?
- ii. Does service innovation influence the relationship between diversity and performance in the Nigerian banking industry?
- iii. What is the nature of cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry?
- iv. How does cultural diversity results in competitive advantage?
- v. How do Nigerian banks manage cultural diversity?

1.5 Rationale of the Research

For an organization, diversity has several benefits, whereas diversity neglect has many drawbacks. Managers from all ethnic origins are generally unprepared to deal with cultural differences. The question of how executives can prepare their organizations to embrace workplace diversity is a huge one. The organization is a cultural melting pot, and managing employees from many social groups is a challenge. In terms of age, gender, ethnicity, and experience, these people are diverse. Employees' perceptions of the company were influenced by these attributes, and they continue to affect their performance. The current study examines the impact of cultural diversity on banking innovation and performance.

1.6 Proposed Methodology

The study used a mixed-method approach to investigate the above aims. Mixed methods research can be a useful tool for evaluating complex initiatives (Homer, Klatka, Romm, et al., 2008; Nutting, Miller, Crabtree, et al., 2009). The mixed-method approach to study combines both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The qualitative method will be used to find out

what the problem is, while the quantitative method will be used to see if there is a link between the different factors.

1.6.1 Data collection

The researcher will employ semi-structured interviews in obtaining qualitative data. This semi-structured will make it possible for the researcher to probe into details and unearth valuable insights into diversity management. Quantitative data on the other hand will be collected using questionnaires. The measures for the questionnaire items will be adopted from previous studies.

1.6.2 Data analysis

Qualitative data for the study will be analyzed using thematic analysis, while the quantitative data will be based on structural equation modelling.

1.7 Structure of the Study

This thesis is alienated into seven (7) chapters.

Chapter one (1) is the main introduction to the research. It talks about the background of the research, why it was done, the goal and objectives of the research, research questions, the statement of the problem, and the proposed method.

Chapter two (2) simply reviews the relevant literature, theories, and models to the thesis. The chapter offers the context of the current study by looking at the relevant literature on theories and models in areas of diversity and competitive advantage. The chapter also reviews some of the literature theories relating to diversity in the context of the definition, concepts of diversity, dimensions, benefits, and the impact of diversity as a requirement to improve business performance, diversity management, workplace diversity, managing diversity, and its challenges.

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In chapter four (4), the methodology is discussed, as well as the research design, research population, sampling process, and sample size. Sources of data, data collection instrument(s), and data collection methods are also discussed in terms of study ethical considerations. Following that, the study's data analysis tools and techniques are discussed. The method for testing the validity and reliability of the research instrument is presented at the end of the chapter.

An analysis of the data is presented in Chapter five (5). The results of the descriptive and inferential data analyses are reported. For qualitative data, thematic analysis is also available. The findings with respect to the literature reviewed are discussed in Chapter six (6), along with a discussion of the findings in relation to the literature reviewed.

The summary of the study and conclusions based on the findings are presented in chapter seven (7), which is the final chapter of the thesis. Following that, the study's implications, limitations, and recommendations for further research are discussed.

1.8 Chapter Summary

This introductory chapter has been able to identify the basis of this study. The study examines the influence of cultural diversity as a tool for service innovation and performance enhancement

in the banking industry. This is because services are unique, and highlighting the characteristics of innovation from a service viewpoint is critical. Prior studies have focused on traditional, technologically focused manufacturing approaches to innovation. The study's objectives have been highlighted and discussed, focusing on how the impact of cultural diversity is viewed as a tool to develop a competitive advantage in the Nigerian banking industry. Also, the methodology approach was reviewed; hence the structure of the thesis is outlined in the chapter.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Chapter Overview

This section of the thesis offers a critical assessment and understanding of the academic literature on the management of cultural diversity and its influence on service innovation and performance in the Nigerian banking industry to help address the research objective. The literature review is separated into three sections, namely conceptual, theoretical and empirical review. The conceptual literature review looked at scholarly studies on culture, Hofstede's cultural dimension, and cultural diversity. The theoretical review covers important theories such as cognitive diversity theory, similarity-attraction paradigm, and social identity theory. The empirical review which led to the development of the conceptual framework and hypothesis underpinning the study covers the findings of prior existing works by prominent scholars in the fields of cultural diversity and innovation and competitive advantage.

2.1 Culture Background

The word "culture" comes from the Latin root "colere," which means "to occupy, cultivate, or honor." It refers to patterns of human behaviour within a community or social group, as well as the symbolic framework that lends meaning to that action. Culture is not set or stagnant; rather, it is a dynamic that is always rapidly evolving (Brunet-Thornton, 2010). The term "culture" has diverse connotations depending on whether it refers to the evolution of an individual, a group or class, or an entire civilization (Eliot, 2010).

2.1.1 Defining Culture

Hofstede (2015) states that defining culture to the understanding of the common man is an uphill task due to its multifaceted nature. To wholly comprehend the concept of culture, Yeganeh (2013) argues for a variety of reference frames, such as country, language, religion, value, and ethics, in explaining the concept. Furthermore, according to Usunier, Lee, and Lee (2005), a

definition of the notion should be based on language, education, organization, country, social class, gender, ethnicity, religion, career, and family background. Culture has an impact on every aspect of human life and conduct, as seen by this. This influence, on the other hand, could be direct or indirect, long-term or short-term (Craig, Greene and Douglas, 2005). According to Amaechi (2021), culture is so entwined with all elements of human existence that determining the amount of its influence on human life is often difficult to ascertain. Hamedani and Markus (2019) are of the view that culture is hazy, complicated, and controversial. It's also an ephemeral concept that changes over time as its influences shift (Usumier Lee and Lee, 2005). This emphasizes the dynamism of culture. Culture is ever-changing, but it does not happen overnight (Braidford, Stone, and Tesfaye, 2013). Culture is gradually being penetrated by components from many civilizations, resulting in cultural pollution, pluralism, and hybridization, making culture more difficult to comprehend (Craig, Greene and Douglas, 2005).

Generally, authors' perspectives, disciplines, and, most significantly, schools of thought influence how culture is conceptualized. As a result, there are numerous definitions of the concepts available, none of which is universally recognized. Emile Littre initially defined the word "culture" in a nineteenth-century dictionary to mean "cultivation and farming operations" (Usumier and Lee, 2005). Kroeber and Kluckhohn (1952) found approximately 160 different definitions of culture in the literature. Despite the enormous number of available definitions, they were able to come up with their own. Although there is a plethora of cultural definitions, not all of them are accepted or used in literature. As a result, the following are some often used definitions as captured in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Definitions of culture

Author(s)	Definition	Dimensions
Tylor (1871)	"Culture is a complex and interconnected set of factors that includes information, beliefs, and values, as well as the arts, law, etiquette, and morals, and any other skills and habits acquired by a human as a member of a particular community".	Knowledge, beliefs, values, manners, morals, arts, law, habits

Linton (1945)	“Culture is the shared and transmitted configuration of learnt behavior and effects of behavior by members of a certain culture”.	Behaviour
Kluckhohn (1951)	“Culture refers to the patterned ways of thinking, feeling, and reacting that are acquired and transmitted mostly through symbols, and that define human communities' particular achievements, including their manifestations in artifacts”.	Thinking, feeling, Reacting
Kroeber and Parsons (1958)	“Culture is the content and patterns of values, ideas, and other symbolic-meaningful systems that are transmitted and developed as elements in the molding of human behavior and the artifacts produced by conduct”.	Values, ideas, symbols, artifacts
Goodenough (1971)	“Culture is a system of common beliefs or values that help an individual decide what is, what can be, how to feel, what to do, and how to go about doing it”.	Beliefs
Hofstede (1980; 1984)	“Culture refers to the collective mind programming that separates members of one human group from those of another and includes value systems”.	Values
Thomas and Muller (2000)	“Culture is the underlying set of values that are unique to a certain group or culture, and which influences the development of certain personality traits and encourages people in that society to engage in behaviors that are not found in other societies”.	Values
Craig and Douglas (2005)	“Culture is a pervasive influence that pervades all aspects of social interaction and behaviour”.	Social behavior and interactions
Beugelsdijk and Maseland (2011)	“Culture is the collective identity of communities”.	Identity

Duman et al., (2015)	“Culture is the shared characteristics of a group of people that is passed down from generation to generation”.	Common features
Hofstede (2015)	“Perceptions, attitudes, and practices that are shared and transferable are referred to as culture”.	Perceptions, values, practices
Woodside et al., (2016)	“A complex system of attitudes, ideas, values, and behavior is referred to as culture”.	Attitudes, beliefs, values. Behavior

Source: Literature Review (2021)

From the definitions as captured in Table 2.1 above, it can be said that culture is everything behavior, beliefs, and values. This is because behavior, beliefs, and values run through all the definitions presented above.

Nonetheless, culture is a process rather than a single object, and the total of its pieces can be used to identify it (Useiner Lee and Lee, 2005). Culture is the process by which people in a society are given instructions on how to live their lives. However, there are cultural differences both between and within civilizations (Huggins and Thompson, 2014). This is especially true in modern civilizations where individuals work in a wide range of jobs and live-in large communities. Even if a group of people in a community has its own culture, individuals within that group preserve some degree of originality (Murray, Lazure, and Peloquin, 2017), and each individual cultivates his own distinct thoughts and deeds (Hellemans, 2017). Determining the boundaries of social collectivity within which beliefs, values, behaviour, and manners are shared is one of the most difficult aspects of studying and applying culture. As a result, it may be more meaningful to refer to or consider class, regional, or communal culture rather than national culture.

2.1.2 Hofstede’s Cultural Dimension

Globally, culture is noted to be interconnected, and business environment is even more global. This implies there is high propensity for manager to work with people of diverse backgrounds or

cultures. Most people, however, “are so ingrained in their own culture that they are often unaware of how it shapes their thinking and behavior patterns” (Wu, 2006). To overcome this difficulty, scholars (Bissessar, 2018; Minkov and Kaasa, 2020; Gallego-Álvarez and Pucheta-Martínez, 2021) have offered ways of evaluating countries based on cultural similarities and differences. Suffice it to state that one of such strategies for cultural disparities is the framework propounded by Hofstede known as Geert Hofstede’s Cultural Dimensions (Rojo et al., 2020). There are six dimensions comprising power distance, individualism/collectivism, masculinity/femininity, uncertainty avoidance, long-term/short-term orientation, and restraint/indulgence which are used to rank countries based on cultural disparities. These dimensions are discussed below;

2.1.2.1 Power Distance

This component demonstrates how less powerful individuals of community support and expect an unequal distribution of power: ideas on how power should be distributed in society. The key problem is how a society deals with socioeconomic disparities (Pelauand Pop, 2018). Members of the upper societies embrace a hierarchy structure in which everyone has a position, and there is no need for more justification. In low-power-distance cultures, people endeavor to achieve balance and find reasons for power imbalances. Two countries with a high-power distance index are China and Saudi Arabia.

2.1.2.2 Individualism/Collectivism

Individualism/Collectivism is a scale that measures the importance of individual vs. group interests. Individualism is a tendency toward a loosely connected social order in which individuals are encouraged to care only about themselves and their direct family (De Mooij and Hofstede, 2010). Collectivism, “on the other hand, is a preference for a close-knit social structure in which people may expect their relatives or members of a particular in-group to look after them in exchange for unconditional loyalty” (Alsswey and Al-Samarraie, 2021). How individuals define themselves in terms of "I" or "us" shows a society's attitude toward this dimension. The

United States of America is frequently described as being one of the planet's most individualistic nations.

2.1.2.3 Masculinity

The Masculinity/Femininity dimension, according to Huang and Crofts (2019), describes how society prioritizes values. The Masculine side expresses a cultural predisposition for success, valor, aggression, and financial benefits. Competition “is more intense among the general population. Femininity, on the other hand, is characterized by a willingness to work together, modesty, sympathy for the vulnerable, and a high quality of life” (Minkov and Kaasa, 2020). The broader public is more concerned with forging a consensus. 'Tough vs. delicate' cultures are usually alluded to in the corporate world as 'masculinity vs. femininity.' Japan is seen as a macho country, but Scandinavian countries like Norway and Sweden are seen as feminine.

2.1.2.4 Uncertainty avoidance

The uncertainty avoidance dimension reflects how uneasy people in a society are with ambiguity and uncertainty (Minkov et al., 2018). Its impact on regulations is also taken into account. The main question is how a society should deal with the reality that the future cannot be predicted: should individuals try to influence it or simply let it happen? Uncertainty-averse countries have a strong belief and conduct controls and are intolerant of unorthodox behavior and ideas. These governments frequently require a flurry of rules to keep uncertainty at bay. Countries with a low Uncertainty Avoidance Index have a more tolerant attitude toward uncertainty, where practice trumps ideals, ambiguity is accepted, and the need for norms to reduce uncertainty is minimal (Minkov, 2018). South American countries such as Chile, Peru, and Argentina are noted for their high level of risk aversion.

2.1.2.5 Time orientation

According to Beugelsdijk and Welzel (2018), every civilization must maintain some ties to its past while dealing with the difficulties of the present and future. Different communities place

varying amounts of emphasis on these two existential goals. According to Nagy and Konyha, low-scoring countries, for example, aim to conserve long-standing traditions and customs while being wary of societal change (2018). They are drawn to the past as well as the present, and they place a high value on society's obligations and traditions. Countries that score well in this category, on the other hand, take a more realistic approach: they are future-oriented and promote austerity as a form of future preparedness, as well as modern education investment. In Asian countries like China and Japan, long-term thinking is common. Morocco is a country that considers the immediate future.

2.1.2.6 Indulgence

The indulgence component is a recent addition to the model (Jackson, 2020). As a result of their upbringing, people attempt to control their urges and impulses in this realm. Indulgence is characterized by a lack of control, whereas restraint is characterized by a lack of control (Ng and Lim, 2019). As a result, civilizations might be classified as either opulent or restrained. Indulgence refers to a society that allows for the somewhat unrestrained expression of basic human emotions like pleasure and satisfaction. Restraint refers to a society that imposes strict social restrictions to prevent and control the fulfillment of aspirations.

2.2 Understanding the Concept of Diversity

There are different views on what constitutes 'diversity'. It has been argued that people's view of diversity is not constant as different situations make these views prone to change. The triggers of change concerning the views of people on diversity appear to consist of interconnected factors in the lives of individuals, including ever-changing social and political settings (Michael, 2016). Diversity has been described in terms of attributes relating to new characteristics including "gender, economic class, marital status, sexual orientation, education level, disability and so on". In an attempt to identify a description for the concept of diversity, researchers realised that there are various categories of difference. According to Janssens and Steyaert (2003) "variety is already a first indication that the reality of diversity cannot easily be categorised. Particularly striking in this variation in categories is the difference between authors who study diversity from a moral-ethical perspective dimension and authors who are interested in the effect of diversity on

organizations from a more economical perspective”. Diversity in a team, according to Ely and Thomas (2001), can open up new learning and growth opportunities. According to these scholars, diversity has the potential to increase and improve the organization's growth or achievement of its goals. Diversity is defined as organizational qualities and conditions that are different from our own and outside the organizations to which individuals belong, but are present in other persons and groups (Ely and Thomas, 2001). Age, ethnicity, class, gender, physical abilities/qualities, race, sexual orientation, religious status, gender expression, educational background, geographical location, income, marital status, parental status, and work experiences are all factors to consider.

Diversity has been defined as any type of actual grouping of people or individuals drawn from a larger range of demographic and philosophical differences (Janssens and Steyaert, 2003). Diversity, according to Janssens and Steyaert (2003), has become so important that its protection and promotion must be encouraged because it aids in the assignment of values to people or groups of people who are free of prejudice, as well as the promotion of a workplace climate characterised by equity and mutual respect. Diversity entails more than just acknowledging and/or tolerating differences. The term ‘diversity’, according to Roberson et al. (2017) refers to a variety of practices, including: (1) “understanding and valuing humanity’s, civilizations’, and natural environment's interconnection”, (2) “mutual respect for characteristics and experiences that differ from our own” (3) “recognize that diversity encompasses not just different ways of being, but also different methods of understanding” (4) “recognizing that personal, cultural, and systemic prejudice gives some people benefits while giving others disadvantages” and (5) “creating cross-cultural coalitions so that individuals can work together to end all types of discrimination”.According to Zhang and Hou (2012), diversity in the workplace has the ability to affect innovation and improved performance. Nonetheless, the presence of heterogeneity has the potential to generate conflict, which can eventually lead to the business organization's performance being harmed (Tajfel et al., 2010). Diversity has a negative impact on the operations of a corporate organization, according to research studies conducted on enterprises in South Korea (Chio and Kwon, 2014; Kim and Yoon, 2012; Lee, Kim, and Sung, 2012). According to recent studies, experts are attempting to demonstrate a link between diversity and corporate performance. In doing so, current academics have shifted their focus from just looking

at the impact of diversity to looking at the effects of corporate members' negative or positive opinions on their acceptance of diversity (Lauring and Selmer, 2013). Finally, the categories of difference are not always fixed but can also be fluid, that individuals have the right to self-identify, and no culture is essentially better to another (Hoover, 2017).

2.2.1 Dimensions of diversity

All human being process information and stimuli via what is described as diversity filter. These diversity filters appear complex and are often brought forth by dimensions of diversity. This also causes the formation of speculations often make of people's behaviours, and eventually inform our behaviour towards others as illustrated in the diagram below. According to Bryant and Craft (2010), organizational dimensions comprise "functional level/ classification external dimensions geographic location management status marital status internal dimensions age income work content/ field parental status race gender personal habits personality appearance union affiliation ethnicity works physical sexual orientation recreational habits division/ department unit/group experience ability religion educational background seniority work location".

Figure 2.1 The Four Layers Model

Redacted due to copyright restrictions.
Original figure can be found in Jossy-Bass/Pfeiffer 1998.

Source: Jossy-Bass/Pfeiffer (1998).

Figure 2.1 above illustrates a detailed analysis of the workings of the four layers model. It includes:

1. Personality: This comprises people's values, beliefs, likes, and dislikes. Personality is fashioned during the formative years of a person's life. It has the propensity to be influenced by the other three layers, and it also can influence the other layers too throughout a person's lifetime and career choices that are made by the person.

2. Internal dimensions: The aspect of the diversity with which a person has no power to control has been regarded as an internal dimension. These internal dimensions contrast with "physical ability" which has the attribute to change in the course of one's lifetime due to a person's choices in life to be active or otherwise through good care of the body in events of ill-health through sickness or. This kind of dimension is the main dimension responsible for the numerous variations among people. It, therefore, forms the core part of the various diversity efforts. The first things seen in people we meet, including race or gender, height, and complexion are components of internal dimensions and they constitute the foundation upon which assumptions and judgments are made about people.

3. External dimensions: the aspect of a person's life in which he or she has the level of control is the external dimension. These external dimensions are subject to change over a period. The decisions which one makes in life including the career paths that are taken by individuals are all influenced by external dimensions. Our external dimensions determine the people that individuals associate with and move on well with. The external layer, therefore, informs the kind of friends we stick with.

4. Organizational dimensions: The kind of explicit culture that is being practiced in an organization constitutes the organizational dimension. The organizational dimension is responsible for the opportunities such as promotion, further studies, and preferential treatments one enjoys in the organization. It can impact the other dimensions. This model is considered very important because of its ability in influencing and shaping people's lives and the organizations within which they work. Barnett (2011) has observed that "whereas the internal dimensions of the organization which are considered to be the internal dimensions are offered primary attention

in the event of effective implementation of diversity initiatives, other organizational elements that are perceived to constitute aspects of the “External” and “Organizational” dimensions usually dictate how people are offered treatment pertaining which employee is “fit” or otherwise in the various departments of the organization, which of the workers is deemed qualified for promotion, who should be allowed to embark on further studies for personal development, and the which worker should get recognition in the organization.

2.2.2 Historical Background of Diversity

The term 'Managing Diversity' was coined during the civil rights movement of the 1950s in the United States of America, as part of the struggle for equal opportunity and affirmative action (Klarsfeld, 2010). The civil rights movement arose from African-Americans' desire for political equality as well as better economic and social conditions (Klarsfeld, 2010). These movements aimed to eliminate inequity and unfairness in society and the workplace (Gilbert et al., 1999). However, it has been claimed (Gilbert et al., 1999) that all these activities had some detrimental implications as a result of the low job satisfaction experienced through their introduction. In the early 1990s, true equality and affirmative action were renamed “valuing differences”, and this became known as “managing diversity” (Button, 1989).

To encourage "knowledge, tolerance, and accepting of people's differences," the term "valuing differences" was coined (Roosevelt, 1995, p. 247). The program's goal, according to Roosevelt (1991), is individualistic rather than organizational. While the civil rights movement aspired to provide opportunities for African-Americans to advance in society (Klarsfeld, 2010), businesses saw this as a method to avoid legal action. As a result, they were enthusiastic about the movement (Hofbauer and Podsiadlowski, 2014). The rise of racial works, which were published in concert with the advancement of equal chance rights and affirmative action, revealed a vastly varied staff (Podsiadlowski, Gröschke, Kogler, Springer and Van Der Zee, 2013). African-Americans' acceptance as minorities helped them to be observed and contented with their differences in the workplace and society (Vos, Çelik and de Vries, 2016). The number of diverse workforces in organizations has increased in the United States, according to statistics. According to estimates, minorities make up about 10% of Fortune 500 employees (Catalyst, 2006; 2014).

Businesses have made significant investments in diversity programs and efforts throughout the years, to say the least (Hansen, 2003). Furthermore, Johnson and Parker (1987) explored the changes that will occur in the workplace about what has been characterised as 'different categories,' such as race and gender, in their book 'Workforce (2000:19)

“Changes in the economy will be marked by changes in the workforce and the job it will perform. Five demographic facts will be most important: the population and the workforce will grow more slowly than at any time since the 1930s, the average age of the population and the workforce will rise and the pool of young labourers entering the labour market will shrink, more women will enter the workforce, minorities will be a larger share of new entrants into the labour force, immigrants will represent the largest share of the increase in the population and the workforce since the first world war.”

Johnson and Parker (1987) studied the late-twentieth-century labour market in the United States. Although the categories outlined have evolved, their methodology is still relevant because the majority of the diversity groupings identified in the past are still present in today's workforce. 'Valuing differences' has also grown into diversity training to establish a workplace that values diversity (Werner and DeSimone, 2006). According to data, more than 72% of organizations held diversity training sessions in 2003. (ibid., p. 624). Although diversity training programs vary in depth and length, Werner and DeSimone (2006) suggest that they are effective in improving cultural understanding.

This training was criticized for being too expensive and focusing just on top management without fully analyzing the program's efficacy across the organization. It was primarily aimed at building interpersonal skills for working with a diverse staff (Werner and DeSimone, 2006). Also, the term 'Managing Diversity' originated in the United Kingdom as a result of equal opportunity regulations (Gold et al., 2010). The multicultural landscape in the UK has evolved as a result of migration from Europe and Asia, as seen by the significant growth in the number of

Muslims employed in the UK, according to Metcalfe (2010). In addition, more women are seeking professional positions in the workplace (Metcalfe, 2010).

Metcalfe (2010) claims that while diversity management is internally driven and focuses on individuals, equal opportunity is externally driven and focuses on groups (Metcalfe, 2010). Managing diversity encompasses a broader spectrum of variations within the workforce, such as women, ethnic minorities, and disabled persons (Whitelaw, 2010). Equal opportunity management is concerned with all employees, particularly supervisors, whereas diversity management is concerned with the personnel department (Mavin and Girling, 2000). In contrast to equal opportunity, Scarborough, Lambouths and Holbrook (2019) argue that diversity management is concerned with not only addressing workplace discrimination but also with maximizing the potential of the staff.

When it comes to Equal Employment Opportunity (EEO), diversity management is a more positive approach, whereas affirmative action is more concerned with appreciating differences among employees and removing prejudice (Shen et al., 2009; Kandola and Fullerton, 1998). According to Shen et al. (2009), diversity management capitalises on the cultural diversity that has arisen as a result of "internationalisation of business, expansion of world markets, increased labour mobility and increasing awareness of individual differences".

As a result of the impact of globalisation on diversity management, a dynamic diversity management process has formed, feeding the global view of diversity management.

2.2.3 Global Context of Diversity Management

Some academics (Ozbilgin, 2019; Sukalova and Ceniga, 2020; Seliverstova and Pierog, 2021) believe that the increased interest in the subject of 'diversity' is tied to contemporary changes in the world's political, social, and cultural systems, shifting from a Western to a global perspective on diversity. This can be seen in the high amounts of migration witnessed in the United States, Europe, and other wealthy countries throughout the world, as well as the shifting of manufacturing to poorer countries (Gold et al., 2010). This global movement of organizations,

notably multinational corporations (MNCs), contributes to a better understanding of global diversity. This is seen in the way corporations depict a corporate culture that may or may not mirror the host country's cultural, societal, and legal needs (Soares et al., 2007).

According to Miller and Rowney (1999), organizations in Canada do not consider diversity management to be a priority because the country is perceived to encourage cultural differences (Polese and Stren, 2000). According to Miller and Rowney's (1999) study of 180 enterprises in Calgary, half of the companies examined were unconcerned about diversity management issues but were concerned about regulatory compliance. Many of these people didn't think the lack of women and minorities in top management positions was a reason for concern. 37.5 percent of the 50 percent of companies that recognised the problem were beginning to focus on diversity management to hire the best people. Only about 12.5 percent of women, minorities, disabled people, and indigenous peoples have successful diversity programs (Miller and Rowney, 1999).

In France, on the other hand, variety has been gaining popularity since 2003 (Klarsfeld, 2009). Diversity is practiced in organizations for a variety of reasons (Mor-Barak, 2005), including economic empowerment (Thomas, 1990), competitive advantage (Wentling and Palma-Rivas, 2000), innovation due to a larger pool of abilities and experiences, and society's expectation that all people be accommodated (Klarsfeld, 2009). As a result of the open-door policy, many privately owned enterprises, joint ventures, foreign investment firms, and Western organizations, including MNCs, entered China, resulting in more cross-fertilization and harmonisation of human resource terminologies and practices between the Western world and the Republic of China (Yang et al., 2004). Meanwhile, according to Budhwar and Yaw (2001), Pakistan's diversity discourse takes a multi-faceted approach, with gender playing an important but not exclusive role. Similarly, India has a caste system that was originally based on certain professions but has subsequently evolved into a hereditary structure in which descendants are expected to continue in their forefathers' footsteps. Gender and disability, in addition to class, are two further aspects of diversity in India (Budhwar and Yaw, 2001).

The concept of diversity frequently focuses with societal categorizations, demography issues, migration, organizational culture and practice vs. state culture and practice, especially when

these organizations are headquartered outside of the United States (Gold et al., 2010; Johnson, 2011). This shows that diversity research in Western studies and around the world (Budhwar and Yaw, 2001; Klarsfeld, 2009) essentially addresses the same themes. This supports the notion that many countries have adopted the Western concept of diversity (Soares et al., 2007). Rather than focusing simply on individual attributes and diversity categories, variety embraces social forms spanning from individual personality to social and communal organizations, according to this rationale (Gold et al., 2010). According to academics, all levels or aspects of diversity can be incorporated (Klarsfeld, 2009; Yuval-Davis, 2006). These emphasised the significance of intersectionality in the context of diversity discourse a topic that is likely to be discussed at both the organizational and national levels. Finally, many global firms have made diversity management a priority. This is mostly owing to their global presence (Nishii and Ozbilgin, 2007), as well as their goal to provide solutions for employees in multicultural workplaces to feel at ease and equipped to be more productive as members of a diverse socio-cultural environment (Green et al. 2009). As a result, the majority of companies refer to their diversity management approach as "diversity and inclusion."

2.2.4 Diversity and Inclusion as a Result of Globalisation

Globalization's consequences on multinational businesses (MNCs) in particular compelled the development of new techniques for achieving positive diversity management objectives (Kapoor, 2011), with the majority of MNCs now referring to diversity as "diversity and inclusion." Diversity management has been recognized in the literature as a forerunner to affirmative action and the work of the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (Herring, 2009), demonstrating that government institutions' political and legal compliance motivations for diversity management have been transformed into business economic interests (Lorbiecki and Jack, 2000). Globalisation compelled previously homogeneous corporations to diversify their operations, allowing them to tap into the global talent pool and management (Farndale et al. 2010).

In recent years, the relevance of diversity and research has gained traction in management literature (Kapoor, 2011), and this became even more obvious when the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC) released statistics in 2009 demonstrating that workplace

discrimination was still common in 2008. In 2009, the EEOC (European Economic and Social Council) published a report Due to the failure of previous EOC efforts to eliminate discrimination, diversity initiatives that emphasise the importance of focusing on the potential of "all employees" representing various diversity dimensions, rather than focusing on specific diversity groups, have continued to be promoted, thereby strengthening the corporation (Kapoor, 2011).

The importance of focusing on both primary and secondary diversity characteristics is emphasised by incorporating inclusion into diversity programs (Diversity Task Force, 2001). This step forward in diversity and inclusion was taken to fill in the gaps left by the absence of non-visible diversity dimensions, as well as to add characteristics relevant to employees such as work experience, tenure, learning, and personality type (Kapoor, 2011, p. 288). It is a successful and helpful initiative by global corporations to positively and successfully revolutionize the workplace experience (Ghorashi and Sabelis, 2013). However, some organizations' difficulties in implementing diversity and inclusion programs have prompted doubts and reservations about the concept's applicability (Point and Singh, 2003). Exploring how to manage diversity is therefore an important problem to address in the context of the diversity debate and this has resulted in the need for further studies. This in part justifies why the current study sought to examine nature of diversity and how to manage it among financial institutions.

2.3 Cultural Diversity

Once memberships of a group or organization vary from one another on one or more important dimensions, diversity exists. Diverse definitions emphasise race, ethnicity, and gender, whereas broader definitions imply that diversity refers to all individual distinctions among people. Diversity is described as "a combination of persons with different group identities inside the same social structure" in its broadest sense (Verkuyten and Yogeeswaran, 2020). It is important to note, however, that diversity is not defined by distinction, type, or object (Raewf and Mahmood, 2021). The collective, all-inclusive mixture of variances and similarities along any particular dimension is referred to as diversity.

While diversity encompasses a wide range of topics, this essay focused on only one of them: cultural diversity. Cultural diversity is the representation, in one social system, of people with distinctly different group affiliations of cultural significance (Vodosek, 2007). In the laboratory contexts of the study of cultural diversity, it has been observed that the concept is sustained from the point of view that there is value-in-diversity associability. In this regard, the availability of cultural diversity in the workplace improves the effectiveness and productivity of the company (Isar, 2006; Kottak, 2015). Other field research on cultural variety has been developed and streamlined in the framework of social identity and the self-categorization theories that go along with it. According to this perspective, cultural diversity is characterized by poor workplace performance (Pretty et al. 2009; Mazur, 2010).

When people who work together form a culturally homogeneous group, individuals in the group are more likely to communicate freely with one another because cultural variety is not a hindrance (Lowe and Archibald, 2009). Because members of a homogeneous worker share the same viewpoint on the world and their environment, there are no cultural barriers to communication. As a result, communication and effective decision-making are enhanced. As a result, they tend to unite and generate opportunities for cohesion and productive working relationships (Amaram, 2007; Fasel, Green and Sarrasin, 2013). Using the social identity theory, cultural homogeneity among management and employees has the potential to improve employee happiness and cooperation inside the company. As Trax, Brunow and Suedekum (2015) explain, this progressively minimizes affective conflicts in the workplace.

In addition to the benefits of cultural homogeneity in the workplace, Seymen (2006) posited that the absence of cultural diversity fosters considerable cultural barriers that prevent in-group social interactions, positive social relationships, and easy social intercourse. In this regard, it has been highlighted that the lack of cultural diversity in the workplace does not result in any harmful self-categorization processes or social identity in any way. Hogg (2018) opines that the availability of various cultural groups in the organization increases cultural diversity, resulting in an increase in social categorization processes and social comparison among company members. Eventually, diverse in-groups/out-groups, as well as cognitive biases, becomes an intrinsic part of the company's social dynamics, with negative consequences such as the establishment of

communication barriers and impediments to constructive social interaction. According to Inglis (2008), the presence of heterogeneity among management groups and workers tends to become mild as the company's homogeneity is instilled. As a result, self-categorization processes and various shades of psychological processes associated with social identity theory arise. Also, individual behaviors that promote peace and solidarity among corporate members become commonplace as a result. Members eventually learn to respect race- or gender-based groups, and display behaviors that are consistent with organizational standards or the norms of the group to which one belongs in the organization, and avoid any type of discrimination against out-group members (Martin, 2014).

According to Earley and Mosakowski (2000), as the level of division along the lines of multiple subculture groups is reduced through the promotion of homogeneity of cultural practices in the company, in-group conflict and organizational disunity are greatly reduced, paving the way for inter-group interaction and intra-group communication. Earley and Mosakowski (2000), for example, discovered that in organizations with heterogeneous groups, many organizational concerns such as communication problems, interpersonal conflict, and poor member identification with an overall work group exist. In terms of the state of management groups, it has been noticed that the indefinable issues that come with cultural variety in organizations affects productivity negatively. When cultural heterogeneity is discovered to be moderate, however, Seymen (2006) claims that cultural heterogeneity has a negative impact on an organization's ability to achieve its goals in terms of productivity by creating barriers to successful social interaction. According to Seymen (2006), significant levels of heterogeneity have the potential to diminish these formidable barriers by distributing each group member more evenly throughout the categories of cultural variation, hence reducing in-group/out-group identities (Inglis, 2008).

2.3.1 Cultural diversity: The Nigerian situation

Nigeria is a varied society with ethnic pluralism and rich cultural heritage. According to Ekanola (2006), the colonial system enhanced inter-ethnic contacts by establishing Nigeria as a single

territorial and institutional framework. Nigerians speak a variety of languages, including Igbo, Hausa, Yoruba, Gbagi, Tiv, Idoma, Nupe, Egbira, Kanuri, Fulfude, Edo, Ijaw, Efik, Ibibio, and others, which are used to measure the variability and richness of the country's culture (Amali and Jekayinfa, 2013). Each of these ethnic groups in Nigeria is a self-sustaining biological group with identifiable interaction membership, a shared value system, normative behaviour, a distinct language, and a specific area within the state (Chidozie and Orji, 2022).

Nigeria was historically a result of British colonial rule, and when the Northern and Southern Protectorates were merged in 1914, it became a geopolitical entity (Amali and Jekayinfa, 2013). According to them, Nigeria has been deeply split along ethnic lines from its inception. The Hausa-Fulani ethnic group ruled the north, while the Yoruba ethnic group dominated the west and the Igbos dominated the east. Tribal allegiances, as well as Islamic and Christian religious faith, had a significant impact on the social lives of Nigeria's numerous ethnic groupings. Following Nigeria's independence in 1960, these issues have ramifications for national unity. The union brought together a diverse range of linguistic, ethnic, and cultural groupings, as well as independent communities, sovereign kingdoms, and caliphates, all of which had achieved varying levels of social, economic, and political progress previously (Folarin, Olanrewaju and Ajayi, 2014). They claim that these disparate cultural, traditional, and historical components were brought together to establish a multi-cultural, multi-ethnic, and multi-national society. This organization was employed to suit imperialistic ambitions, which were essential for colonial administrative convenience, as the Nigeria structure did not depict or was intended to provide the groundwork for integration in any form (Ifeanacho and Nwagwu, 2009). This is backed up by Shively (2003), who claims that Nigeria was built for the British's administrative convenience rather than for cohesion.

Nigeria's cultural variety has become practically synonymous with the country's social, economic, and political challenges in recent years (Green, 2011). Cultural diversity, according to scholars, is to blame for the country's low economic growth and development (Posner, 2004a), political instability and conflict (Buhaug, 2006), high inequality (Milanovic, 2003; Barr and Oduro, 2002), and low provision of public goods (Milanovic, 2003; Barr and Oduro, 2002). Nonetheless, despite the public's opposition to the existence of multiculturalism in Nigeria, it

remains a potential road for long-term growth if fully utilized. To support this position, Akanle (2009) asserted that cultures' perplexing ability to foster progress and development should not be underestimated, even when they exist in their traditional forms and alone, much less than when they are harnessed as collectivities in a nation as viable as Nigeria. Cultural diversity is essential for a nation's growth, oneness, integration, identity, and long-term development. As a result, culture, growth, progress, development, and even national integration are all intertwined (Ekanola, 2006; Olutayo and Akanle, 2007; Egwemi, 2009; Shokpeka, 2009). Nigeria's variety defines the uniqueness of its nationhood as a source of trade, invention, and innovation (Aisagbonhi, 2009).

2.4 Theories on diversity

According to literature, theories are constructed to explain, predict, and interpret phenomena, as well as to question and extend current knowledge within the limitations of important boundary assumptions (Abend, 2008). Stewart and Klein (2016) also described the theory as an explanation of a phenomenon based on a careful examination and consideration of the relevant evidence. Theories can be used at many phases of the research process, providing a justification for the study as well as a framework for data analysis and interpretation. It is very important to consider the theoretical basis right from the planning stage of research. Therefore, this study examines how the following theories cognitive diversity theory, similarity-attraction paradigm, social identity theory, and justification-suppression model can help explain the relationship between cultural diversity and firm competitive advantage.

2.4.1 Cognitive diversity theory

The cognitive diversity theory is one of the theories that underpin this study. The cognitive diversity theory emerged through Fiedler's 1967 Contingency Model. Generally, the contingency model asserts that leadership style depends upon the situation in which there needs to be a leader but also posits that there is no ideal leader anywhere; every situation is different. However, intelligence and skills, and other cognitive resources are the factors that influence the success of

leadership (McLaughlin, Bush and White, 2018). Specifically, the cognitive diversity theory calls for the inclusion of people of diverse, different, and relevant expertise or skill sets in a team in order to achieve business success (Chow, 2018).

The theory predicts that (1) a “leader’s cognitive ability contributes to the performance of the team only when the leader's approach and style is directive”. This means that not only planning and strategic thinking will contribute to team performance rather leaders must at all times communicate plans to team members rather than impose or agree with them. (2) “Stress in the workplace affects the relationship between intelligence and decision quality. When there is low stress, then intelligence is fully functional and makes an optimal contribution. However, during high stress, a natural intelligence not only makes no difference, but it may also have a negative effect”. (3) “Experience of team members is positively related to decision quality under high stress. When there is a high-stress situation and intelligence is impaired, the experience of the same or similar situations enables the leader to react in appropriate ways without having to think carefully about the situation”. Finally, (4) “For simple tasks, leader’s intelligence and experience is irrelevant”.

Based on the informational processing/diversity cognitive resource approach, Jehn, Greer, and Rupert (2008) say that cognitive diversity plays a significant role in improving work team performance and creativity. People from different backgrounds that comes together to form a team are more likely to have diverse knowledge bases and viewpoints that are distinct and non-redundant according to the notion (Pöyhönen, 2017). The unique cognitive abilities of team members help the company expand and have a significant impact on its success. Each team member's cognitive resources contribute significantly to the success of not only the team but the organization as a whole. Information sharing, examination of alternative ideas, and study of various perspectives, and team performance will improve as a result of cognitive diversity, resulting in higher quality, better solutions and innovation. Team learning and participation in decision-making are important components in aiding the process of exchanging a wide range of viewpoints. Accepting differences and appreciating the value of individuality is essential for internalizing cognitive variety, which improves team performance and creativity.

Cognitive diversity theory, according to Chen, Liu, Zhang, and Kwan (2019), gives valuable insights into team diversity characteristics and their possible effects on performance outcomes. The value of diversity postulates that exposure to varied or divergent opinions may drive team members to develop more inventive ideas (Aggarwal and Woolley, 2019). Diverse groups have a broader and more diverse foundation of experience from which to generate fresh and innovative problem-solving solutions. Since of members' distinct perspectives and cognitive resources, such as expertise, skills, and knowledge, which may be integrated into decision-making processes, cognitive resource diversity has a favorable impact on performance (Nowak, 2020). Better and more creative results can also be obtained by combining concepts in novel ways. As a result, improved performance is achieved by leveraging members' knowledge disparities. Diverse groups are also better at solving complex and unusual situations (Rockich-Winston, 2018). According to Perry-Smith and Shalley's (2003) value-in-diversity theory bring about more exposure to sharing of variety of ideas and this perspective might encourage people to come up with new principles. According to this theory, cognitive team diversity leads to improved team innovation and performance. As a result, the cognitive theory is used as a theoretical foundation in this thesis to explain the relationship between cultural variety, creativity, and competitive advantage. Nonetheless, there are some theories in the literature that contradict this assertion.

2.4.2 Similarity-attraction paradigm

Although a majority of the studies on diversity have shown that cultural diversity significantly leads to organization performance (Barth, 2018; Suharnomo, Wahyudi and Wikaningrum, 2017), some other studies have also argued that members who belong to diverse work groups may become less attached, are absent from work more often, and are more likely to quit thus leading to increased firm performance (Were, 2018), and causes conflict and higher employee turnover (Narayana, 2018). The similarity-attraction theory, and social identity theory joined together, have the authority to explain the conflicting findings on the relationship between diversity in the workplace and competitive advantage (Schaffer, 2016; Gooden, Perkins, Evans and Pang, 2018). Similarity-attraction theory is one of the foundational theories that try to elucidate the conflicting findings on the relationship between diversity in the workplace and competitive advantage (Kwon, Ha and Im, 2016).

The theory postulates that individuals are attracted to others with whom they share attitude similarities. Also, the similarity-attraction paradigm explains how diversity can have negative outcomes for an organization. On the other hand, social identity theory argues why the relationship between workplace diversity and competitiveness may be negative (Marstand, Epitropaki and Martin, 2018). In effect, the social identity theory posits that when people first come into contact with others, it's important to categorize them as belonging to an in-group (i.e., the same group as us) or an out-group (not belonging to our group). Therefore, joining the similarity-attraction paradigm and social identity theory as a combined force will help to explain the conflicting relationship between workplace diversity and competitiveness. The two theories hold that individual's preferences for interacting with others like themselves can result in diversity having a negative effect on the group and organizational outcomes.

The notions of 'similarity-attraction' and 'similarity-differentiation' have significant consequences for cultural diversification initiatives. They discuss the various effects of highlighting and praising group distinctions. Before any conclusions can be formed, more field study on the importance of similarity in intergroup relations among ethnic groups is required. When some of the groups are ethnic minorities, it is especially important to look into the role of similarities. Another idea is that resemblance will only have an impact when the target is a member of a minority group. This is because acceptance is the "typical" pattern of conduct toward majority-status ethnic groups, whereas rejection is more common for minorities. When the focus of evaluations is a minority group, there is a chance that perceived resemblance will come into play and lead to a departure from the "typical" pattern of rejection (Arndt, Karande and Glassman, 2016). As a result, by combining the similarity-attraction paradigm and social identity theory, a cohesive understanding of why there are contradicting data on the relationship between workplace diversity and competitive advantage or firm performance will be presented.

2.4.3 Social identity theory

The social self, a component of the self-concept known as the social identity that arises from memberships in social groups and social groups, is at the heart of the social identity theory, as

opposed to one's identity, which displays the qualities of individual members (Terry, 2003). The social identity theory's relevance in the context of workplace diversity has been thoroughly demonstrated (e.g., Haslam, and Platow, 2001; Hogg and Terry, 2000). The notion is that workplace diversity, as well as team members are essential social identifiers. Furthermore, in organizational contexts, cultural diversity factors such as gender, age, and ethnicity are likely to be prominent. As a result, understanding workplace diversity and social identity are critical for understanding social relations both within and between organizations.

Perceptions of relative group status and the permeability of intergroup constraints are exact notions that should be relevant to an understanding of intergroup relations in the workplace from the position of social identity (Wells and Aicher, 2013). Earlier studies on workplace diversity, according to Jost and Elsbach (2001), have focused on relationships between groups; nevertheless, both nested and cross-cutting social groupings are likely to differ in terms of status and power. As a result, employees' ability to develop a positive sense of self at work is likely to be hampered by power and status distinctions that exist in today's diverse workplaces, which are deliberately promoted in the quest for organizational performance.

Knowing that workplace class structures, status, and power influence performance, the social identity theory proposes two techniques for low-status employees to improve their social identity and hence improve performance (Hogg, 2016). Individual mobility, which implies attempts to join a relevant high-status comparison group, is the first method for low-status workers. The second strategy, known as social creativity, involves favouring the in-group in intergroup comparisons (also known as in-group bias and in-group favouritism) to positively re-evaluate the in-group. To achieve method two, intergroup comparisons on new comparative dimensions, a change in the values assigned to comparative dimensions, or the selection of a different comparison group can all be used (Huddy, 2001). As a result, according to social identity theory, group diversity frequently leads to competitive behaviour and conflict. As a result, heterogeneous work groups have less internal communication and cooperation than diverse work groups (Joshi and Jackson, 2003). Given the many theoretical perspectives, more research is needed to understand how people of various cultural backgrounds influence innovation and competitive advantage as a result of the multicultural aspect of the workplace.

2.4.4 Justification-Suppression Model

Due to the call for diversity in the workplace because of aversive racism and monoculturalism at the workplace, Hoffarth, Hodson, and Molnar (2018) came out with the justification-suppression model of prejudice which implies that people who engage in prejudicial behavior stemming from prejudicial beliefs look for non-racialized explanations to defend that their decisions are a result of something other than prejudice. Theory about prejudice argues that every individual tends to be prejudicial, that the prejudice is learned from childhood, and that they have a hard time departing from them as they grow older (Dietz, 2010).

Individuals will strive to suppress their bias to retain a non-prejudiced self-image; yet, by employing excuses, they can communicate their prejudices while maintaining a non-prejudiced self-image (Ho and Doan, 2020). Adegbebo (2019) describes justification as “any psychological or social mechanism that can serve as a means of expressing true prejudice without suffering the external or internal consequence. Prejudice can be voiced once it has been masked as socially acceptable (Robotham, 2021). The more prejudiced behaviour or thinking is, the higher the need to justify it, according to the justification-suppression model (Adegbebo, 2019). Essentially, the justification suppression model contends that workplace discrimination is the result of two opposing forces: suppression and justification (Ho and Doan, 2020). ‘The distinction between both forces is that suppression reduces prejudice where as justification strengthens it’ (Crandall and Eshleman, 2003). People hide their prejudice in an environment where they strive to maintain a good, non-prejudice self-concept and disposition to be seen as politically correct. As a result, "an externally or internally motivated attempt to limit the expression or consciousness of prejudice" is referred to as "suppression" (Mateus, 2020).

To summarise, repressed prejudice causes psychological strain, which leads individuals to seek out ways to show their prejudice. Only via reason can this be accomplished (Crandall and Eshleman, 2003). The importance of justification in the workplace has been established in several studies. Participants who were told about a manager's goal for homogeneity in the organization, for example, recommended fewer immigrant applicants for interviews than those who were not told about the manager's desire for homogeneity (Petersen and Dietz, 2005).

According to Robotham (2021), suppression and rationalisation are two separate processes. As a result, people tend to repress their prejudice, but they seek justification as a result of the increased tension generated by the suppression. As a result, the justification-suppression model demonstrated why diversity management is necessary.

2.5 Theories of competitive advantage and strategic management

Researchers (e.g., Furrer et al., 2008; Hoskisson et al. 1999; Porter 1997) have identified that the pursuit of competitive advantage is arguably the central theme of strategic management. Pearce and Robinson (1988, p. 6) define strategic management as, “the set of decisions and actions resulting in formulation and implementation of strategies designed to achieve the objectives of an organization.” Certo and Peter (1990) consider strategic management as, “a continuous, iterative process aimed at keeping an organization as a whole appropriately matched to its environment”. Looking at the definitions of strategic management, one would say that “it is concerned with defining organizational performance, its variables of strategic choice, and competitive advantage. Strategic choice determines the market in which to participate and where to position the organization within those markets, (there are concepts which, as we will see in the next section, are closely aligned with the market-based view of strategy)” (Kotha and Vadlami 1995).

In the study of Ramos-Rodríguez and Ruíz-Navarro (2004), three core roots of strategic management were identified, and they are economics, sociology, and psychology. From the perspective of Ramos-Rodríguez and Ruíz-Navarro (2004), “transaction cost theory, agency theory; evolutionary economics and the resource-based view of the firm derive from the economic roots of the discipline, while contingency theory, resource-dependence theory, and organizational ecology derive from the sociological roots.” They pointed out further that organizational behaviour theory and the structural patterns proposed by Mintzberg (1978) form part of the psychological roots of the framework of Ramos-Rodríguez and Ruíz-Navarro (2004). In their study of large-scale surveys of strategic management scholars as an initiative to offer a fundamental definition of strategic management, Nag et al. (2007) made the following proposals for the definition of strategic management.

“The field of strategic management deals with the major intended and emergent initiatives taken by general managers on behalf of owners involving utilisation of resources to enhance the performance of firms in their external environments” (Nag et al. 2007). In validating their findings, the researchers carried out a second study that involves associated disciplines, including economics, sociology, marketing, and management. Concerning the finding of their second study, the researchers augmented their earlier definition with the concept of internal organization (characterized by notions such as process, routines, organising, internal, practices, and implementation).

According to Furrer et al. (2008), “strategic management was initially a body of knowledge that would underpin practical advice to managers but evolved into the endeavour to identify a theory with explanatory and predictive power. Porter (1985) argued that competitive advantage is a key determinant of superior performance. The superior performance of a firm arises from sustainable competitive advantages that are the result of either monopoly rents, Ricardian rents or Schumpeterian rents (Peteraf 1993; Powell 2001). Monopoly rents are usually obtained from a protected market position when there is a lack of competition. It has been described as a ‘deliberate restriction of output’ (Peteraf 1993). Ricardian rents generate firm-specific resources by idiosyncratic, intangible, internal inputs such as knowledge, leadership and or culture (Peteraf, 1993). Schumpeterian rents come from the dynamic capability of renewing advantages over time by innovation (Peteraf 1993; Powell 2001). The following sections will provide an introduction to the key theories that underpin the study of strategy and competitive advantage.”

2.5.1 The market-based view (MBV)

There are several studies which employed the market-based view in investigating the operations of business organizations. The “Market-Based View (MBV) of strategy argues that industry factors and external market orientation are the primary determinants of firm performance (Bain 1968; Caves and Porter 1977; Peteraf and Bergen 2003; Porter 1980). Bain’s (1968) Structure-Conduct-Performance (SCP) framework and Porter’s (1980) five forces model (which is based on the SCP framework) are two of the best-known theories in this category. The sources of value

for the firm are embedded in the competitive situation characterizing its end-product strategic position. The strategic position is a firm's unique set of activities that are different from its rivals. Alternatively, the strategic position of a firm is defined by how it performs similar activities to other firms, but in very different ways. In this perspective, a firm's profitability or performance is determined solely by the structure and competitive dynamics of the industry within which it operates (Schendel, 1994). The Market-Based View (MBV) includes the positioning school of theories of strategy and theories developed in the industrial organization economics phase of Hoskisson's account of the development of strategic thinking (of which Porter's is one example) (Hoskisson et al. 1999; Mintzberg et al. 1998; Porter 1980).

During this phase, the focus was on the firm's environment and external factors. Researchers observed that the firm's performance was significantly dependent on the industry environment. They viewed strategy in the context of the industry as a whole and the position of the firm in the market relative to its competitors. Bain (1968) proposed the Industrial Organization paradigm, also known as the Structure Conduct-Performance (SCP) paradigm. It describes the relationship between how industry structure affects firm behaviour (conduct) and ultimately firm performance. Bain (1968) studied a firm with monopolistic structures and found barriers to entry, product differentiation, number of competitors, and the level of demand that affect firm's behaviour. The SCP paradigm was advanced by researchers (Caves and Porter 1977; Caves 1980; Porter 1980) and explained why organizations need to develop a strategy in response to the structure of the industry in which the organization competes to gain competitive advantages."

In framing strategy, it has been advised that an overall competitive advantage assessment be made by the companies based on their external environment (Porter 1979; 1985). Five main factors have been identified as crucial in undertaking this assessment. These five forces consist of "barriers to entry, the threat of substitutes, bargaining power of suppliers, bargaining power of buyers and rivalry among competitors (Porter 1985). In this perspective, a firm's sources of market power explain its relative performance. Three sources of market power are frequently highlighted: monopoly, barriers to entry, and bargaining power (Grant, 1991). When a firm has a monopoly, it has a strong market position and therefore performs better (Peteraf, 1993). High barriers to entry for new competitors in industry lead to reduced competition and hence better

performance. According to Grant (1991), higher bargaining power within the industry relative to suppliers and customers can also lead to better performance.”

Wang (2004) has observed that the five-force model helps organizations analyse their “current situation of their industry in a structured way. However, the model has limitations. Porter’s model assumes a classic perfect market as well as a static market structure, which is unlikely to be found in present-day dynamic markets. In addition, some industries are complex with multiple inter-relationships, which make it difficult to comprehend and analyse using the five-force model (Wang 2004). Moreover, Rumelt (1991) stated that the most important determinants of profitability are firm-specific rather than industry-specific.

Prahalad and Hamel (1990) suggested that competitive advantage based on resources and capabilities is more important than just solely based on products and market positioning in terms of contributing to sustainable competitive advantages. Contrary to Porter’s focus on industry, Penrose (1959) and others (Prahalad and Hamel, 1990; Rumelt 1991) have emphasized the importance of the (heterogeneous) resources that firms use, as the primary source of competitive advantage. Furrer et al. (2008) suggested that since the 1980s onwards, the focus of studies in strategic management has changed from the structure of the industry (MBV) to the firm’s internal structure, with resources and capabilities”.

2.5.2 The resource-based view (RBV)

According to Hoskisson et al. (1999), “the resource-based view of the firm (RBV) draws attention to the firm’s internal environment as a driver for competitive advantage and emphasizes the resources that firms have developed to compete in the environment”. At the early stages of a firm’s strategy development, researchers (Hoskisson et al. 1999), have shown that great attention to strategic thinking is given to the internal factors of the firm. However, it has been noted by Furrer et al. (2008) that the focus of inquiry has evolved since the 1980s. This has resulted in the realisation of an altered structure of the industry, where the Structure-Conduct-Performance (SCP) paradigm and the five forces have modelled the internal structure of the firms by effectively utilising the available resources and capabilities (the key elements of the Resource-

Based View (RBV). After the Structure-Conduct-Performance (SCP) paradigm and the five forces resource-based view of strategy (RBV) came the emergence of one of the known theories of competitive advantage, RBV. Researchers have been able to trace the origin of the RBV in Penrose (1959), who was of the view that the resources a firm possesses, deployed, and used are the most important components of the firm, even more, important than the structures of the whole industry.

Wernerfelt (1984) is credited as the one who proposed the 'resource-based view'. For Wernerfelt (1984), the firm constitutes a constellation of assets or resources which are knitted semi-permanently to the firm. The researchers, Prahalad and Hamel (1990) coined the term core competencies are when critical categories of resources such as the firm's capabilities become the focus of attention. In this regard, Barney (1991) pointed out that the firm's resources constitute the primary source of competitive advantage for the firm. According to Ramos-Rodríguez and Ruíz-Navarro (2004), the Resource-Based View of strategy is the most noticeable contribution to the discipline of strategic management.

Ramos-Rodríguez and Ruíz-Navarro (2004) note further that Wernerfelt (1984) and Barney (1991) are credited as the two most influential research works on strategic management. According to Ansoff (1965), earlier researchers simply categorised the resources of firms into physical, monetary, and human. Hofer and Schendel (1978) have observed that these categories of resources also evolved into more detailed descriptions of the resources of the organization such as knowledge and skills, and technical know-how. In another study, Amit and Shoemaker (1993) recommended an alternative categorisation that comprises physical, human, and technological resources and capabilities. However, Lee et al. (2001) suggested that a distinction need to be established between firm-level resources and individual-level. Miller and Shamsie (1996) also classified organizational or a firm's resources into property-based resources and knowledge-based resources.

As regards this, Barney (1991) intimates that besides the firm's resources which are considered general, other resources, including human resources, physical capital resources, and organizational capital resources are also available to the firm. In a later study, human resource

management-related resources were added by Barney and Wright (1998). According to Ray et al. (2004), the resources of a firm could be described as tangible or intangible. Wernerfelt (1984) suggested that a firm's resources can be semi-permanently attached to the enterprise. All "assets, capabilities, organizational processes, firm attributes, information, knowledge, etc., controlled by a firm that enable the firm to conceive of and implement strategies that improve its efficiency and effectiveness," according to Barney (1991), whereby firms with the ability to mobilise desired resources for the implementation of "value-creating strategies that are not simultaneously implemented by the current or potential competitor can achieve competitiveness (Barney 1991).

Proponents and supporters of the RBV are of the view that the organization should only consider resources that are strategically relevant to the firm useful; also, Barney (1991) has suggested that competencies should be considered as important sources of competitive advantage. Concerning this, various terminologies have been employed by various researchers to describe the condition. For instance, Barney (1991) and Prahalad and Hamel (1994) used the term core competencies while distinctive competencies were employed by Papp and Luftman (1995). In other studies, (e.g., Amit and Shoemaker 1993; Markides and Williamson 1994) strategic assets were used. These terms have been used by various researchers as descriptions of strategically important resources and competencies, which offer a firm the potential competitive edge over its competitors. Strategic assets are, "the set of difficult to trade and imitate, scarce, appropriable and specialized resources and capabilities that bestow the firm's competitive advantage" (Amit and Shoemaker 1993).

In a study conducted by Powell (2001), it has been recommended that business strategy should be considered a significant tool that can be used in the manipulation of resources to ensure the creation of competitive advantage. Core competencies are distinctive, rare, valuable firm-level resources that competitors are unable to imitate, substitute or reproduce (Barney 1991; Prahalad and Hamel 1994). Distinctive competencies refer to all the things that make the business a success in the marketplace (Papp and Luftman 1995) and Wang (2004) outlines an approach to firm-level analysis that requires stocktaking of a firm's internal assets and capabilities. The assets in question could be physical assets, knowledge assets (intellectual capital) as well as human resources, which in turn determine the capabilities of a firm.

Maier and Remus (2002; 110) employ the term ‘resource strategy’ and define three steps in a firm’s resource strategy competence creation, competence realization and competence transaction. Competence creation defines and analyses the markets, products and services. Competence realization involves the execution of services, procurement, and production. Competence transaction involves market logistics, order fulfilment, and maintenance (Maier and Remus 2002). Some researchers (Del Canto and Gonzalez 1999; Lockett and Thompson 2001; Ray et al. 2004) distinguished between tangible and intangible resources and conclude that intangible resources are often the most important ones from a strategic point of view. They argue that intangible resources are more likely to be a source of sustained competitive advantage rather than tangible ones. Other researchers (Barney and Wright 1998; Prahalad and Hamel 1990) treated human resources as the most valuable type of resource. Prahalad and Hamel (1990) argued that these should not be ‘locked’ inside a business unit but should be available for reuse by other parts of the firm wherever a potential use yielding higher returns can be identified”. Having understood that firms face in attempting to change resources, Ray et al. (2004) propose that remodelling the business organization’s operational routines, processes, and activities makes it possible to the organization to realise efficient and effective usage of resources and capabilities that have the propensity to result in the creation and achievement of sustainable competitive advantage.

In criticism of RBV, Hooley et al. (1996) asserted that this view disregards the attributes of market demand and places attention on only the internal resources. Some researchers are also of the view that the internal and the external resources of the business organization are inseparable, and therefore managers of firms and business organizations require to find a fit where they combine them effectively. Maier and Remus (2002) indicated that the concept of ‘fit’ is a complementary act between the external-oriented MBV and the internal-oriented RBV. Amit and Schoemmaker (1993) established the vital association between the firm’s internal resources and its external market conditions.

According to Wang (2004), the interaction between the individual firm and the network of relationships in which the firm is rooted is critical for competitive advantage. Wang (2004) also

suggested that an inter-organizational level view be used to analyse business interactions because neither the RBV nor the MBV covers this topic. The fact that there are evident conflicts between the RBV and the MBV, according to Dyer and Singh (1998), shows that existing theories of advantage are insufficient to explain inter-organizational competitive advantage.

2.5.3 The knowledge-based view (KBV)

Researchers (Murray 2000; Teece et al. 1997; Tiwana 2002) who subscribe to the RBV framework consider knowledge as a generic resource, with distinct tributes which enable it to become the most valuable and relevant resource. In their explanation, Hamel and Prahalad (1994) intimate that knowledge is the know-how, and serves as the intellectual assets and competencies which constitute the fundamental drivers that ensure optimum performance in today's information age. According to Tiwana (2002) and Evans (2003), the major significant resource in the firm is knowledge. In his argument Evans (2003) stresses that other resource of the firm such as materials appear to decrease with use, while the knowledge resource of the firm increases with use. In the study of Tiwana (2002), it has been noted that market, capital, and technology, share or product sources seem easier to be copied by competitors of the firm, but the knowledge as a resource is difficult to be copied by competitors. Grant (1996) identified two kinds of knowledge as firms' resources: information and know-how. Beckmann (1999) devised a five-layer hierarchy of knowledge and it is composed of data, information, knowledge, expertise, and capabilities. However, Zack (1999) considers organizational knowledge as a unit of three categories which are core knowledge, advanced knowledge, and innovative knowledge. According to Zack, core knowledge is fundamental knowledge and it helps the firm to persist in competition in the market, especially, in the short term. The researcher considers advanced knowledge as the provider of similar knowledge that the competitors of the firm have and tends to allow the company to dynamically compete with its competitors in the short term. On the other hand, innovative knowledge seems to offer the firm a competitive position over competing firms. According to Zack (1999), a firm that has innovative knowledge has the propensity to introduce to its client innovative products or services, which sometimes help the firm to become a leader in the market.

2.5.4 The capability-based view

Contributing to the discussion, Grant (1991) explains that a firm's capabilities are serving as the source of competitive advantage, whereas the resources of the firm constitute the firm's source of capabilities. Adopting a similar position, Amit and Shoemaker (1993) suggested that the resources of firms do not contribute to the sustainability of competitive advantages the firm enjoys, even though the capabilities of the firm do contribute to the sustainability of competitive advantages. Other researchers such as Haas and Hansen (2005), and Long and Vickers-Koch (1995), concurred with the idea that the capabilities of a firm are crucial to its sustainability of the firm. They pointed out that a firm stands the chance to gain competitive advantage superiority when its capabilities are effective and efficiently utilised in the performance of salient activities within the firm. In this regard, Amit and Shoemaker (1993) defined a firm's capability by contrasting it with resources. They explain that as "a firm's capacity to deploy resources, usually in combination using organizational processes to affect the desired end. They are information-based, tangible or intangible processes that are firm-specific and developed over time through complex interactions among the firm's resources". Teece et al. (1997) defined dynamic capabilities as, "the firm's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments".

According to Grant (1996), a firm's capability is, "a firm's ability to perform repeatedly a productive task which relates either directly or indirectly to a firm's capacity for creating value through effecting the transformation of inputs to outputs". Based on the definition he provides, Grant (1996) splits the concept of capability into four categories: cross-functional capabilities, broad-functional capabilities, activity-related capabilities, and specialized capabilities. Concerning this, Sirmon et al. (2003) emphasised the need for the firm to keep learning to be abreast with time and do things per the trend in society. The researchers were of the view that capabilities and organizational learning, directly and indirectly, form part of the firm's strategy. It has been argued by Zack (1999) that the opportunity of a firm to learn to obtain new knowledge is important as it enhances the opportunity for the firm to obtain a competitive advantage.

2.6 Empirical Studies on Cultural Diversity and Gaps in Literature

2.6.1 Empirical studies on diversity's influence on organizational performance

Existing literature has countless empirical studies on cultural diversity and outcome variables like competitive advantage and firm performance. Pertinent to state that the findings of these studies have been mixed that's negative effects or positive effects. For instance, a systematic literature review by Khatib et al. (2021), Suharnomo, Wahyudi and Wikaningrum (2017), and Manoharan and Singal (2017) have acknowledged some advantages and disadvantages of organizational diversity in organizations. The extant literature stressed that cultural diversity at the workplace positively influences organizational productivity, whereas cultural homogeneity at the workplace may have some detrimental consequences on work structures. Seliverstova (2021) found that corporate organizations that are characterized by cultural diversity benefit from the heterogeneous characteristics of their members in attracting and retaining skilled employees and managers. The company's employees' cultural diversity, as well as their various levels of experience and professionalism, provides a larger pool of labour.

Ilaboya and Ashafoke (2017) explained that organizations can attract and retain qualified and talented minority members by making them develop trust in the company through various means such as offering to them equitable and fair opportunities to progress in their career prospects, ensuring that they are treated fairly and creating opportunities for them to obtain a significant competitive edge over their colleagues in different companies stand the chance of seeing progression. Also, Osazevbaru and Yahaya (2021) found that organizations that are characterised by a multiplicity of culture have the advantage of being able to serve their customers, both potential and actual than a more homogeneous company, especially in the increasingly global market. The reason is that these multicultural companies can understand the desires or dictates of the culturally diverse socio-economic, political, legal, and cultural environments of the various foreign markets within which these organizations operate.

In research-oriented and hi-tech industries, “the broad base of talents generated by a gender-and ethnic-diverse organization becomes a priceless advantage, which makes creativity thrive on

diversity” (Elia Petruzzelli and Piscitello, 2019). Additionally, it has been acknowledged that multicultural organizations appear to be in a better position when it comes to “problem-solving and they have a better ability to extract expanded meanings, and are more likely to display multiple perspectives and interpretations in dealing with complex issues.” Moreover, Giannetti and Zhao (2019) have indicated that organizations of such nature appear less prone to ‘groupthink’. Another advantage is that multicultural organizations are inclined to become more flexible and easier to adapt to changes that emerge in the organization. In this regard, women are highly tolerant of diversity than men.

It has been noted that despite the advantages diversity seems to offer to the organization, there are certain adverse effects it has on the smooth running of the organization. For instance, Richard et al. (2004) observed that in the context of “problem-solving, extraordinary costs in time and financial resources can negate the benefits of synergy, and can even degenerate into dysfunctional conflicts. Diversity can make it harder to agree on a particular course of action and can result in negative dynamics and cultural clashes that can create work disadvantages for women and minorities. Traditionally, cultural conflicts between majority and minority group members are usually resolved in favour of the majority groups. This, in turn, creates significant barriers to full participation by minority members in potential conflicting situations”. Tsui, Egan, and O’Reilly (1992) analysed 151 work groups and reported that diversity in an organization which brings about segregation leads to lower levels of psychological identification among members of the groups in the organization, with the consequential effect being a detraction from the overall performance. This creates a negative effect on the organization lowering the organizational productivity and absenteeism on the part of workers.

However, it appears that limited studies in Sub-Saharan Africa have looked into how cultural diversity affects company performance. The vast majority of research on the impact of cultural diversity on multinational corporations is conducted in advanced economies such as the USA, Western or European countries (Abugre, 2018). Furthermore, Abugre (2018) noted that empirical work on cross-cultural or cultural diversity research is not balanced globally, resulting in a lack of understanding of cultural diversity phenomena in the multinational corporate landscape, especially in Sub Sahara Africa. Accordingly, it is critical that these gaps be filled, as evidenced

by the empirical studies documented above, which aim to empirically explore the effects of cultural diversity on competitive advantage in the context of a developing country. Aside from that, it's worth noting that there have been few empirical studies on the impact of cultural diversity on employee tasks or organizational performance in international firms (Ohunakin et al., 2019; Strydom and Fourie, 2018; Busolo, 2017; Kirop and Oduor, 2017). According to Guillaume et al. (2017) and Arokiasamy (2013), little is known about the relationships between worker diversity and organizational success, and the evidence is inconclusive (Tiwari and Gupta, 2013; Sabharwal, 2014). According to Tiwari and Gupta (2013), experts are still divided on whether workforce diversity has a positive or negative effect on organizational performance. Understanding the impact of workforce diversity on a company's successes, on the other hand, is vital because it is one of the most important markers of a company's performance and competitiveness (Choi and Rainey, 2010). To fill the gap in the diversity literature, studies on diversity and its impact on business performance and competitive advantage are needed.

In a knowledge-based economy, however, a company's tangible assets are less important than its intangible assets (Teece, 2018). As a result, the firm's human capital, or knowledge base, becomes even more crucial in explaining its performance. The diversity of personnel composition and interaction has an impact on human capital (Laursen et al., 2005). As a result, personnel diversity is a critical factor in determining the firm's knowledge base. Individual demographic characteristics are frequently employed as proxies for distinct attitudes, knowledge bases, and cognitive models (Harrison and Klein, 2007). Group participation, social connections, and the firm's structure all have an impact on individual employees' knowledge structures (Walsh, 1995).

Much previous research on the relationship between diversity and corporate performance have looked at the impact of diversity in senior management teams (TMT). The upper-echelon framework investigates the factors that influence senior leadership strategy as well as organizational behaviour and performance. Executives' active background and demographic factors influence how they interpret issues, according to Finkelstein and Hambrick (1990), and tenure is linked to strategic inertia. They discovered, however, that the traits of the entire management team were more predictive of corporate performance than the features of the top

manager. Laursen et al. (2005) look at the makeup of all engineers in Danish engineering consulting businesses to see how diversity in the workforce affects overall business success. They claim that a company's success is determined not only by the quantity but also by the quality of its people resources. They also argue that both too little and too much variety might be detrimental, implying an inverted curve between diversity and performance. Laursen et al. (2005) discovered that combining fundamentally different skills provides a competitive advantage, but they also found unexpected support for a curvilinear relationship between diversity and performance, i.e., that a low level of diversity is harmful to performance and a high level of diversity is beneficial.

2.6.2 Empirical studies on diversity's influence on innovation

Individuals in a company's group are frequently responsible for innovation. The numerous sorts of individual knowledge come into play in the setting of a complex social system in an organization to develop new information or ideas (Mumford et al., 2000). As a result, understanding the composition of persons within a firm is critical, because diversity in the makeup of a firm's personnel adds to the diversity in the knowledge base. As a result, analysing TMT diversity alone is insufficient; the entire firm must be considered. Employees work in groups to develop, discuss, change, and implement new ideas, which is an interactive process. As a result, group variety is likely to encourage innovation (van der Vegt and Janssen, 2003). According to Wenger (2000), innovative learning necessitates a group's diversity of experiences and competencies. Learning is the result of the interaction of various competencies and experiences. However, if they are too disjointed, only a small amount of learning occurs (Wenger, 2000). According to group decision-making theories, more diverse groups improve the quality and consensus of group decisions, but it takes longer to reach an agreement. To prevent a premature agreement when faced with unknown and difficult challenges, some degree of cognitive struggle and voicing of opposing opinions is generally required to achieve excellent conclusions (Priem et al., 1995). However, variety is harmful if it causes socio-emotional conflict among employees because this form of conflict is unrelated to a fact-based problem-solving process and diverts valuable resources away from the task at hand (Priem et al., 1995; Pelled et al., 1999).

Only a few researchers have looked into the link between diversity and innovation success. Bantel and Jackson (1989) investigate how the makeup of TMT in the finance sector influences innovation. They describe innovation as a company's adoption or development of new products, initiatives, or services. They discover a link between educational attainment, professional experience, and inventiveness. In the medical industry, Zajac et al. (1991) discovered that age similarity among members is positively connected to creativity in internal corporate joint ventures. Van der Vegt and Janssen (2003) examine the impact of task interdependence and work group diversity on innovative behaviour in a Dutch multinational financial services organization from a broader perspective. When they account for size and work organization, they discover no direct link between work group diversity and inventive behaviour. According to Pitcher and Smith (2001), diversity in TMT is beneficial to creativity, but it is limited if managers are given directives from the firm's headquarters.

Also, the existing literature shows that diversified firms are more inventive and innovative (Breschi et al., 2003; Suzuki and Kodama, 2004; Garcia-Vega, 2006). Cross-fertilization and spillovers between linked knowledge bases are created through technological variety, which benefits the firm's innovative capabilities. Firms that add new technologies to their technological basis expand their hunt for complementarities and creative combinations (Quintana-Garca and Benavides-Velasco, 2008). A firm's ability to exploit knowledge from external sources is also enhanced by diversity in its knowledge base (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Zahra and George, 2002). The firm's absorptive ability is determined by the firm's knowledge variety. Knowledge variety strengthens the foundation for learning and allows businesses to experiment with new combinations (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990). Through contact and learning, companies with a diverse set of skills, information, and experiences among their personnel expand the potential for new combinations of internal knowledge (Lundvall, 1992; Wenger, 2000; van der Vegt and Janssen, 2003). Different perspectives, educational backgrounds, and experiences help a company's exploratory competency by improving issue solving and generating new ideas (Quintana-Garca and Benavides-Velasco, 2008).

It is required for a firm's varied knowledge bases to interact to experience a diverse effect. Since diversity impacts the way information is generated and implemented in the innovation process, diversity among persons who interact supports the innovation process. As a result, personnel diversity should typically promote creativity while large degrees of diversity may lead to conflict, information overload, and a slowdown in the process. There is a trade-off between individual variety and knowledge commonality (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Wenger, 2000). Therefore, there is a need to examine diversity and innovation within an organizational context by not limiting it to managers alone.

2.6.3 Empirical studies on types of diversity

In their review of 40 years of research on demography and diversity in organizations, Jehn, Greer, and Rupert (2008) discovered that diversity has both direct and indirect effects on group dynamics and performance. Some data, however, suggest that diversity has a positive effect, while others suggest that diversity has a detrimental effect, meaning that diversity may have two opposing effects. Recent literature reviews have revealed similar results (see, e.g., Horwitz, 2005; Harrison and Klein, 2007; Horwitz and Horwitz, 2007). Many field researchers revealed that some aspects of variation have no or a negative impact on performance, whereas controlled studies typically reveal a positive advantage. According to Jehn, Greer, and Rupert (2008), the difficulty in detecting significant benefits of diversity may be related to differences in defining performance measurements and a lack of differentiation between the creative (invention) and implementation (innovation) phases. Employee diversity can help with creativity, but it can also impede new ideas. While it may be effective for small groups, personnel diversity in principle can aid an organization's flexibility and adaptability throughout the implementation stage.

Furthermore, in a study by Ilmarinen (2005), it was established that task performance and age had no distinct relationship. Employees of a different age group would be more productive than those of the same age group (Campbell and Mnguez-Vera, 2008). On the other side, Elia, Petruzzelli, and Piscitello (2019) discovered that age diversity has a negative impact on individual output. They also claimed that organizations with monotonous sorts of labor, as well as an increase in age diversity, see a drop in productivity. Ahmed and Bukth (2019) found that an

increase in age diversity causes communication problems among teams. Kundu, Bansal, and Pruthi (2019) went on to say that in order to reap the benefits of a diverse workforce, companies need to have a mix of generations. Some argue that cultural diversity may either be a source of tremendous success or a source of great disaster (Roberson, Holmes IV, and Perry, 2017). Ethnic diversity refers to racial, religious, cultural, and linguistic variances (Alesina and La Ferrara, 2005). It was discovered that teams of people from diverse ethnic groups make better decisions than groups of people from the same ethnicity (Martn-Ugedo, Mnguez-Vera, and Rossi, 2019). As a result of complementarities and possibilities, ethnically diverse teams produce more innovation and creativity (Lee and Nathan, 2011). Nathan (2015) also discovered that ties between people of the same race have more affinity and vocational support than interactions between people of other races. Selvaraj (2015), on the other hand, claimed that ethnically diversified teams performed worse than homogeneous ones. Hoogendoorn and Van Praag (2012) believed that ethnicity, when used in moderation, has no impact on team performance or business outcomes, particularly in terms of sales, earnings, and shares. However, if the bulk of the team members is ethnically diverse, the extra ethnic diversity improves performance. According to Brett, Behfar, and Kern (2006), a full awareness of the possible stumbling blocks and opportunities that cultural diversity brings is crucial. Jyoti and Kour (2015) indicated that cultural intelligence has a significant impact on employee task performance; hence culturally intelligent supervisors contribute positively to task performance. Also, Okoro and Washington (2012), supporting diversity in the workplace indicated that is a positive catalyst that can attract and retain qualified individuals while also increasing organizational competitiveness. As a result, labor diversity in multinational corporations (MNCs) does not pose an issue; rather, it boosts motivation, which leads to greater firms' performance (Abdullah et al., 2016).

According to studies by Abugre and Debrah (2013) and Fenech, Baguant, and Abdelwahed (2022) multinational firms must give their expatriates global perspectives, and provide an understanding of cultural differences in the foreign countries they operate to be successful. Abugre (2018) and Manzoni (2019) opine that existing studies on cross-cultural competence have not addressed the critical issue of cross-cultural skills as a vital talent that enhances expatriate performance and ultimately firm performance. According to studies, multinational firms are more sensitive to employee relationships at the workplace as a result of cultural

diversity (Li and Chen, 2018). Relationship between people of the same culture is tough, according to Lillis and Tian (2009), but the relationship between people of different cultures is even more difficult. However, if the cultural domains of the people involved overlapped, distortions may be avoided (Abugre and Debrah, 2013).

2.7 The Concept of Innovation

Ever since its inception in leadership studies, the concept of innovation has remained broad and adversely defined (Damanpour and Schneider, 2006). Schumpeter and Nichol (1934), the pioneers of the concept of innovation, define it as a new way of doing things or a unique combination of production elements. Product innovation, process innovation, management innovation, organizational innovation, and marketing innovation are among the topics addressed by Schumpeter and Nichol's description (Talegeta, 2014). Innovation, according to Damanpour and Aravind (2012), is a complete or partial change in a company's structure, operations, or outputs that increases integration with the outside world. Based on this approach, Damanpour and Aravind (2012) appear to propose three possible outcomes from the innovation process: a change in the ultimate output, structure, or method. This means that for something to be regarded as an innovation, it must be properly integrated into the environment, regardless of its source, as this has the potential to affect its acceptability and use. Furthermore, innovation must have a positive impact on the environment, giving a social dimension to the process.

Elçi (2006) provided a more recent definition of innovation, defining it as "constant changes and differentiations in products, services, and working procedures." Because innovation is the total of both social and technological processes, it must be both social and economic, according to Yi, Berry, and Chen (2018). When the phrase was initially coined in the 1960s, it was associated with the introduction of new items. As technical developments showed new methods of doing things, this notion grew to include technology adoption. Drucker (1985) advocated for innovation as a catalyst for advancement, drawing a fundamental link between business, wealth creation, and innovation as a result of the growing necessity for companies to advance economic growth and development. Porter (1990), who was the first to notice a link between innovation and competitive advantage, shares this viewpoint. Another definition proposed by Rogers (1995)

featured and highlighted the entity's use and application of ideas that were unique to it in some way.

Recognizing the need for environmental stewardship, Tajeddini, Martin, and Altinay (2020) suggest a social and environmental component to innovation, emphasising the need for ecologically conscious innovation (able to be integrated into the environment). Gustafsson, Snyder, and Witell (2020) agree, saying that innovation must be both socially and technologically beneficial. The focus of innovation has shifted away from merely introducing and implementing new technology. It has progressed beyond structural, process, and output changes to include the adoption, adaptation, and introduction of concepts, methods, and technologies that can be incorporated into the environment while also providing social and technical benefits. The author defines innovation in this context as the continuous and quick implementation of novel ideas, methods, and technologies that alter a company and its products, method, or organization even while contributing to the firm's socio-economic environment.

2.7.1 Innovation and Competitive Advantage

Innovation is viewed as a vital component of firm performance and competitive advantage in this third industrial revolution period (Thornhill, 2006). This is because, in an increasingly complicated and fast-changing environment, firms can develop and give value to customers while maintaining a competitive advantage through innovation (Wang and Wang, 2012). In general, innovation may assist firms in maximising existing resources, increasing efficiency and potential value, and attracting new intangible assets. Innovative businesses will be better at responding to customer needs and developing new capabilities that will help them achieve higher performance or a competitive edge (Craig and Dibrell, 2006; Lee, Lee and Garrett, 2019). Businesses must be imaginative to attain operational efficiency (Zhang, Rong and Ji, 2019). According to an assessment of available studies, there is a well-established positive association between innovation and business performance (Turulja and Bajgoric, 2019; Tajeddini et al., 2020; Aboramadan et al., 2020; Trachuk and Linder, 2022). According to the empirical literature, innovation is defined as inventiveness, openness to change, future orientation, proactiveness, and risk-taking Turulja and Bajgoric, 2019; Tajeddini et al., 2020; Aboramadan et

al., 2020; Trachuk and Linder, 2022). As described by the definitions, product innovation, process innovation, marketing innovation, and organizational innovation, are all instances of innovation. The study concludes that innovation is linked to competitive advantage in general, regardless of the type of innovation applied.

2.8 Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis Development

The current study's conceptual framework depicts the causal linkages between the variables under investigation. Diversity (age, gender, job experience, qualification, marital status, culture, ethnicity, disability, class, and language) is the independent variable in this study, whereas competitive advantage and innovation are the dependent and mediation variables respectively. The conceptual framework, in effect, illustrates three direct relationships and one mediation relationship. The first relationship (H1) is that diversity and creativity have a significant positive correlation. The second relationship (H2) is that diversity and competitive advantage have a positive significant linkage; the third relationship (H3) is that innovation and competitive advantage have a positive significant relationship. Finally, innovation mediates the relationship between diversity and competitive advantage in the fourth relationship (H4). The study's conceptual framework is depicted in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.2 Conceptual Framework of the Study

2.8.1 Diversity and Innovation

Many scientists consider diversity as a significant difference that distinguishes one person from another. As a matter of fact, each person possesses a variety of qualities and characteristics, both visible and unseen. Understanding diversity, according to Van Knippenberg and Schippers (2007), produces a climate that is inclusive, harmonious, and promotes the organization's strong reputation as one that can recruit the best people in the market. It also makes employees feel valued, rewarded, and motivated to do well for the company. People no longer live and work in isolated communities; they are now part of a global economy that competes in a global framework. There are various diversity characteristics but in this current study, ten (10) diversity characteristics are used. These characteristics are; age, gender, work experience, qualification, marital status, culture, ethnicity, disabilities, class, and language.

Relying on the ten diversity characteristics above, this study argues that an organization where there is diverse age, gender, class, work experience, qualification, marital status, culture, ethnicity, disabilities, and language background promotes constructive task conflicts encouraging thoughtful strategic choices concerning a firm's innovation strategy. This implies that an organization with high diversity is expected to facilitate the strategic decision to focus on innovation fields (Talke, Salomo and Rost, 2010). First, it appears feasible that employees or workforce co-design a firm's innovation strategy because the development of competencies in developing new business areas is a central part of the overall firm strategy, and thus a key part of employee mandates (Auh and Menguc, 2005). Second, the development of competencies in various business areas necessitates certain abilities and views, which homogeneous employees may lack (Tsai, 2021). Third, empirical research has shown that good strategic decisions, especially in volatile and complex situations, require diversity (Talke, Salomo, and Kock, 2011; Mohammadi, Broström, and Franzoni, 2017). In such situations, staff diversity enhances problem-solving abilities and the possibility of uncovering new connections, allowing companies to better comprehend and respond to market changes (Talke, Salomo and Kock, 2011).

Assimilative power is strengthened because heterogeneity in a diverse workforce is expected to aid opportunity recognition, which may raise the likelihood that incoming knowledge will relate to what is earlier known (Mohammadi, Broström, and Franzoni, 2017). Setting up actual innovation fields necessitates top managers to decide on the number of resources, whether human, financial, or time, that will be assigned to each area (Bechtoldt, De Dreu and Nijstad, 2007). The efficient development of innovations within focal areas, according to innovation scholars, needs significant human and financial resources as well as a long-time horizon (Treven and Mulej, 2007). A more diverse workforce is projected to use more organizational resources. Due to differences in information, expertise, and views, such teams are more likely to be able to anticipate future innovation hurdles and, as a result, allocate longer time horizons and more human and financial resources. Differentiation in social ties, such as differences in social networks and trading partners, goes hand in hand with diversity in teams (Hull, Tang, Tang, and Yang, 2020). To summarize the foregoing points, it is argued that workforce diversity promotes a firm's strategic decision to focus on innovation fields by defining, establishing, and allocating resources to these fields.

H1: Workforce diversity significantly facilitates a firm's strategic choice to be innovative.

2.8.2 Diversity and Competitive Advantage

To offer significant value to a company's success by way of competitive advantage, diversity programs must be created to support corporate objectives and strategies (Hunt et al. 2018). In 2015, McKinsey carried out a study to determine if a new competitive advantage measurement or metric for diversity might be developed. By so doing, McKinsey and Company investigated not only whether and where workplace diversity matters, but also how companies can use it to achieve their objectives and by extension achieves a competitive advantage. Their most recent study contributes to our understanding of the relationship between diversity and competitive advantage, as well as its worldwide implications. The study employs two competitive advantage measures: profitability (measured as average EBIT margin) and value creation (measured as average EBIT margin) and is based on a larger data set of over 1,000 businesses from 12 countries (measured as economic profit margin). A study found that having a racially diverse

workforce leads to more customers, more sales revenue, higher relative profitability, and a larger market share. Gender diversity was also found to be linked to higher sales revenue, more consumers, and higher relative profits in the study. Companies in Europe, North America, and Asia were evaluated on nine organizational criteria by McKinsey to determine their “competitive advantage.”

The relationship between cultural diversity and firm competitive advantage was also statistically significant at the board level. According to a study, companies with the most ethnically diverse boards of directors are 43 percent more likely to have higher earnings. A beneficial relationship between ethnic/cultural diversity and value creation has been observed at both the executive team and board levels (McKinsey, 2018). The fact that cultural diversity on executive teams continues to have a strong relationship with financial success supports the premise that increasing cultural diversity in top teams around the world is advantageous. Addressing the challenge of developing an inclusive or diverse company culture across cultural differences could have a significant impact on organizational effectiveness and firm competitive advantage. Turáková (2018) established that cultural diversity among the company’s top executives could send a message to employees and other stakeholders that the company truly knows and values the community and customers it serves. To that end, it is hypothesized that;

H2: Workforce diversity significantly facilitates a firm competitive advantage.

2.8.3 Innovation and Competitive Advantage

In the field of strategic management, competitive advantage is the most popular or buzzing terminology. It explains the aspects that influence company performance (Sigalas and Papadakis, 2018). It occurs when other businesses fail to replicate the advantages of competitive advantage (Weerawardena and Mavondo, 2011). To succeed in the competitive global marketplace, companies concentrate on defining alternative product strategies, developing core competencies, employing competent staff, and acquiring intellectual property (Bhat and Darzi, 2018). Competitive advantage is achieved, according to Wang, Lin and Chu (2011), through the role of leadership, diversity, and the success of implementing initiatives that affect the organization’s

environmental operations. It has been observed by Calantone, Cavusgil and Zhao (2002) that four innovation dimensions such as product innovation, marketing innovation, organizational innovation, and product innovation, are the main factors for building a competitive advantage based on sustainability. According to Anning-Dorson (2018), firms need to make practical innovations to maintain competitive advantage and success.

Economic growth, productivity, and competitive advantage are all aided by innovation. In this arrangement, one company's innovation output becomes part of another company's innovation intake (Hinterhuber and Liozu, 2014). The high pace of innovation in semiconductors (Moor's Law), for example, helped drive the innovativeness of the PC business, which in turn helped drive the innovativeness of the PC business, which in turn fed back as a driver of the PC business, and so on. Successful innovation results in new products and services, new markets, increased corporate growth, and increased consumer value (Yanadori and Cui, 2013). Innovation improves existing products and processes, resulting in increased productivity, lower costs, more profitability, and more jobs (Le and Lei, 2018). Innovative businesses have a larger global market share, stronger growth rates, more profitability, and a higher market value. Customers that buy new items gain access to more options, better services, lower prices, and increased productivity. The nation's "knowledge stock" expands as innovations are welcomed and distributed, providing the framework for increasing productivity, long-term wealth creation, and higher living standards. Based on the above it is hypothesized that

H3: Innovation significantly facilitates a firm competitive advantage.

2.7.4 Innovation as Mediator of Diversity and Competitive Advantage

As argued earlier, shared values, attitudes, and assumptions embraced by organizational members that promote the transformational process are referred to as innovation culture (Dabić, Lažnjak, Smallbone and Švarc, 2018). It further defined innovation as a set of staff beliefs, attitudes, values, and behaviors that contribute to the improved product, service, and innovation performance (Saunila, Pekkola and Ukko, 2014; Arsawan et al., 2020). Consequently, to accomplish long-term innovation, companies must build a shared value system that includes

activities that stimulate open communication, opinions, and new ideas. Internal innovation standards can also help employees share messages among themselves that their creative ideas are valued. When an innovation culture spreads, employees are free to express their ideas and try new ways to contribute to the organization's success (Grimsdottir and Edvardsson, 2018).

It is critical to state that the dimensions of innovation culture (organizational culture, product, process management, and objectives innovation) form the basis for achieving a firm competitive advantage (Ghasemzadeh, Nazari, Farzaneh and Mehralian, 2019), disabling external environment uncertainty (Eidizadeh, Salehzadeh and Esfahani, 2017), and, most importantly, facilitating the development of sustainable competitive advantage (Kafetzopoulos, Psomas, and Skalkos, 2019). It is also the case that the culture of innovation creates the groundwork for sustaining company performance (Chatzoglou and Chatzoude, 2018). The point is that innovation has a major impact on competitive advantage (Chahal and Bakshi, 2015; Chatzoglou and Chatzoude, 2018) and is a vital aspect of the competitive capability of a business (Nguyen, Yu, Melewar and Chen, 2015; Saji and Ellingstad, 2016). Based on this description, a hypothesis is formulated as follows

H4: Innovation culture mediates the relationship between diversity and competitive advantage

2.8 Chapter Summary

The main constructs of the conceptual framework were evaluated in this chapter. The chapter also reviews existing research on cultural diversity, innovation, and competitive advantage to establish a relationship between these constructs. Additionally, various theoretical explanations and empirical data have also been offered to guide the conceptual model's hypothesized relationships between constructs. The next chapter presents the context of the study.

CHAPTER THREE: CONTEXT OF THE STUDY

3.0 Chapter Overview

This section of the thesis elucidates the study's setting. The chapter talked about the Nigerian banking economy. It talked about the country's economic history, the history of banking and financial regulation in Nigeria, corporate governance policies, and a prediction for the future of the Nigerian banking industry.

3.1 Economic History of Nigeria

Nigeria obtained independence from British colonial masters in 1960. The country comes next to none in terms of population in the entire continent of Africa. Being the country with the largest population, Nigeria is considered to have the largest consumer market for goods and services produced and offered in the continent of Africa. In terms of population, 177 million are noted to be living in the country of Nigeria. However, about 70% of this number people have been living conditions characterised by abject poverty (Adegbite and Nakajima, 2011; CIA, 2014). The country has been noted to be plagued with the canker of corruption. For example, in the year 2012 Nigeria was ranked in the 139th position out of 180 countries (TI, 2013). Corruption has been noted as a contributor to the thriving of poverty in most developing countries; poverty in effect, also contributes to contraption, leading to the creation of a feedback loop.

Despite being a developing country, the banking sector has been noted as one of the growing sectors, not only in Nigeria but also across Africa. This is evident from the sector's performance on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), which has been described by Adegbite and Nakajima (2011) and Sanusi (2010) as one of the largest equities holders in Africa. According to the findings of the studies conducted by Adegbite and Nakajima (2011) and Sanusi (2010), an approximate number of 300 companies have been listed by the Nigeria Stock Exchange. The findings of these studies also show that the performance of the Nigerian Stock Exchange was considered the best in the world stock market.

A study conducted by Amaeshi et al. (2006) indicated that the country Nigeria is one of the countries in the continent of Africa and on the global economy with abundance of natural resource. On the oil market, Nigeria is contributing the largest, in terms of crude oil production and exportation in Africa. On the global front, Nigeria's deposit of considered the sixth largest, especially in terms of natural gas. Concerning other natural resources, Nigeria alone has about 34 solid minerals. According to Soludo (2007), since the 1960s, Nigeria has been able to generate about \$600 in money from the production and marketing of oil. Studies conducted by Amadi and Abdullah (2012) and Amaeshi and Amao (2009) have revealed that oil production and marketing by Nigeria contribute 95% of the country's total commodity-based export revenue. The total oil reserve of Nigeria stands at 1.3 trillion barrels. Out of this quantity, an approximate quantity of 84.6 million barrels is produced by the country on daily basis. According to Adegbite and Nakajima (2011), the United State of America imports about 13.7 million barrels of crude oil produced by Nigeria on daily basis. Despite this, the figures in Nigeria concerning poverty are not pleasing. As indicated by Philips (2006), the poverty rate in the country has been on the rise since 1980, with figures between 1980 and 1996 increasing from 28% to 66%. This according to Philips (2006) places the need on the government of the country to adjust policies and establish new ones that would help the improvement of the lives of the people of Nigeria.

Figure 3.1 Nigeria Gross Domestic Product

3.2 The Banking Industry in Nigeria

Nigeria has a banking industry that has about 21 commercial banks. It has been established that 860 microfinance banks exist in the country. Apart from these, there are other financial institutions. The number of discount houses in Nigeria amounts to five. Also, the number of Finance Companies in the country is 64. Additionally, Nigeria has five development finance banks. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) is noted for the regulation of these financial institutions in Nigeria. The Central Bank of Nigeria also controls the activities of Bureau-de-Change (BDCs), Finance Companies (FCs), and Primary Mortgage Institutions (PMIs). The primary mandate of CBN is the formulation of policies and monitoring of the entire banking sector of the economy so that the operators of the various institutions within the banking system of the country will comply with monetary, credit, and foreign exchange regulatory guidelines. Commercial banks in the country perform three key functions consisting of accepting deposits, granting loans, and operating payment and settlement mechanisms. It has been established that the manner in which a country's financial system is regulated and supervised determines the scope and extent of its economic challenges. The financial system of the very country plays a very crucial role in the country's quest to realise socio-economic development. The financial sector of Nigeria, therefore, it catalyzes for economic growth and there is the need for the sector to be properly supervised, controlled, and monitored. Theoretical economic and legal analysis offers a useful normative standard for appraising, analysing, and evaluating finance houses and banks in our contemporary times. Although economic theories provide the foundation for financial deregulation yet, the law provides the backbone through which these processes are carried out. Thus, legal and economic scholars make a robust contribution to understanding the interconnection between the legal and economic systems.

Therefore, activities of financial regulations or bank and banking supervision serve as an equilibrium position where law and economics meet, in other to embrace a more pragmatic approach, especially regarding Banking supervision in Nigeria; we have to go a little bit further, not limiting ourselves to strict law. The issue under discourse bothers majorly on the Nigerian banking system, supervision, and its challenges. Given the current global financial crisis and its effects on all other sectors, this essay provides useful insight into the current state of Nigerian

banks and their corporate governance. It is an obvious point of fact that in the financial system, corporate governance is an important factor. It determines the level of a nation's financial comprehensiveness and development by regulating the nation's market mechanisms". On the contrary, banks are obliged by good corporate governance, in this context, to undertake their operation in a customer-friendly (protecting the interest of the depositors), safe and sound manner. This makes it needful on the part of the banks to "observe the stipulated regulations and laws, rules and regulations as provided for by the overall supervisory body in place" Amadi and Abdullah, 2012).

3.3 Banking and Financial Supervision in Nigeria: A Historical Overview

The banking industry in the country could trace its history to 1892 when African Banking Corporation, was established. The first Nigerian Bank was then called the Bank of British West Africa (BBWA). As a colonial bank, its activities of commercial affairs influenced the financial activities of the country and shaped the course of trade and commercial transactions throughout the whole of West Africa. In the year 1925, Barclay's bank was established and became operational in the country via a merger with the Colonial Bank, the Anglo-Egyptian Bank, and the National Bank of South Africa. The British and French Bank was later established, in the year 1948. This bank later became known as the United Bank for Africa. It needs to be said that these established banks were not seeking the interest of the people of Nigeria, but the colonial masters.

The Industrial and Commercial Bank which was established in 1929 was the first indigenous bank to be established in Nigeria. However, its existence was brief after going into liquidation fifteen months after its existence in 1930. Dr. Nnamdi Azikwe established African Continental Bank with African heritage in 1949. The motive for the establishment of the bank was the fact that he together with his group of companies was victim of discrimination by the colonial banks. The act of discrimination he suffered from the colonial banks made him establish the bank in the name of Pan Africanism. The failure of the African Continental Bank has been attributed to different causes, including mismanagement, accounting incompetence, and embezzlement. Even

though it has been argued that serious repression of the economy as noted during that era plays a contributing role in the collapse of the bank, mismanagement was the main factor.

Mercantile Bank took over the properties of the African Continental Bank in 1931. Most of the directors of Mercantile Bank were the directors of the defunct ICB. After a year, Mercantile Bank established branches in Lagos and Aba. After six years of existence, the supposedly flamboyant bank could not see the light of the day and followed the suit of its precursors; just as with Mercantile Bank its case was a voluntary liquidation. The Nigerian Farmers and Commercial Bank came into existence in the year 1947. The establishment of these local banks prompted the appointment of Mr. G.D. Paton, an official of the bank of England to make inquiries into the operations of banks in Nigeria. The investigations by Mr. Paton brought out certain recommendations concerning the operations of banks in the country, Nigeria. These recommendations were basically about the forms and scope of control the government should have over the activities of these financial institutions. The committee which was led by Mr. Paton presented its findings and recommendations to the government in the year 1952. The history of the banking system of Nigeria reveals that the report of the committee led to the establishment of the first Banking Ordinance Act in the year 1952. The ordinance aimed at streamlining the activities in the banking sector to bring orderliness to commercial banking. It aims of the ordinance was also to ensure that non-viable banks are not established to misappropriate people's investments and savings. It has been mentioned that the establishment of the ordinance has led to the blocking of the establishment of unviable banks and prevented banks from undertaking unregulated banking activities. In the year 1958, specifically, in March, the House of Representatives in Nigeria received the draft legislation which sought the establishment of the Central Bank of Nigeria. On 1st July 1959, the bill was passed into law and was fully implemented. This shows that before the establishment of the Central Bank to regulate the banking activities and the establishment of banks in the country, operations of the banks were not regulated. In this regard, the period between 1892 and 1952, which is before the establishment of the Central Bank, has been referred to as the "free banking era". The period has been described as the "free banking era" because there were no banking legislations to control the establishment and operations of banks in Nigeria. The deregulation of the finance and banking sector got introduced between the years 1959 and 1989. This was inspired by the

establishment of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) which was motivated by the Conference of Bretton Woods. There was a high increase in the establishment and operations of financial institutions as a result of the establishment of the SAP. It was also observed that financial institutions that were collecting deposits increased, with the activity of receiving deposits becoming a norm in the financial sector. The reforms that were brought to the banking sector also led to the establishment of numerous community banks, and finance and short loan houses. One advantage that the financial supervision through the creation of the Central Bank of Nigeria brought to the people of Nigeria is the establishment of the People's and Mortgage Banks. It has been observed that the once vibrant institution, the People's and Mortgage Banks was officially called Primary Mortgage Institutions which unfortunately presently exists only in name and logo.

In the year 1988, the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) was established with the key function being the oversight responsibility of financial reforms and assisting the Central Bank of Nigeria to formulate financial policies. NDIC Act was passed to empower the agency to perform its supervisory role in aid of the Central Bank of Nigeria. However, it needs to be noted that the concept of regulation or supervision being it contemporary or historical, as far as banking is concerned, does not have a universally accepted definition. The lack of a common definition for the term has been attributed to the broad scope of the concept. Again, the failure of researchers to agree on a common definition is partially attributable to its presence in various fields of study, including law, economics, and political science. Banking regulation in the context of Nigeria is concerned with policies, and quasi-legal structures which have been formed regarding Codes, Bye-laws, Acts, and Decrees. Banking regulation concerning the banking system of Nigeria has to do with statutory regulations instead of financial regulations. In this regard, various authors have attempted to provide operational definitions for the concept, especially from socio-economic perspectives. According to Kahn, the concept involves a "direct governmental prescription of major aspects of their structure and economic performance ... control of entry, price fixing, prescription of quality and conditions of service and the imposition of an obligation to serve all applicants under reasonable conditions". Stigler in his comprehensive explanation of the concept indicates that "as rule, regulation is acquired by the industry and is designed and operated primarily for its benefit". Stigler identified four different

categories which are related as offering the best explanation for the concept: “(a) Direct subsidies of money, (b) control of new entry, policies (c) promoting complimentary goods and (d) discouraging substitutes as well as control of prices”. As good as these financial points of view seem like, a huge hassle financial materialist philosophy slammed them as myopic because they ignored a crucial factor termed "The Market." According to Spulber22, regulation should be viewed as general rules or specific actions imposed by administrative agencies that interfere directly or indirectly with market allotment, method, or customer and company demand and supply decisions.

Supervisory Mechanisms of the Nigerian Banking System: Supervisors and Their Roles. Two main bodies have been identified with the key responsibility of regulating the banking sector of Nigeria. The first of these bodies is the Central Bank of Nigeria. This body has been the authority provided by the constitution of the country to carry out the superior regulatory function. The second category with the oversight responsibility of regulating the banking sector of Nigeria consists of the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Company (NDIC), and the External Auditors (EA). The government of Nigeria employs these agencies in the regulation and supervision of the banking sector. These two bodies, like the Central Bank, are set up through:

“An Act of Parliament to regulate and control financial activities and monitor actors within the Nigerian banking system. The CBN’s core supervisory role is feasible in the area of policies formulation, establishment of specific administrative or bureaucratic procedures that must be adhered to by all banks and financial institutions in Nigeria. Thus, CBN is seen as lender of last resort to all banks in the nation. On the other hand, NDIC is known also as a government agency, which is responsible for ensuring financial institutions, paying and controlling deposits in accordance with the in the event of failure of an insured financial institution.”

The NDIC in discharging its supervisory role protects depositors and their deposits in the various banks in Nigeria. This ensures that “monetary and transfer stability, supports, and encourages an efficacious payment system, making sure that dodgy, unsafe and unsound banking practices does

not occur, and where it occurs, it must be checked for prevention of future reoccurrence. The NDIC has three ways in which it supervises the banking system (a) transaction-based supervision, (b) risk-based supervisions and (c) consolidated supervisions. There are also external auditors, often from private companies, providing periodic audits of the financial books and records of the banks”. The auditing judgments that these auditors made were considered empirical because they employed accounting and arithmetic calculations in measuring the development or decline of the banking system in the country. Even though these auditors are in most cases appointed by the banks, they are approved by the NDIC or respective regulators to provide requested services.

3.4 Supervisory Mechanism of the Nigerian Banking System: The CBN

The CBN is the principal body that oversees the smooth running and functions of the various players within the financial sector of Nigeria. The directors of the Central Bank of Nigeria have been given the power to exercise the formulation and implementation of monetary policies. The policies and directives that come from the Central Bank are subject to the approval of the Federal executive council. This has become relevant in ensuring that there is no conflict of interest. Section 3 of the Central Bank of Nigeria Act makes provision that: (1) “The board shall keep the Commissioner informed of the monetary and banking policy pursued or intended to be pursued by the Central Bank. (2) The Commissioner shall, from time to time if he disagrees with the board on the monetary and banking policy pursued or intended to be pursued by the Central Bank, so inform the board of his disagreement thereto, and the Commissioner may submit his representation and that of the Central Bank on the disagreement to the Federal Executive Council (3) The Federal Executive Council may in writing after considering the representations direct the Central Bank as to the monetary and banking policy pursued or intended to be pursued and the direction shall be binding on the board which shall forthwith take all steps necessary or expedient to give effect thereto. This regulatory structure weakened the authority of the CBN since the final authority for monetary and banking policy was with the Federal Executive Council.”

As shown in the quotation, the provisions in the Act ensure that there are some levels of “checks” that ensure that the CBN does not overlord the various agencies with its regulations. These checks tame the authority of the CBN and prevent it from acting arbitrarily. In this regard, it is worth noting that, while the CBN is the primary supervisory agency for the Nigerian banking sector, the Federal Executive, which is part of the first tier of government, has the ultimate authority (The Executive arm). This is a key issue that jeopardizes the CBN's supervisory abilities, which will be discussed in the next chapter, but first we need to understand how the CBN supervises Nigerian banks and financial institutions, particularly those that operate in the country.

3.5 Corporate Governance Policies

The government's establishment of the Central Bank of the country served as the beginning of the corporate governance policy in Nigeria. The establishment of CBN provided a supervisory mechanism through which the government of Nigeria influences the banking and financial sector of the country. The establishment of the Central Bank of Nigeria brings to the fore the principal cornerstone of the banking sector of the country in terms of the formulation of financial regulatory policies in the country.

“Corporate governance policies in Nigeria could be traced to colonial days. There were “several Acts created under this platform, from Bubble Act of 1720 which was passed by the English Parliament, forbidding the creation of a joint stock company without an approval (royal charter), which was done to manage competition and control unwarranted creation of companies to The Joint Stock Companies Act of 1844, which allows the creation of companies through the process of registration was to be incorporated by a process of registration, and the Companies Allied and Matters Act 1990, which now forms the cornerstone of Nigerian Company and Business laws. Generally, corporate governance can be defined as the exercise of power supervision of executive actions, and acceptance of a duty to be accountable.”

Corporate regulation has been defined as “the regulation of corporation(s) within the jurisdiction of the states in which it operates. But recently, Anazett gave it a comprehensive definition as a

system of law and sound approaches by which corporations are directed and controlled focusing on the internal and external corporate structures to monitor the actions of management and directors and thereby mitigating agency risks which may stem from the misdeeds of corporate officers.” In this regard, the term corporate governance, especially when used to mean an instrument of control and intervention (or supervision) in banking operations can be explained in the light of “public interest theory” developed by the New Institutional Economics (NIE) School.

3.6 Interests Rate Regulation

The Central Bank of Nigeria “supervises and regulates the financial and banking sector of the Nigerian economy by controlling the interests’ rate. Even though there was no specific guideline till in the 60’s when section 7(4) was inserted into the Banking Ordinance of 195843.

“This section provided that rates of interest charged on credit facilities and advances by the banks shall be linked to the minimum rediscount rate of the Central Bank subject to a stated minimum rate of interest”.

A similar law made it clear that approval from Central Bank is needed;

“it is a precondition for the interest rate structure of each bank, and that "the minimum rate of interest when so approved shall be same for all licensed banks 44, but in 1970, there was an amendment, creating a special proviso, included in the amendment to allow different which allows different rates of interests to be approved for various categories of banks”.

Between the early 1970s and the late 1980s, interest rates were historically low, and the early 1990s to the late 2000s were marked by either an even or eased rate, but from early 2010 to late 2011, interest rates soared, scaring global corporations away from borrowing and causing them to seek funding sources, such as their parent corporation or international banks.

3.7 Impact of Banking Sector Reforms in Nigeria

Nigeria has undergone a series of banking industry reforms since 1986. Nigeria's banking reforms are an important aspect of the country's overall reform agenda, which aims to ensure that the country's economy achieves the stated goal of being recognized as one of the world's top 20 economies by the end of 2020. In 1986, SAP was established to achieve this goal, allowing for many economic reforms. These economic reforms, it has been explained, paved the stage for a shift from a regulated to a free market economy. The financial sector reforms were the seed that grew into a strong and healthy banking sector capable of driving major growth in the business. Nigerian banks can now be regarded worldwide players in the international financial markets as a result of this (Long, 2014).

To escape extinction and compete effectively in the market, banks were forced to reform their vision and mission, reinvent their business models, and employ organizational development strategies in response to this new development. Numerous approaches have been implemented as a result of the banking sector's reforms. Many banks completed mergers and acquisitions, while others entered the capital market to acquire additional funds through an IPO (IPOs) (Adjasi, Osei and Fiawoyife, 2011). To meet the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) new capital base of N 25 billion, other banks have turned to international borrowing.

According to Shehu (2014), the process of the reforms which also required "strict compliance to the new rules and ethics, abstaining from sharp negative malpractices and ensuring maximum safety of the depositors' fund has compelled the banks to adopt new strategies to achieve greater performance and acquire customer confidence and loyalty in the market. A significant level of achievement was recorded in the 2004 banking sector post-reform. The number of banks reduced from 89 to 25, with a post-consolidation asset base rising from N 2,768 billion in 2003 to N 14, 932 billion as of May 2009, an average of 439%. Equally banks' capital and reserve rose by 192% from N 327 billion in 2004 to N 957 billion in 2006 while their capital adequacy ratio which stood at 15.18% took a quantum leap to 22% in 2008 (Shehu, 2014).

The number of branches grew by 40% from 3,247 to 5,407 within the period including 46 foreign branches (Izuchukwu, Long, Shehu, and Olufemi, 2014). Beyond the recapitalization of banks, the reforms also focused on the strict enforcement of corporate governance principles in banking, the introduction of a flexible interest rate-based framework that made the monetary policy rate the operating target, and risk-focused and rule-based regulatory framework (Izuchukwu et al., 2014). However, it is worthy to note that the concurrent changes that are gradually being implemented in the banking industry in the form of reform must have an effect on the employees' perceptions particularly about their job prospects and despair, being fully aware that every change is associated with opportunities and threats. A considerable number of researches support the argument that employees always resist change because of its uncertainty and possible negative consequences.” Izuchukwu and Ofori (2014) have observed that, even though it is not all of these changes in the financial sector appear to be detrimental to employees as many change processes led to viable opportunities for staff to excel and achieve personal goals, there were some changes that rendered some workers relieved off their posts (Izuchukwu and Ofori, 2014).

3.8 Chapter Summary

Nigeria's total oil reserves stand at 1.3 trillion barrels and 84.6 million barrels are produced by the country daily. Nigeria has a banking industry that has about 21 commercial banks and 860 micro-finance banks. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) is noted for the regulation of these financial institutions in Nigeria. The financial system of the country plays a crucial role in the country's quest to realise socio-economic development. The banking industry in Nigeria could trace its history to 1892, when the African Banking Corporation was established. Banking regulation in the context of Nigeria is concerned with policies and quasi-legal structures regarding codes, bye-laws, acts, and decrees. Two main bodies have been identified with the key responsibility of regulating Nigeria's banking sector. The Nigerian Deposit Insurance Company (NDIC) and External Auditors (EA) perform this supervisory role. These two bodies, like the Central Bank, are set up through an Act of Parliament to regulate financial activities. The directors of the Central Bank of Nigeria have been given the power to exercise the formulation and implementation of monetary policies. While the CBN is the primary supervisory agency for

the Nigerian banking sector, the Federal Executive Council has the ultimate authority. This weakened the CBN's supervisory abilities. The establishment of the CBN provided a supervisory mechanism through which the government of Nigeria influences the banking and financial sectors of the country. The term "corporate governance" can be explained in the light of "public interest theory" developed by the New Institutional Economics (NIE) School. Nigeria's banking reforms are an important aspect of the country's overall reform agenda. From 2010 to 2011, interest rates soared, scaring global corporations away from borrowing. Nigerian banks can now be regarded as worldwide players in the international financial markets as a result of this. The number of banks decreased from 89 to 25, with post-consolidation asset bases increasing from N 2,768 billion in 2003 to N 14, 932 billion in May 2009. Banks' capital and reserves rose by 192% from N 327 billion in 2004 to N 957 billion in 2006. The Nigerian banking industry's future, according to Ajibo (2015), lies in a risk-based framework that follows global best practices and governing structures in banks. According to earlier research, the banking system, which began in Nigeria in 1892, has been primarily turbulent, with waves of failures in the 1990s and early and mid-2000s. This research backs up the idea that capital controls are a typical strategy in Nigeria for strengthening banks and rescuing them from financial difficulties. The Central Bank of Nigeria, on the other hand, has relied on agency ratings in recent years when making regulatory and investment choices. These regulatory efforts are also said to have failed to shield banks from financial disasters (Ajibo, 2015). Therefore, the next section provides a methodology that can be used to examine the framework proposed to improve the competitiveness of the Nigerian banking industry in Chapter Two, under Section 2.8.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.0 Chapter Overview

This section of the thesis goes over the research methods and design used in the study in great detail. This chapter explains the study's methodological approaches and, as a result, describes the techniques often employed to attain the research objectives and research questions. Various philosophies, approaches, goals, strategies, and data collection methods are discussed. This chapter describes why a quantitative data collection strategy was chosen and how the questionnaire was designed to elicit the desired response using best practices. Concerns such as the target responder, sampling technique and sample size, data types and sources, research equipment, data handling, and ethical considerations are all addressed in the methodology section. The methodology also aims to use the most appropriate and reliable statistical method for testing hypotheses. The “how” of performing such research is crucial to the research's success. The way research is carried out is just as important as the findings of the study. The how refers to the methodology, which is also known as research design. The cornerstone of effective research is the development of a suitable research strategy. Different layers of process approaches and ideologies combine to make the design. The architecture for study, or design of the study, could be regarded as the "glue" that holds all of the elements of research altogether. A design is being used to frame the investigation and show how all of the project's key components – samples or groups, measures, treatments or programmes, and assignment mechanisms – work together just to answer the research questions. The research paradigm (underlying beliefs), approach, purpose, strategy, data collection method, and analysis technique employed in this study are all discussed in this chapter.

4.1 Research Philosophy and Approaches

4.1.1 Research philosophy

In any research process, the researcher needs to understand the research philosophies or paradigms that contribute to research quality and originality (Easterby-Smith et al. 2012).

According to Easterby-Smith et al. (2012), understanding research philosophies supports the researcher in selecting and specifying the most relevant procedures for the issue at hand. Locating data sources, determining the types of data required for the investigation, responding to research questions, and supporting the researcher in comprehending the study findings are all part of this process.

Researchers in the field of management have stressed the distinction between the major aspects of the research philosophy, namely: positivism, critical realism, interpretivism, postmodernism, and pragmatism that guide a research study (Saunders, Lewis, Thornhill and Bristow, 2015; Jackson, 2020; Poucher, Tamminen, Caron and Sweet, 2020). For this study, the pragmatism approach was adopted because the researcher believes that objectivism and subjectivism, facts and values, precise and rigorous knowledge, and various contextualised experiences are all important (Saunders et al., 2015). As a result, the researcher admits the possibility of a single or several realities that can be investigated empirically (Creswell and Clark, 2011). Pragmatist scholars “recognize that there are many different ways of interpreting the world and undertaking research, that no single point of view can ever give the entire picture, and that there may be multiple realities” (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Hence, pragmatism philosophy is often linked with mixed-methods or multiple methods (see Biesta 2010; Creswell and Clark 2011).

4.1.2 Approach to theory development

A research approach can be defined as the plan and procedure which consists of the steps and the detailed procedure used in conducting the research in a specific area or on a particular topic. This includes the data collection, data analysis, and data interpretation. Often the selection of the research approach is based on the nature of the research problem and the objectives being set in the study. The approach to data collecting and the strategy to data analysis are the two main types of research approaches. The research approach also guides the methodological choices of the research namely, quantitative, qualitative and or mixed-method.

There are two main research approaches namely inductive and deductive. The inductive approach, which is sometimes referred to as inductive reasoning, which commends the researcher's procedure as an awareness before the theory is proposed out to be an observation at the end of the research process. Neither a theory nor hypothesis applies to inductive research from the beginning of the research. The researcher is thus free and therefore can alter the course of the researcher after it has been started. It needs to be mentioned that the inductive approach to a research study does not mean the researcher does not employ a theory in the analysis or formulating the research objectives and questions. The inductive approach only seeks to produce meanings from the data set gathered to ascertain the patterns and relationships upon which a theory may be proposed (Patton, 1990).

The deductive approach on the other hand is concerned with “developing a hypothesis (or hypotheses) based on existing theories and then designing a research strategy to test the hypothesis” (Manna and Waldinger, 1980). It has been indicated that deductive means reasoning from the particular to the general. A deductive design “might test to see if this relationship or link did obtain on more general circumstances” (Gallaire et al., 1989). The deductive approach can be explained by the means of hypotheses, which can be derived from the propositions of the theory. In other words, the deductive approach is concerned with deducting conclusions from premises or propositions. The deduction begins with an expected pattern “that is tested against observations, whereas induction begins with observations and seeks to find a pattern within them” (Manna and Waldinger, 1980). The deductive research approach explores a known theory or phenomenon and tests if that theory is valid in given circumstances.

It has been noted that “the deductive approach follows the path of logic most closely” (Berger, 1977). The reasoning “starts with a theory and leads to a new hypothesis and this hypothesis is put to the test by confronting it with observations that either lead to a confirmation or a rejection of the hypothesis” (Pearl, 2014). Moreover, deductive reasoning can be explained as “reasoning from the general to the particular”, whereas inductive reasoning is the opposite. In other words, the deductive approach involves the formulation of hypotheses and their subjection to testing during the research process, while inductive studies do not deal with hypotheses in any way.

In this study, both a deductive and an inductive approach were adopted. The inductive approach analysis was conducted to help discover themes relating to cultural diversity, competitive advantage, and its management in the Nigerian banking industry. On the other hand, the deductive approach was used in this study for testing or confirming hypotheses on the relationship between diversity, innovation, and competitive advantage within the Nigerian banking industry.

4.2 Methodological Choice

There are three main methodological choices in a research study, namely; qualitative research method, quantitative research method, and mix-method (Cortini, 2014). When doing an exploratory study or when there is a limited theoretical understanding of the phenomenon (i.e., when the research field is new) the qualitative approach is usually preferred (Creswell and Plano, 2013). The qualitative approach allows you to investigate the phenomena further, explore the research problem in greater depth, and eventually establish a foundation for conceptions or theories (Pearl, 2014). The subjectivity and narrative form of the argument is the fundamental disadvantages of the qualitative technique, which contributes to the perception that validity and reliability in qualitative research are difficult to resolve. When the goal is to verify current ideas or test hypotheses created based on earlier research, the quantitative technique is typically used. The quantitative method's key advantage is the ability to obtain an objective and accurate appraisal of a social phenomenon or human behaviour. However, whether such a complicated phenomenon as human conduct can be accurately explained using statistics is a point of contention. Personal interpretations and feelings, which are a natural part of social research, are difficult to quantify with statistics or counts (Sullivan, 2001; Hair et al. 2003).

Mixed-methodologies data collection and analysis refers to the collecting and analysis of data using both qualitative and quantitative methods (Creswell and Clark, 2007). Rather than focusing on a single strategy, the approach emphasises the idea that combining quantitative and qualitative approaches increases research quality and provides a comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the subject at hand (Creswell, 2014). Three forms of mixed approaches have been identified in social science research: contemporaneous, sequential, and embedded (Johnson et al. 2007).

Concurrent mixed methods (triangulation) combine qualitative and quantitative approaches to provide an in-depth look at the study topic. In embedded mixed approaches, one methodology complements the other (Blaikie, 2010). Sequential mixed-methods research builds on one method's findings with another and may start with a qualitative interview to study the topic, followed by a quantitative survey to generalize the findings (i.e., exploratory sequence). To prove a theory, a quantitative method could be utilized, followed by a qualitative examination of a few cases (explanatory sequence) (Creswell and Clark, 2010). Mixed methods research takes time and does not provide researchers with proficiency in a specific method, but it does encourage the use of both approaches simultaneously (Creswell and Plano, 2013). According to academics, it is a crucial part of knowledge generation that researchers should consider (e.g., Creswell, 2014).

To gather, analyze, and combine quantitative and qualitative research data, this study used a mixed methodologies research technique (Creswell and Plano, 2013). This method of investigation was the greatest fit for reaching the research objectives because there was little evidence guiding the management of cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry, to begin with. This bolstered the argument for exploratory qualitative research aimed at elucidating unknown or inarticulate phenomena, particularly in unique contexts like Nigeria's financial system (Morse, 1994; Sofaer, 1999). Second, to investigate hypothesis relationships, quantitative approaches must be used. As a result, using sequential quantitative and qualitative data collection with equally weighted results was the most appropriate strategy to explore cultural diversity management and its impact on service innovation and performance in the Nigerian banking business.

4.3 Population and Sampling

When conducting research, it is vital to identify the appropriate demographic or population. As a result, to conduct a full study, a population sample from the target group is required. According to Collis and Hussy, "population" is a group of people on which the study is conducted (2013). "The population is made up of the individuals, locations, and events that contribute to the study's data source," Flick (2014) explains. To satisfy the study's objectives, the population of this study

includes employees of commercial banks in Nigeria during the sample period. Because the researcher is unable to interview the complete population, he or she chooses a representative sample of that population, which is referred to as the population sample (Creswell, 2009). The population sample, according to Collis and Hussey (2003), is a percentage of the total population. They went on to state that the researcher has complete control over the number of participants in the population sample. Probability and non-probability sampling are the two primary types of sample procedures (Callegaro, Villar, Yeager, and Krosnick, 2014), and both were utilized in this study. Probability sampling is often connected with surveys and experimental research, in which each member of the population has an equal chance of being chosen, whereas non-probability sampling is concerned with personal judgment (Saunders et al., 2011). Making meaningful inferences about the population of interest becomes challenging when the former is used. Despite this, Saunders et al. (2009) claim that non-probability sampling research is theoretical and cannot statistically generalize its target population.

To select the banks for this study, a probability sampling method known as random sampling was employed to select the six (6) commercial banks for the study. This method was employed to provide every bank in Nigeria with an equal chance of being selected (Creswell, 2009). To achieve this, every commercial bank in Nigeria is coded with a unique number on a sheet of paper, packed in a container, and extensively shuffled throughout the sample period. After that, a coded piece of paper is withdrawn from the container one by one and not replaced until all six banks have been chosen. This method helped to eliminate any bias associated with the study's bank selection (Saunders et al., 2015). The convenience sample technique, which is a non-probability sampling technique, was used to choose employees at their Lagos headquarters for the quantitative study. Researchers use non-probability sampling procedures to acquire a better understanding of the sample population, according to Brick (2015). Convenience sampling is used to include participants in the research study who are more easily accessible to the researcher (Suen, Huang, and Lee, 2014). According to Suen et al. (2014), one advantage of convenience sampling is the ease with which willing and available persons can be recruited. Purposive sampling methodology was used to select respondents from the chosen banks for the qualitative study, as it is a non-probability sample method. Due to the nature of the study goals, a purposive selection strategy was used to select people who could serve as primary data sources (Saunders

et al., 2015). Because banks make strategic decisions, the qualitative research focuses on Chief Executive Officers (CEOs), Managing Directors (MDs), and Top Managers (TMs).

4.3.1 Sample Size

A researcher's sample size is a subset of the population chosen for a study to make generalisations and inferences about the greater population (Sekaran, 2000; Newman, 2014). The goal of sampling is to provide a limited group of data that is representative of the larger picture. Employees were sampled for the quantitative study using Miller and Brewer's (2003) sample size proportion calculation, which is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(\alpha^2)}$$

Where n = sample size, N = Target population and α = error term. The total number of employees from all sizes of the selected banks = 1,950. Thus, $N = 1,950$. Therefore, $1,950 / 1 + 1,950(0.05^2) = 331.91$. From the above sample size formula, a total number of three hundred thirty-six (336) questionnaires were administered to respondents. Hence, fifty-six (56) questionnaires were administered to each of the six banks. After the data collection process, three hundred twenty (320) individuals participated in the study. Yet, three hundred five (305) were collected filled, and used for the study.

The saturation strategy was used to determine the sample size for qualitative research. Saturation occurs when no new or meaningful pattern arises; each category is well-developed in terms of ideas and attributes, and the interplays between the categories are logically discernible (Velayati, Shabani and Nazarian, 2020). Before saturation was attained, twenty-four (24) semi-structured interviews were conducted.

4.4 Data Collection

Primary data and secondary data were employed in the research. A survey questionnaire and semi-structured interview were used to obtain primary data.

4.4.1 Qualitative data collection

Qualitative data were collected via interviews. The interview guide is presented in Appendix B. All of the interviews were done by a single researcher to ensure consistency (Edirisnghe et al., 2020). Contacts were made by phone and email before the interviews, with invites sent electronically. The interviews lasted between 40 and 65 minutes on average. Before the meeting, each respondent was given a summary of the research purpose. Respondents were informed that participation was optional and that they might opt out of the study at any time. This was done to comply with ethical standards. The participants were also guaranteed that their identities would not be revealed. The respondents were invited to expound on their ideas during the interviews, with the researcher asking follow-up questions as needed. The interviews were taped and subsequently transcribed with the participants' permission. For information and data, secondary data was acquired via reading journal papers, books, journals, and other published objects.

4.4.2 Quantitative data collection

Questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data for this investigation. According to Oppenheim (2008), a questionnaire is a key tool for research evaluation, not some type of formal form with hastily jotted-down questions. In reality, a questionnaire is a frequent marketing research method (Churchill, 1995) and a common sub-element of the data collection process (Malhotra and Birks, 2007). The benefits of using questionnaires include the ease with which they may be tabulated and analysed (Peterson, 2000), as well as the reliability they provide due to the framework of set options (Smith and Albaum, 2005). However, because the respondent does not have the choice to react in his own words, he may be forced to choose an option that does not accurately portray the genuine scenario (Churchill, 1995). Nonetheless, in business and management research, it is one of the most effective methods of data collection.

4.5 Ethical Considerations

Some guidelines must be followed while performing the study; as a consequence, the analyst established some ethical limits, which were acknowledged by managers of one of Nigeria's top

commercial banks. According to Munhall (1988), the privacy and safety of the chosen sample are crucial, and analysts must ensure that no member of the public is harmed as a result of the research. As a result, measures for risk mitigation must be established. The mental states of the respondents are crucial for the study, which should be free of outside influences and entirely dependent on the comfort of the interviews. According to (Silverman, 2013), the analyst should not employ compulsion to elicit the intended responses, and all data collected should be discrete and, in most cases, anonymous to protect the data from misuse. As a result of these ethical considerations, after the evaluation method was concluded, the analyst removed all gathered data from all mediums, allowing the respondents to feel safe and secure regarding their views.

4.5.1 Right to Self-Determination

A study conducted by Collis and Hussey (2013) revealed that the samples the researcher draws for the study “cannot be used for the study without their approval and therefore forcing them to actively participate in the study is considered unethical. Yin (2014) explains that to adequately cater to this consideration, the research participants must be told both goals and aims of the study, in a language that they clearly understand. In this study, the respondents were told the purpose of the study, and the also no financial benefits were mentioned. They were also made to understand that they could opt out of the study; they quit at any minute they wished to. To ensure that all the documentations are legal, a written and a verbal agreement was undertaken with the respondents to avoid any misunderstandings in the later stages”. This information can be seen on the questionnaire.

4.5.2 Right to Full Disclosure

The consent of the research participants was sought before the commencement of the study. This was done to ensure compliance with ethical considerations of research. The study’s objectives and the fact that they have the liberty to quit at any time were made known to the research respondents (Gao and Low, 2014). This is the foundation for the self-determination step, which involves disclosing the details of the questions and the study's goals to the participants ahead of

time to acquire their trust and interest. An unbiased attitude and suitable approach toward the responders are necessary for a flawless study of the issue.

Participants should be chosen based on the study's aims rather than the analysts' preferences, according to Yin (2010).

- a. At no stage should any judgment or assumptions be drawn about those who stopped or shifted away from the study's focus.
- b. The analysts should address the respondents' concerns and queries about the study at every level of the process.
- c. Because the analyst must evaluate the norms and traditions of every group and religion, each respondent's views and cultural notions should be respected.
- d. It is critical to maintaining a positive attitude toward the participants.
- e. Participants in the study should be chosen based on their knowledge and experiences.

This right, according to Kincheloe et al. (2011), is concerned with the confidentiality of obtained data as well as the preservation of their ideas without being abused. The respondents' identities were protected, and they answered the questions in a pleasant and relaxing environment, devoid of any pressure or coercion, with the confidentiality and discretion of their responses taken into account. Although the interviews were filmed, the interviewees' identity was guaranteed, and anonymous remarks were taken to ensure perfect fidelity. In this method, the respondent's personal information would not obstruct the analysis.

He made the following methods to strengthen the analyst's credibility and discretion:

- a. All information was kept under lock and key, and no one was allowed to share it.
- b. The recorded responses and data were maintained separately from the respondents' personal information to protect anonymity.
- c. In addition, the respondents' identities were concealed, and no recordings bearing their names were made.

There are numerous institutions that are concerned with the issue of copyrights and the duplication of material content. It is therefore required that any idea that is not the author' should

be properly acknowledged through citation and referencing. If someone's idea is quoted, the appropriate formats are used in order not to tamper with the credibility of the author or any particular research findings. In this study, the researcher has followed the adopted referencing style to adequately cite and reference all secondary sources consulted in the study. Additionally, instead of using secondary data for the conclusions, the data obtained from other researchers were used for analysis.

4.6 Generalisation, Validity, and Reliability of the Research

Researchers have devised strategies for ensuring the data's reliability and validity, highlighting the importance of these features in any research project (Yin, 2014). For this study, the researcher focused on the behaviour and characteristics of the population sample rather than statistical testing. To gain a better understanding of the sample's features, statistical hypothesis testing was used. They also examined how respondents replied to the questions posed during the interviews.

4.6.1 Generalisation

According to Yin (2014), in quantitative research, findings from a sample population can be extrapolated to the full community, but this is not possible in qualitative research, which is both a benefit and a drawback for the researchers doing the study. Analysing the data collected can be a time-consuming and expensive process. Generalizing the data, on the other hand, is a considerably simpler and faster operation (Rennie, 2012; Gao and Low, 2014). The findings of the population sample research would be recognized as the population's overall answer, implying that responses from a portion of the population reflect the population's overall perception (Rennie, 2012).

4.6.2 Validity

Validation is essential to confirm and check that the research is carried out following the study's objectives and aims, according to Gao and Low (2014). In each research study, this is a crucial

step. According to Kincheloe et al. (2011), to establish whether the responses are genuine and original, it is crucial to pay great attention to the respondent's conduct. The sample population was chosen because it is easily available and relevant to the study, and it may be re-gathered if necessary. According to Bell and Bryman (2007), these measures are necessary to confirm that the study is legitimate.

4.6.3 Reliability

According to Silverman (2013), reliability is a crucial technique for verifying the research's consistency and constancy. In this study, the researcher accurately distinguishes relevant secondary information entities, ensuring that the data acquired and the findings made are transparent, authentic, and trustworthy. The demography was not chosen at random, and the questions were also pertinent to the study's focus.

4.7 Data Analysis

The methods utilized to analyse the data for this study are described in this section. Quantitative and qualitative data analyses are the two most popular data analysis approaches. The numerical representation and manipulation of observations/data with the goal of describing and interpreting the phenomena that those observations/data reflect is known as quantitative analysis. Qualitative analysis is the “non-numerical exploration and interpretation of observations with the goal of uncovering underlying meanings and patterns of relationships” (Babbie, 2004).

4.7.2 Quantitative data analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22.0 and Amos 23 were used to conduct the quantitative analysis in this study. These programs have been widely used as quantitative data analysis tools by researchers in the field (Roy and Banerjee 2012; Asamoah, 2014). Before transferring the raw data to Amos for further analysis, SPSS was used for initial coding and inputting of the raw data, as well as data filtering and exploratory factor. Before beginning data analysis, double-check that the data set is free of errors. This is due to the fact

that data input errors are widespread, which could muddy the study's findings. Pallant (2011) goes on to say that not only are some studies more prone to "outliers," or results that are significantly lower or higher than the norm, but that the data screening process itself has three steps: Step 1: Look for errors - for each of your variables, look for scores that are out of range (that is, outside the range of possible values). step 2: locate the data file error - discover where the data file error happened (which case is relevant); step 3: resolving data file issues – each variable was subjected to a thorough data screening process to look for out-of-range, missing, or incorrectly recorded scores, but no inconsistencies were detected.

The hypotheses were examined using a two-stage structural equation modeling (SME) approach to achieve the goals. The one-stage method examines the measurement items' reliability and validity (Meldrum, 2010), whereas the two-stage method examines the suggested framework's reliability and validity (Kline, 2005; Schumacker and Lomax, 2010). Hair et al., 2010, Hair et al., 2010, Hair et al., 2010, Hair et al. when cause and effect relationships among several latent components are required, SEM looks to be a widely used multivariate statistical approach, particularly in management research (Hair et al., 2011). According to Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), a set of equations that determines the structure of relationships among observed and unobserved (latent) types of variables (McQuitty and Wolf, 2013). According to McIntosh (2007), SEM is a set of statistical processes used to verify a conceptual or theoretical model. One or more observable variables are used to measure a model that defines the latent variables, and the latent variables are connected using a structural regression model (Hair et al., 2010). While some scholars argue that SEM does not study or "prove" causation in the natural sciences (e.g., Bagozzi and Yi, 2012), others (e.g., Byrne, 2013) argue that the technique analyses and evaluates the impact of one construct on another within a fully described model.

Based on scholarly claims that it can help overcome the constraint of first-generation statistical approaches, SEM was chosen as the major data analysis tool for this investigation. Path analysis, factor analysis, and multiple regressions are all examples of SEM techniques that can be used to evaluate complicated interrelated dependent connections between variables (Eid, Courvoisier, and Lischetzke, 2012). The technique also assesses the un-dimensionality, reliability, and validity of each construct in the model, as well as the impact of measurement errors on the

structural coefficients of the relationship (Kline, 2005). SEM serves an integrative function, according to Bagozzi and Yi (2012), by (1) assisting researchers in more precisely defining hypotheses and operationalizing constructs, (2) considering the reliability of measures in tests of hypotheses in ways that go beyond the averaging of multi-measures of constructs, and (3) guiding exploratory and confirmatory research in a way that combines self-initiated and self-directed research. As a result, SEM is appropriate for assisting this study in defining, “estimating, and testing the research model using a causal path diagram that depicts the hypothesized interrelationships among the study variables, as well as modifying and deleting any causal paths that do not fit with the principal model using a causal path diagram” (Kline, 2011).

4.7.2 Qualitative data analysis and data coding

Interviews were recorded and transcribed. The researcher used ATLAS to make verbatim transcriptions of audio recordings. The goal of transcription was to capture the entire statements of both the interviewer and the interviewee while leaving out trivial words like "uhms," "well," and so on. The researcher used ATLAS to prepare the qualitative analysis. The transcripts were used to identify the emerging themes for various sections (Schulenberg, 2007). The categorization technique was carried out after the themes were identified, which involved taking the information units (themes) produced during the unitizing phase and arranging them into categories based on meaning similarity (Schulenberg, 2007). To create groupings, the constant comparative technique was used, which involves constant revision, alteration, and modification of the classification till all newer models could be positioned into such a correct section, as well as the addition of new components does not broaden or develop new categories – that is, evidence-based metrics from of the six banks' data were compared for similarities. This technique, also known as open coding, comprises thoroughly analyzing all interview transcripts for descriptive categories (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). Clarification exchanges were typically uncoded, in which the respondent requested an explanation of an interviewer's question.

Since the nature and goal of the two types of research are different, terms like dependability and validity from quantitative research do not apply to qualitative research (Krefting, 1991). The validity of qualitative research can be assessed using three criteria: believability, conformability,

and transferability (Albrechtsen, 2007; Thagaard, 2002). The research procedure is described in detail, which adds to the trustworthiness of the findings. The data transcribed must accurately reflect what the respondent said during the interview, and the data reporting must be correct as well. To achieve this, the transcription was done word for word after numerous listens to the interview audio. Furthermore, because reliable data from the respondent is required, the researcher functioned as a discussion partner during the interviews, simply listening to the informants and asking them as needed without influencing them. Thick descriptions were also supplied in the paper to ensure the research's trustworthiness. Second, conformability is achieved through the development of study questions based on theory, as well as constant control and precise transcription during interviews (Albrechtsen, 2007). Before the interview sessions, the researcher conducted an in-depth literature review and content analysis of numerous theories and factors to determine conformability and designed research questions accordingly. In addition, the informants were emailed a synopsis of the interview transcripts to gain their approval. The informants made no significant comments or adjustments. The measure for transferability was next studied to guarantee validity. Since qualitative results are not generalisable, it is important to assess whether the findings are transferable to other contexts. This research was carried out among banks. Organizations from various industries were purposefully chosen and questioned. The information regarding the context and the organizations investigated is carefully presented to provide knowledge of the context, which increases the likelihood of the results being transferred to other situations.

4.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter goes through the study philosophy, kind, strategy, data collection, sample size and sampling, data analysis, generalization, validity, reliability, and ethical considerations in depth. The research strategy was devised to gather the data required to meet the study's goals and objectives. The chapter also explains why this method of research was chosen. The findings and analysis of the research are presented in the following chapter.

CHAPTER FIVE: PRESENTATION OF EMPIRICAL DATA

5.0 Chapter Overview

This chapter of the thesis presents the findings of the study to address the research objectives proposed in the introduction section of this project. A two-stage analysis is provided to address the research object. The quantitative analysis is first presented, followed by the qualitative analysis. A descriptive statistic about the respondents is first supplied about the quantitative analysis. The confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) results for the constructs in the conceptual framework are next presented. Furthermore, various reliability and validity tests on the scales used in this study were conducted to validate and authenticate the final model derived from the empirical data presentation. Next, a descriptive statistic was performed for the diversity items. Finally, structural equation modeling was presented in order to assess the relationship between cultural diversity, innovation, and competitive advantage. The qualitative section of this chapter focuses specifically on cultural diversity, and forms of cultural diversity in the banking industry, while also highlighting the issues of cultural diversity and how it can be managed within Nigeria's banking industry.

5.1 Quantitative Analysis

5.1.1 Profile of respondent and sample demographics

Respondents were recruited from major banks in Nigeria. The demographic statistics provided a cross-sectional summary of the respondents' information about gender, age, categorization of respondents by level of management, and years of working experience with the bank.

Table 5.1 Respondents' Profile

Details		Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	60
	Female	40

Age	20 – 30	20
	31 – 40	45
	41 – 50	30
	51 and above	5
Level of Management	Top-level	5
	Middle level	15
	Operational level	80
Experience	1-5	25
	6-10	30
	11-15	10
	16 and above	5

Table 5.1 reveals that 60% of respondents were males while 40% were females. When the respondents were grouped according to age the results show that 20% of respondents were aged between 20 and 30 years, 45% between 31 and 40 years, 30% between 41 and 50 years, and 5% between 51 years and above. In the view of the respondents by their level of management, 5% of respondents fall under the top level, 15% middle level, and 80% operational level. Table 5.1 also shows the results when the respondents were grouped according to years of experience. 50% of respondents had experienced between 1 to 5 years, 45% had 6 to 10 years, 10% had 11 to 15 years and 5% had 16 years and above.

5.1.2 Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

The two-stage SEM approach was described in the previous chapters as the analytical method used to evaluate the hypothesized associations in the study framework, based on Anderson and Gerbig's (1988) ideas. In the first stage, the measurement phase, the causal linkages between the observed variables or measurement items and the underlying theoretical constructs were specified by completing a CFA using AMOS version 22. The CFA was used to develop a

measurement model. The second phase, the structural phase, examines the causal linkages between the predictive factors and responses, as well as the mediating and moderating effects, using a structural model. The methodology utilized to conduct this two-stage analysis as well as the results, are detailed in the following sub-sections.

5.1.2.1 Measurement Models

According to academic scholars, examining a structural model is useless unless the measuring model is created; if the measurement items selected for a construct do not measure that construct, the given theory must be amended so that it can be examined (Bagozzi, 2010). It is critical to disclose the characteristics of the measurement items that will be utilized to answer the structural hypotheses in this regard. A confirmatory factor analysis was used to evaluate the measurement models for the three dimensions (diversity, innovation, and competitive advantage) (CFA). Only factors with a minimum value of 0.5, as proposed by Hair et al. (2010), were accepted for further analysis in the CFA. Six items out of the twelve items identified from the literature review for measuring diversity had a factor loading greater than 0.5. Thus, age, gender, culture, religion, language, and race had factor loading greater than 0.5, while working experience, educational qualification, marital status, ethnicity, disabilities, and class did not load well and were dropped. The CFA results of the initial measurement models are displayed in Table 5.2 below. Convergent validity is established as all items in the CFA loaded significantly with large patterns of coefficients (Gerbing and Anderson, 1988).

Table 5.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA).

	loadings	T-value
Diversity		
In this bank, there is a diversity of age	0.66	13.817
In this bank, there is diversity in gender	0.623	12.85
In this bank, there is diversity in cultural	0.7	14.937
In this bank, there is diversity in religion	0.628	12.97
In this bank, there is diversity in race	0.611	12.528
In this bank, there is diversity in language	0.614	12.624

Innovation

In recent years, our bank has developed new service processes	0.803	17.599
In recent years, our bank has improved existing services	0.779	16.898
In recent years, our bank has repackaged existing services	0.753	16.129
In recent years, our bank has introduced new services that competitors do not offer in the market	0.568	11.28

Competitive advantage

In this bank, there is an exploitation of all market opportunities	0.745	15.818
This bank's full exploits of market opportunities	0.834	18.366
This bank neutralization of all competitive threats	0.761	16.261
Think bank full neutralization of all competitive threats	0.323	6.009

5.1.2.1.1 Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's alpha was calculated for the three constructs. The ten items use to measure diversity had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.867, the four items used to evaluate competitive advantage as a result of cultural diversity had a Cronbach Alpha of 0.711 while the four items use to examine service innovation had a Cronbach alpha as 0.813. All constructs produce satisfactory Cronbach's alpha which was greater than the recommended level of 0.7. Composite reliability (also known as construct reliability) is an assessment of the internal consistency of the measurement items, similar to Cronbach's alpha (Netemeyer, 2003). The findings showed that diversity had composite reliability of 0.867, competitive advantage composite reliability was 0.774 and innovation was 0.819. Similar to Cronbach's alpha, every construct had composite reliability which was greater than the recommended level of 0.7.

Table 5.3 Reliability Statistics

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability	Number of Items
Diversity	0.867	0.867	10
Competitiveness	0.711	0.774	4
Innovation	0.813	0.819	4

5.1.2.1.2 Validity

Discriminant validity testing ensures that each construct is unique and that factors that are not similar but theoretically relevant are captured (Henseler et al., 2015). This is accomplished by linking pairs of latent variables or constructs. To verify the prevalence of construct validity for every pair of structures, this same square-root of the average variance extracted (AVE) “correlation between such a construct and itself” must be larger than the critical within and between correlation “correlation between the construct and other constructs” (Cable and DeRue, 2002). As demonstrated in Table 5.4, the square-root value of the AVEs is higher than the correlation between each combination of constructs, demonstrating that the final measure is discriminately valid.

Table 5.4 Correlation Matrix for Discriminant Validity

	Diversity	Innovation	Competitiveness
Diversity	0.629		
Innovation	0.581***	0.732	
Competitiveness	0.583***	0.561***	0.695

Note: Diagonal (bold) values are square roots of the AVE; off-diagonal values are the inter-construct correlation

5.1.2.1.3 Elements of diversity in the Nigeria banking industry

This section of the thesis discusses the responses regarding the grounds for cultural diversity from bank employees at the different levels of the banking system in Nigeria such as operations, marketing, managers, and customer representatives. The findings from table 5.5 revealed that 67.5%, 55.9%, 60.3%, 65.7%, 58.7%, and 47.3% agreed and strongly agree that gender, ethnicity, age, religion, language, and race are the grounds for cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry. However, 5.8%, 13.2%, 8.8%, 7%, 9.9%, and 16.1% of the participants did not agree (thus, strongly disagree and disagreed) that gender, culture, age, religion, language, and

race are the grounds for diversity in the Nigerian banking industry. The remaining participants were unsure.

Table 5.5 Grounds for diversity

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Gender	1.6%	4.2%	26.8%	47.5%	20%
Culture	2.3%	10.9%	30.9%	46%	9.9%
Age	2.3%	6.5%	30.9%	46%	14.3%
Religion	2.3%	4.7%	27.3%	48.6%	17.1%
Language	2.9%	7%	31.4%	47.5%	11.2%
Race	3.4%	12.7%	36.6%	39.2%	8.1%

From the analysis, the majority of respondents indicated that gender, culture, age, religion, language, and race are the grounds for cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry as compared to those who did not agree and those who were neutral. The results revealed that there is an indication that there are issues of diversity in the Nigerian banking industry. Furthermore, the findings revealed that gender (67.5%) was believed to be the grounds for the most cultural diversity issues in the Nigerian banking industry and this was followed by religion, age, language, culture, and race.

5.1.2.2 Structural Model

After the measurement model has been specified, proved to be reliable, and validated with an acceptable fit, the next logical step is to test the structural model. This phase, which is considered the most important in SEM analysis, allowed for the calculation of structural routes to test the study framework's hypothetical suppositions. Structural models, in particular, aid in the simultaneous testing of many links in complicated models while adjusting for measurement mistakes (Byrne, 2013).

Table 5.6 displays the parameter estimates of the direct and mediation model. Hypothesis 1 states that diversity in the banking industry has a positive significant influence on competitive

advantage. As shown in Table 5.6, there was a significant relationship between diversity and competitive advantage ($\beta=.41$, $p < 0.05$), providing support for H1. H2 was also supported as diversity was significantly related to innovation ($\beta=.65$, $p < 0.05$). Similarly, H3 was supported, as the findings of the study revealed that innovation has a positive significant influence on competitive advantage ($\beta=.37$, $p < 0.05$). Lastly, H4 was supported given that innovation mediated the relationship between diversity and competitive advantage ($\beta=.24$, $p < 0.05$),

Table 5.6 Structural Model Results

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Diversity --> Competitiveness	0.416	0.046	8.816	***
Diversity --> Innovation	0.657	0.038	17.08	***
Innovation --> Competitiveness	0.37	0.047	7.841	***
Diversity --> Innovation --> Competitiveness	0.243			***

Significance of Estimates:

*** $p < 0.001$

** $p < 0.010$

* $p < 0.050$

† $p < 0.100$

5.2 Qualitative Analysis

The interview transcript for the qualitative data was analysed using thematic analysis. Both the code and preconceived thematic analysis was applied to the data. This approach was applied to interview questions that sought to identify the forms of cultural diversity and its influences on competitive advantage in the Nigerian banking industry, given that preconceived themes were expected to be reflected, based on existing knowledge of cultural diversity. A data-driven inductive approach was utilized to determine the themes from interview questions that aimed to determine how cultural diversity issues are managed in the Nigerian banking industry. The themes emerging from the semi-structured interviews show that there are various forms of cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry, such as gender, age, and culture as well as language differences, which helps the banks to be competitive. From the themes, it was evident

that cultural diversity improves banks, creativity and innovation, and labour productivity which enable them to be competitive. The themes also provided an approach to which cultural diversity is managed in the Nigerian banking industry. A more in-depth discussion is provided below.

Table 5.7 Data sources

Banks	Types	Position	ID/Name
Bank A	Local	Business Manager	LocalA1
		Branch Manager	LocalA2
		Relationship Manager	LocalA3
		Sales Manager	LocalA4
Bank B	Local	Business Manager	LocalB1
		Marketing Manager	LocalB2
		Human Resources Manager	LocalB3
		Treasurer	LocalB4
Bank C	Foreign-owned	Branch Manager	ForeignC1
		Bank Marketing representative	ForeignC2
		Internal Auditor	ForeignC3
		Loan Officer	ForeignC4
Bank D	Foreign-owned	Branch Manager	ForeignD1
		Bank Marketing Manager	ForeignD2
		Internal Auditor	ForeignD3
		Loan Officer	ForeignD4
Bank E	Cross-border Nigerian bank	Branch Manager	CrossE1
		Data Processing Officer	CrossE2
		Marketing Manager	CrossE3
		Accountant	CrossE4
Bank F	Cross-border Nigerian bank	Treasurer	CrossF1
		Customer Care Manager	CrossF2
		Commercial Lender	CrossF3
		New Accounts Officer	CrossF4

Note: cross-border Nigerian bank refers to “indigenous Nigerian banks that have cross-border”

5.2.1 Forms of cultural diversity

To identify the forms of cultural diversity in the banking sector, participants were asked ‘*would you say cultural diversity exists in the banking industry and why?*’ Gender, age, and cultural diversity, according to the respondents, are sources of diversity in the banking business. Neither of the local banks, apart from foreign-owned and cross-border Nigerian banks, have a formal HR strategy or affirmative action plan to promote gender equality or diversity. Discrimination against older and rural employees continues to be a problem. In line with the existing literature on cultural diversity (see Joshi, Liao and Jackson, 2006), the results from the interview show that gender differences in relation to male and female form a ground for cultural diversity in the banking sector. A participant stated that:

“...before, depending on the area in the banking sector either gender may be preferred. When it comes to sales, females were mostly selected, a similar case is found in the teller section where you find more females. However, now there are more and more male tellers” (ForeignD4).

On the same note, another respondent stated that:

“When I started working the banking industry, we did not have female managers, now the situation is different. We have a number of female managers now; some are even branch managers” (CrossF3).

About 90% of the respondents also claimed that individuals from different social groups and national or cultural traditions work in the Nigerian banking industry. An indication that ethnicity is also a ground for cultural diversity. One of the respondents indicated that:

“... In almost all the banks you would find that almost all cultures are represented in an office space but in different ratios depending on the location of the work place. For example, if you take the Access Bank in Nigeria, you will find different cultures represented the Ijaws, the Hausas, the Yorubas, and the Igbos etc. The only difference is if the work place setting is in the Northern part of the country you will realize that more

of the cultures in the north are represented more the south. And in recent times cultural diversity has become policies in most international organizations where a position of the staff has to be from different cultures not peculiar to Nigeria but other countries. In this bank, I have worked with Black African, Ghanaians, individuals from Togo and South Africans” (ForeignD3).

On the same note, another respondent interviewed from the bank noted that:

“The different culture represents individuals with different language and/or style of communication and race” (LocalB4).

For instance, the Business Manager (LocalB1) revealed that his bank fired all rural migrant workers with inadequate skills and education and replaced them with young college graduates to improve its corporate image. All employees above the age of 45 were also fired by the corporation. Since all of the company’s employees were under the age of 35, the corporation could brag about a young and well-educated workforce. However, contrary to the firm's goal of improving its reputation, this approach resulted in negative press for the company.

The managers of Nigerian banks that are cross-border and foreign-owned banks are far more familiar with the concept of variety. Individuals are more knowledgeable and eloquent on issues of diversity in their country and banks. They use a broader definition of diversity management than that established in the literature. Cross-border Nigerian bank managers, for example, recognised workforce skill level, attitude, confidence, motivation level, and people and IT abilities as varied traits that must be controlled in addition to the sources of diversity described above.

When it came to managing diversity, the foreign-owned bank executives interviewed took a historical/long-term approach. Diversity, according to the managers, always has been a part of the culture and is nothing new:

“We have been managing diversity for thousands of years. If we make a big hype of it, it will create more tension and more diversity within the country. If it is for foreign employees, then it is OK. But we only have four or five foreign employees here, so no need for a diversity management policy” (ForeignD1).

Respondents are skeptical of the hype surrounding cultural diversity management. They are wary of democracy's potential impact and are concerned about how political parties incite social differences, demands, and even animosity among various identity groups. Most respondents stated emphatically that actively promoting an organizational policy in cultural diversity management may cause more harm than good in the workplace, as it emphasizes rather than minimizes differences. They emphasize the dangers of rehashing old and new grievances, both genuine and imagined, as well as the desire for collective identity and special consideration.

5.2.2 Perceived sources of cultural diversity

Cultural differences - More than half of the respondents highlighted two dimensions of cultural diversity in the workplace. The first is the distinction between expatriates and local employees. The other one is from Nigerians who have returned home from abroad and are eager to work for and are preferred prospects for, Nigerian banks. According to a human resources manager:

“All foreign employees [expatriates] emphasized their cultural shock when they come to Nigeria. But [Nigeria-owned] have not developed a formal policy to manage these cultural shocks” (LocalB3).

Some international bank employees claim that their company employs a big number of abroad graduate returnees. Unique life patterns and aspirations are brought with these identity Western-trained graduates. They anticipate excellent pay and rapid advancement. For banks operating in Nigeria, how to recruit and handle abroad returnees is a critical challenge. As a result, banks are allegedly being more careful in recruiting and managing these returnees, as they are perceived as "demanding" staff that are difficult to keep.

Regional differences - A source of variation among employees observed by all responders is regional diversity. Employees from southern Nigeria are thought to be simpler to handle in general. They are more dedicated and capable of enduring adversity than their northern counterparts. Companies also prefer to hire college grads in rural areas since they are easier to handle and keep.

“Their rural living habits get diluted after years of university education and living in the city, so these [rural-urban] cultural differences will not cause any conflict at the workplace” (CrossF1).

Surprisingly, respondents anticipate that regional disparities will become less of a cause of stress among highly educated personnel as time goes on. This seems to be partially due to the persons' regional habitual style becoming diluted by years at university and living independently from their birthplace.

5.2.3 Cultural diversity as a source of innovation

Multi-cultural team, according to interviewees, increased the number and level of creativity in the team. They cited a deeper and also more diverse setting as a source of total innovation, owing to the diversity of national and cultural origins. Different classifications can be made based on the specific answers:

Different personal characteristics - The innovative ideas that emerge from many informed are a source of inspiration. Even though team members have the same academic background, they differ in their educational concentration, according to interviewees. Members of the R&D team, in particular, benefit from a common academic basis and similar problem-solving methodologies, while varied educational focuses allow for knowledge expansion. Unique mindsets, such as diverse viewpoints, different ways of solving problems, and different points of view, help members of the team from cross-functional and extended teams. This is shown by the statement:

“You put people together and ask to think about issues. Of course, different characteristics, different behaviours, different knowledge can help to engineer more brilliant ideas” (CrossF4).

Cultural diversity appears to be a source of total diversity within a team, influencing cognitive and problem-solving strategies, academic education, and, as a result, expertise. This is in line with the findings of Hülshager et al. (2009), who found that cognitive style variation has a positive impact on empirically measured creativity.

National diversity - a larger breadth of knowledge and expertise will arise from a greater diversity of nationalities. Expertise, according to Wang et al. (1993), is an important factor in producing new solutions. Access to diverse knowledge backgrounds within the team, as well as new items while traveling to other countries, will boost specific experiences and, as a result, creativity will be fostered. Working in different countries and visiting new locations stimulates creativity. Collaboration with different nationalities and drawing on their product knowledge as a source of inspiration, on the other hand, may develop fresh ideas:

“I go to Togo and South Africa and I work with people from these countries so they give a lot of input and also more understanding of the product. There are things that are not for sale in the Nigeria and Ghana” (ForeignC2).

Working with people from different countries provides motivation and improves team spirit by allowing members to share their home countries' living styles, customs, policies, and history in informal talks. In addition, team members' perceptions of their own country are echoed by team members who find a welcome source of amusement in challenging others with cultural prejudices. Culture, according to one respondent, is a "social lubricant" that leads to greater enjoyment and a more engaging work environment. Cultural variety plays a vital part in team formation within national varied teams, according to the following statement:

“I never understand Peter’s jokes. So, it is just about . . . saying ‘Oh she is Ghanaian, that’s normal. She doesn’t understand.’ Then I keep asking ‘No, no, no, I want to

understand. I want to be part of the team.’ And that is how it is . . . just because people explain stuff like that. A kind of creativity — a kind of feeling bonding and then he knows it is just stupid interaction but I would have it just because I am Ghanaian. Stuff like — you know — “ooh la la” or that makes people laugh. That’s it. So, you can play on that. I play that part of my personality just to create some time up — a positive mood” (LocalA2).

National diversity appears to be a motivating factor in a team. However, it does not appear that this motivational factor has a direct and meaningful influence on boosting creativity or invention. It appears to have a secondary effect instead. National diversity in a team has an impact on group cohesion, which is defined as a team member's motivation to keep the team together and a team spirit (Hoegl and Gemuenden, 2001). Cohesion, in turn, has a positive impact on innovation and creativity (Craig and Kelly, 1999; Hoegl and Gemuenden, 2001).

5.2.4 Cultural diversity as a source of competitive advantage

Promotes creativity and innovation - Both male and female respondents agreed that Nigerian banks employing people from various ethnic origins have varying cultural expertise, which in this case included awareness of client preferences. The bank benefits from this expertise since the individuals are more sensitive to diverse cultures and so provide better customer service. Furthermore, cultural diversity enhances the workplace by making it more interesting and providing variation. It makes the task itself more entertaining, demanding, and thrilling, according to a small percentage of interviewers. Furthermore, better outcomes can be gained since larger subjects of knowledge are covered, according to one interviewee, and a higher level of inventiveness is achieved, according to a few interviewees. As stated by a respondent:

“.....you are much more creative, since the bank presents with individuals in diverse groups in the society, with socio-cultural differences, with different views” (ForeignD3).

In line with this, another respondent indicated that:

“It opens your recruitment net, attracts higher potential employees, gives the brand a broad and varied collection of backgrounds which can facilitate access to broader markets, and a treasure trove of perspectives that enhance innovation” (CrossF1).

Organizational learning and knowledge management - Both respondents noted that cultural diversity enhances organizational learning and knowledge management which helps in improving the competitiveness of the banks in the long run. A respondent stated that:

“diversity encourages inclusion initiatives, this inclusion encourages the process of creating, retaining, and transferring knowledge within the bank ... this the process of creating, sharing, using and managing the knowledge and information of a bank, helps improves the performance, competitive advantage, innovation, the sharing of lessons learned, integration, and continuous improvement of the organization and these efforts overlap with organizational learning” (LocalA3).

Task and relationship conflict - The results from the interview revealed that cultural diversity helps in task and relationship conflict management. As noted by the female respondents:

“The banks that want to harvest the full potential of their culturally diverse workforce will first create a structure that is fluid and flexible, is open to novel ideas, and encourages constructive conflict and interaction. The bank will implement training across the board that focuses on cultural awareness and sensitivity, as well as career development. The bank will help its employees reduce the stress associated with feeling different by creating and supporting social networks. Involvement of culturally diverse teams in strategic processes such as vision-setting will be promoted by the bank” (ForeignC4).

Other respondents also noted that:

“... Organizations with diversity cultural have an advantage in attracting and retaining the best talent. The capabilities of women and minorities offer a wider labour pool.

Hence, they that are able to attract and retain qualified minority group members and keep faith with them through fair and equitable career advancement treatments, gain competitive advantage and derive high quality human resources dividends” (ForeignC1).

“Organizations with diversity cultural is also better suited to serve a diverse external clientele in a more increasingly global market. Such organizations have a better understanding of the requirements of the legal, political, social, economic and cultural environments of foreign nations” (LocalA1).

In stating the advantages of cultural diversity, the respondent also noted some drawbacks. For instance, respondents indicated that:

“In problem-solving situations, extraordinary costs in time and financial resources can negate the benefits of synergy, and can even degenerate into dysfunctional conflicts diversity can make it harder to arrive at an agreement on a particular course of action, and can result in negative dynamics and cultural clashes that can create work disadvantages for women and minorities” (ForeignC4).

There is therefore the need for cultural diversity management to address the drawbacks associated with it.

5.2.5 Managing cultural diversity

Nigeria banks are advanced diversity management thinking because of the diverse nature of the culture and the influence of its foreign business unit. Local Nigerian banks appear to be managing diversity to avoid conflicts and cultural confrontations. To put it another way, they perceive diversity management as a problem-solving exercise rather than a business-enhancing HR job.

Foreign-owned and cross-border Nigerian banks, on the other hand, took a more proactive and business-oriented approach to the need for diversity management, recognising the implications of

managing a varied customer group for HR practices. Private utility companies, for example, have a long history of hiring workers from a variety of backgrounds to match their consumer base. Due to market rivalry, the public sector is now beginning to embrace this practice:

“We need employees who are able to speak the dialect used by the local community and to understand the local culture and customers’ needs [. . .] The culture [of our company] is not about managing diversity of employees but that of the customers because of their diverse backgrounds” (LocalA4).

In general, the respondents stated that most businesses have no official diversity management policy beyond what would be necessary by law. As a customer care manager commented, “firms will only comply with the law on diversity issues. They will not go an extra mile to implement anything else” (CrossF2). However, diversity issues may be addressed in their HR policy for a small number of them. The lack of a diversity management policy does not imply that diversity is not handled or that managers lack the necessary abilities to do so:

“Although there is no company diversity management policy, we have long practiced the skills of managing diversity. For example, each new post we are assigned to, we try to learn the language, culture, and hobbies of the local communities to make a better connection with the local employees and customers” (ForeignD4).

It was noted from all the respondents that although cultural diversity has its advantages managing people from different backgrounds about gender, ethnicity, age, religion, language, and/or race comes with its challenges, hence, the interview was aid in identifying themes in relations to how issues of cultural diversity are managed within the Nigerian banking sector.

Process, structure, and operation philosophy - The findings from more than half of the respondents’ interviews revealed the first way of dealing with the issues of cultural diversity, is to have a laid down plan. It should be a strategic orientation of the bank. The male respondent highlights this when he stated:

“Once the banks' process, thus is, structure and operating philosophy are established in such a way that promotes multicultural workforce, the is easy to implement actions at the individual level” (ForeignD4).

Diversity management training programs – All the respondents agreed that management training programs help in dealing with issues relating to cultural diversity. As noted by some respondents:

“Training program especially for leaders is one way of dealing with this problem, as the information they learn might help them identify existing problem areas that can be quickly corrected. It will also help them build the banks acceptance culture which must start from the top. The frequency of training, as well as the type of training, such as one-on-one coaching, must be planned carefully, depending upon each unique set of circumstances” (ForeignD1).

Employee involvement and engagement - The interview revealed employee involvement and engagement is important to overcome the problems associated with cultural diversity. A respondent noted that:

“... Cultural diversity can never be realised if the environment is not created for it, hence the employees must share in this way of thinking, this vision, and this competency. The involvement and engagement of employees in strategic processes enable them to understand its benefit and own it” (ForeignC3).

Measuring and rewarding - The findings from the interview showed that measuring and rewarding such cultural diversity initiatives at the beginning is important for their sustainability in the long run. Some respondents noted that:

“My bank is successful because we have been able to identify methods of measuring and rewarding individuals as well as teams for outstanding diversity management initiatives” (LocalB4).

“There is a mechanism to hold managers accountable for meeting diversity goals. This is reflected in the performance evaluation process. The acid test includes how much and how fast the organization breaks the glass ceiling to increase the percentage of minorities and women in the higher salary echelons through career development opportunities, mentoring, and meritorious executive appointments” (CrossE2).

5.2.6 Perceived challenges to diversity management

A variety of obstacles in managing cultural diversity have been noted by the participants. Seniority, both in terms of staff age and institutional rank of managers, is the most significant problem. It is generally observed as younger workers are unable to challenge senior personnel, particularly those from cultures other than their own. They have a hard time persuading the latter to adopt their ideas:

“Age is respected in Nigeria. These are emotional issues. If the young ones are not showing respect to the elder employees that may cause grievance” (LocalA2).

Managers and supervisors also felt helpless when it came to making decisions without the consent of greater rank:

“A good performer who is junior may not get promoted because the line manager needs to report to the headquarters for permission. He may have to wait for six months for the decision and during this period, the person is demotivated and may leave the company” (LocalB4).

A further issue is the type of the firm and its area. Hiring women and assigning them to rural locations, for instance, could be troublesome since they may not feel safe working alone in remote places at night, or they may have trouble finding housing. This issue was also mentioned in Venkata Ratnam's and Chandra's (1996) book. Keeping young talent that works in remote regions, in which some bank branches are located, is also a challenge:

“Younger employees always want to search for better places to work. No matter how much soft HR policy you implement, they will still leave. We use devices for talent management, fast promotion, job rotation and other similar schemes to manage regional diversity, but they are not sufficient to retain everybody” (ForeignC2).

Many obstacles have hampered the implementation of diversity management policies. The importance of preserving a consistent corporate culture and principles, as well as the challenges that banks face in doing so, has long been recognised (Brewster et al., 2005; Evans et al., 2002; Sparrow et al., 2004). Managing diversity for banks has shown to be more difficult due to context differences and various management agendas. The CEOs highlight many challenges with DM in banks. One is that, although this is arguably a problem that affects all banks, indigenous banks appear to be making little effort to build an integrated corporate HR strategy and diversity management policy. "The international operations will have their diversity management policy," said a marketing manager (CrossE3). "It's not something we deal with." "We have launched a mutual learning/sharing approach to HRM with our abroad operations," says another manager, emphasizing the necessity for more integration efforts. They should send individuals to work in India to understand how we function and what our culture is like as well as the other way around."

Furthermore, post-merger and acquisition integration has long been viewed as the most challenging undertaking due to company cultural differences (Cartwright and Cooper, 1993; Morrison and Robinson, 1997; Schuler et al., 2003). These disparities are exacerbated by cross-border mergers and acquisitions between western and eastern countries. According to managers, cultural conflicts were the most difficult aspect of their post-acquisition integration. Senior management churn worsened the problem because they frequently took their people and HR initiatives with them when they departed, only to be replaced by their successors. When top executives arrive from a third country, they bring a new set of cultural values and management practices with them, worsening the cultural challenges.

The second finding in this area is that, as past research has indicated; foreign-owned enterprises may confront host-country resistance to diversity management measures (Ferner et al., 2005). According to diversity management literature, every employee in the company, especially those with people management duties, plays a key role in advancing diversity management. Due to the low level of knowledge of the concept and the necessity for diversity management in Nigeria, banks aiming to enhance their recruiting and retention outcomes by boosting diversity management activities may face substantial hurdles. Although their quality was on par with if not greater than that of their male counterparts, a multinational bank's HR director revealed that the recruiting agency business they hired in Nigeria frequently screened out female candidates. The bank has a global equal opportunity policy and a gender ratio in hiring. As a result, the Nigeria subsidiary's gender ratios frequently fell short of the corporate goal. When the recruiting agency's intervention was discovered, the HR director informed the agency's workers of the company's policy and instructed them to refrain from discriminating against female candidates. The Nigerian recruitment team dismissed the proposal, hoping to persuade the HR director that this was the usual procedure in Nigeria, where women employees were perceived to be less productive due to family obligations. This episode highlights an important question: how may diversity management, like other aspects of Western Banks' CSR (e.g., labour norms), be extended outside the organization to influence, if not outright dictate, supplier enterprise behaviour in developing nation business networks?

The third discovery is based on combining perspectives, which is an important component of western diversity management literature (Mor Barak, 2005). Respondents, on the other hand, are receptive to the idea of a codified HR policy on employee flexibility. They choose to deal with it informally on a case-by-case basis rather than formalising the arrangement. Managers provided examples of how to discreetly accommodate certain workers' family obligations, such as caring for a sick family member. This is a moral obligation for them, shaped by their societal culture. Excessively long work hours are the norm in many of Nigeria's fast-growing enterprises. Hours of commuting due to the country's outdated infrastructure, increased workload due to bureaucracy, and the need to connect with abroad counterparts in Western countries worsen this problem (Nathwani et al., 2007). On the other side, work-life balance may not be enough to retain top talent. Younger people with a strong education in both countries are ambitious and

desire to succeed in their careers. People expect not only outstanding pay packages from their employers but also early promotions and opportunities for professional growth overseas. If these conditions are not met, or if better chances are available overseas, people are willing to change jobs.

5.3 Chapter Summary

The section of the thesis presents the findings of a study on cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry. First, a quantitative analysis was presented. According to the results of the quantitative investigation, cultural diversity significantly affects competitive advantage in the banking sector through innovation.

Table 5.8 Summary of the results and decisions

Hypotheses	Estimate	P	Decision
H1 Diversity --> Competitiveness	0.416	***	Supported
H2 Diversity --> Innovation	0.657	***	Supported
H3 Innovation --> Competitiveness	0.37	***	Supported
H4 Diversity --> Innovation --> Competitiveness	0.243	***	Supported

Second, the qualitative section focuses in particular on the problems with cultural diversity and how they might be handled within the sector. Thematic analysis was used to examine the transcript of the interviews used for the qualitative data. According to those who participated in the interviews, the results demonstrate the significance of employee involvement and engagement in resolving issues related to cultural diversity. The biggest issue is seniority, both in terms of personnel age and the institutional status of managers. Hiring women and placing them in rural areas could be problematic since they might not feel secure working by themselves at night in isolated settings or they might have problems finding lodging. Diversity management rules have had a difficult time being implemented because of many issues. Due to contextual variations, managing diversity for banks has proven to be more challenging. Due to varying corporate cultures, post-merger and acquisition integration has always been seen as the most difficult. Cross-border mergers and acquisitions worsen these inequities. Banks may face

significant obstacles in their efforts to improve diversity management initiatives' effects on hiring and retention. Every person in the organization contributes significantly to the advancement of diversity management, according to diversity management literature. The idea of a formalised HR policy on employee flexibility is well received by the respondents.

CHAPTER SIX: DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

6.0 Overview

This section of the study provides a discussion of the findings from the quantitative and qualitative data in relation to the objectives of the study. The results from the study are compared with the existing literature relating to the subject matter of providing a better interception.

6.1 Grounds for diversity

6.1.1 Age

The empirical analysis of this study shows that age forms the basis for cultural diversity in the banking industry. The result from the qualitative analysis shows that employees within the banking industry have to work with people younger and older than them. The findings from the quantitative analysis revealed that 60.3% of the target respondents agreed that age is a reason for cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry. These findings are in line with previous studies as age as a dimension of cultural diversity has long been acknowledged as an important part of a firm's human resources needed for competitive advantage (Gordon, 2018). According to Rudolph, Toomey, and Baltes (2017), the issue of age as an imperative for competitive advantage in the context of work must be analyzed from the general spectrum of ageism and age stereotypes. Ageism is a common global phenomenon and it is defined as being biased or discriminating against people (especially older people) on the basis of their age (Olivas-Lujan and Bondarouk, 2017). As such, most countries, through legal frameworks, have tried to prohibit discrimination against applicants based on age in terms of hiring, promotion, compensation, and other functions of employment (Stephenson, 2017). In effect, this legislation is meant to protect all workers from age discrimination in the workplace and abolish the use of age limits in recruitment and selection. While ageism relates to older people, individuals of any age group also suffer discrimination in the workplace, and this development is known as age stereotypes (Hales and Riach, 2017). Ageism can manifest for individuals of any age and thus occurs in a

variety of work contexts (Nowacka, 2017). This evidence suggests that workplace ageism or ageism typically occurs when individuals are systematically overlooked for opportunities based on their age.

When age diversity is embraced in the workplace, the marketing and financial performance of firms can improve (Jayne and Dipboye, 2004). For instance, age diversity can help firms to appreciate well the demands and preferences of their aging customers, which in turn will improve firm performance (Duehr and Bono, 2006). For example, a financial institution trying to sell its products to middle-aged and older customers may be more successful if it has the right proportion of employees in these same age categories. Empirically, there is evidence to suggest that it is beneficial for a firm to adjust the demographic proportions of its human resource mix to reflect the age spread of its target market (Richard, 2000). (Giancola, 2006) Another reason why age diversity is important is that both old and young employees have unique skills that their companies can use to gain a competitive edge. In a study by Li et al. (2020), it was revealed that age diversity provides varied perspectives, skills, and insights that can boost creativity and problem-solving capabilities, thereby leading to a firm's competitive advantage. To confirm this study, other studies such as Ntatsopoulos (2001) and Peterson and Spiker (2005) have established that older employees have unique value because they contribute to a dimension of human resources obtained only through many years of working in a specific organization and learning a specific industry.

Furthermore, older employees are beneficial by way of offering social connections developed across years of working in a given business environment (Tanikawa, Kim, and Jung, 2017). On the contribution of younger employees, Beaver and Hutchings (2005) found that younger employees offer unique values such as flexibility, energy, and creativity relevant to firm performance. As argued by Krishnan, Gowrishankar, and Kanagaraj (2017), the contribution of younger employees to firm performance is linked to the fact that young employees are better educated and physically more capable. Based on the above findings, Odhiambo, Gachoka, and Rambo (2018) admonish firms to inculcate some appropriate level of age diversity into their recruitment policy because it allows the value of both groups of employees to complement one another and, subsequently, help the firm achieve good performance.

6.1.2 Culture

The fact that firms exist to serve diverse target groups makes the concept of cultural diversity in the workplace a consequential issue. Also, globalization and affirmative action campaigns have played a tremendous role in making the concept of cultural diversity at work important (Ahmed, 2019). Culture is simplistically referred to by Makokolo (2005) as the tribalistic grouping of people. Cultural differences exist in all spheres of life and are about how individuals perceive and interact with one another in group settings (Sanyang and Othman, 2019). According to Leslie (2017), people in group settings (work environments) do not establish a social organization anew out of engagements with their members, but rather keep external status differences within the group. Therefore, members of cultural groups with low or high status in the workplace are perceived as having equal status by others in the same environment (Verma, 2020). Consequently, the status distance that exists between two cultural groups in a work environment has the potential to change interpersonal relationships and interactions between people working in the organization. Because of its benefits, cultural diversity has emerged as an economic driver in global business (Rawat and Basergekar, 2016). The findings of this study confirmed the assertion that culture forms the basis for cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry. Interview participants indicated that individuals from different cultural backgrounds can be found in the banking industry, although the ratio differs depending on the banks' location. The quantitative analysis was also statistically significant in this regard.

Past studies confirm that culture forms the ground for cultural diversity. For example, in a study by Dastane and Eshgbe (2015), it was established that there existed high innovation and creativity in highly culturally diverse organizations. It must be stated that high innovation and creativity are at the core of competitive advantage and superior firm performance. It is also the case that cultural diversity on its own doesn't promote competitive advantage; rather, it is incumbent on managers to exert the knowledge needed to manage diversity because it comes with detrimental effects if not managed (Ikon and Okolie-Osemene, 2017). Leaning on social identity and self-categorization theory, Mba, Ofobruku, Nwanah, and Anikwe (2018) found that a work environment where there is cultural diversity produces psychological processes such as in-group liking, in-group attraction, and, worst, in-group favoritism. This finding invariably

offers behavioral change to employees, such that employees may only choose to favor colleagues who share their cultural orientation. The negative sides of this finding are that it has the propensity to promote poor communication, engender less cooperation, and less cohesiveness (Akpakip, 2017).

According to several studies, cultural diversity is a valuable financial asset because it improves decision-making in work groups. In a stock-trading simulation, Levine, Apfelbaum, Bernard, Bartelt, Zajac, and Stark (2014) found that cultural diversity or group inclusiveness has improved not only the decision-making process but also makes decisions faster and more accurately. Also, Paletz, Peng, Erez, and Maslach (2004) revealed that “teams mostly comprised of cultural minorities rated the group they worked with as more pleasurable and reported experiencing more positive emotions towards group members.” The understanding of this finding is that people from a minority group in a larger group increase minority members' self-esteem and confidence, breaking down the feelings that would normally lead to exclusion. On the contrary, Van Dick, Knippenberg, Hägele, Guillaume and Brodbeck (2008) found that in groups where there is no cultural diversity but there is the existence of a common corporate vision, employees still contribute work towards the achievement of the corporate vision. More profoundly, Watson and Hunter (2015) found that cultural diversity in the work environment, especially at the executive level, significantly correlates with financial performance in countries worldwide.

6.1.3 Gender

In relation to gender, the analysis of the study revealed that gender (67.5%) was believed to be the basis for the most cultural diversity issues in the Nigerian banking industry. Despite workplace gender diversity (WGD) being the most common ground for cultural diversity issues, it is a complex topic and acknowledged by scholars as one of the mechanisms by which firms can influence and control their capability to achieve competitive advantage (Colovic and Williams, 2020). As stated by Zhang (2020), gender diversity is a prominent strategic imperative in the inclusivity initiatives that lead to superior firm performance and competitive advantage. Using the gender socialization theory, females and males are different and are considered the two main categories of gender classification. Gender diversity in the context of the workplace

environment is defined by Fine, Sojo, and LawfordSmith (2020) as sexual heterogeneity in the workplace. By this definition, a work environment where there is an equal proportion of male and female employees has the highest degree of gender diversity, whereas a gender homogenous work environment has low gender diversity. The need for gender diversity for firm competitive advantage is premised on a study by Ibrahim and Hanefah (2016) where it was established that female executives are more receptive to the code of ethics than their male counterparts. A blend of both genders in the work environment thus offers firms a superior advantage. Another study by Liu (2018) revealed that women are more aware, sensitive to ethical issues, and caring for others than their male counterparts. Additionally, Al-Shaer and Zaman (2016) found that “women directors are less power-oriented as compared to men by having strong traits of kindness and passion, which encourage the understanding and protection of people and nature.”

Generally, two strands of arguments, namely ethical and economic, underpin the basis of gender diversity in the workplace (Van der Walt and Ingley, 2003). Ethical arguments consider gender diversity in the workplace as a desirable end in itself and stress that it is discriminatory to eliminate certain groups from the corporate elite based on gender (Singh, Meng, and Hansen, 2014). Prior literature on the ethical argument states that disproportionate inclusion of certain groups raises ethical issues that derive from an imperative to empower those groups excluded from positions of economic power. On the other hand, the economic argument for gender diversity states that gender diversity in the workplace affects the way employees perform, which is intractably linked to firm performance (Leung, 2020). Economic arguments for gender diversity also arise from the fact that the systematic non-selection of able candidates damages a firm's financial performance (Chang, Yip, and Chen, 2019). Overwhelmingly, studies implore firms to ensure gender diversity in the workplace because it helps firms achieve superior performance (see, for instance, Kalev and Deutsch, 2018; Essig and Soparnot, 2019; Soleman, 2020).

6.1.4 Religion

The study findings show that religion is a cause for cultural diversity issues in the Nigerian banking industry. Fundamentally, religion is an important determinant of human civilization, and social development and how society interacts and lives also form the basis of whether a behavior is acceptable (Manyaga and Taha, 2020). Religion is regarded as part of culture; the two concepts are different in scope. Culture is derived from specific locations, whereas religion transcends geographic borders. But, the relationship between the two concepts stems from the fact that “religious values and beliefs are typically rooted in religious scriptures, which makes them consistent and stable over time” (Minton et al., 2015). At the heart of many political and civil skirmishes or conflicts is religion, which has negative consequences for human and economic development (VanAlstine, Cox, and Roden, 2013). Within the spectrum of corporations, religion affects investment decisions as well (Martin and Drogendijk, 2014). Also, religion plays a crucial role in the formation of corporate culture because the spirit of capitalism is profoundly rooted in historical religious developments (Weber and Fried, 2011). Additionally, religion can enhance social capital such as trust and social networks, which can lead to a firm's competitive advantage (Alpalho, Pereira dos Santos, and Tavares, 2020).

Traditionally, religious diversity implies that there are significant differences in religious belief and practice (Kodila-Tedika and Agbor, 2014). Religious diversity requires corporate executives to use a pluralistic mindset in recruitment processes, which suggests that one religion is as good as any other (Tavares and Wacziarg, 2001). As established by Ying, Liu, Bao, and Zhou (2017), religious diversity has both positive and negative economic effects. The former arises from complementarities in production and diversity of skills, ideas, and experiences, while the latter is due to disagreements about public policies, animosity between different groups, and conflict (Alesina, Harnoss, and Rapoport, 2016). The point must be made that recent empirical findings link firm competitive advantage to religious activities (see Hiatt, Sine and Tolbert, 2009; Yue, Wang and Yang, 2019; Zhao and Lounsbury, 2016). Specifically, Zhao and Lounsbury (2016) found that religious diversity in the workplace plays a significant role in firm sustainability. On the contrary, a study by Ali and Azmi (2016) on the relationship between religious diversity and

firm performance revealed that there was no relationship between religious diversity and firm performance.

6.1.5 Language

Firms in recent times have deployed the strategy of assembling a workforce with a diverse and optimal mix of skills; therefore, it was not a surprise that the findings of the study show that language forms a ground for cultural diversity issues in the Nigerian banking industry. According to Groutsis, O'Leary, and Russell (2018), assembling a workforce with diverse human capital has the propensity to enhance productivity and profitability. Over the years, there have been emphasizes that employees who can speak several languages are a resource that firms can leverage for competitive advantage (Yanaprasart, 2018; Fabricius, Mortensen and Haberland, 2017). Employing a workforce with varied linguistic capabilities is a global trend. Notwithstanding the importance of language diversity, it has generally been accused of having cost implications for firms, and thus slow down production since information dissemination slows leading to misunderstanding employees (Churchill and Valenzuela, 2019). This drawback of language diversity in the workplace has the potential to increase with the distance between two languages. While workforce language plurality is an important resource, empirical evidence on the return is mixed. For instance, Fry and Lowell (2003) found that employees with diverse language capabilities do not get well paid by the job market. On the other hand, Chiswick and Millar (2015) found that firms with employees who have diverse linguistic strengths do not add economic value to their organization.

More specifically, an empirical study on the relationship between language diversity and firm competitive advantage is unexpectedly limited. Ottaviano and Peri (2006) found a positive correlation between language diversity and competitive advantage. Also, Peri, Shih, and Sparber (2015) revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between language diversity and firm competitive advantage. Quite the reverse, Kahane, Longley, and Simmons (2013) found that performance of the workforce surge when they speak the same language. Then also, Parrotta, Pozzoli, and Pytlikova (2014) found that no negative relationship exists between language diversity and firm competitive advantage. But largely, the argument is made that

communication between employees becomes ineffective if they do not speak the same language, which can result in production problems and conflicts (Trax, Brunow and Suedekum, 2015). Furthermore, language disparity can result in task differentiation, which might have negative effects on productivity if non-native language speakers do not have complementary skills. Language diversity can have positive effects as well, for instance, if firms hire immigrants from the countries they trade with (Tagne and Evou, 2020; Kemmerer, 2019).

6.1.6 Race

Traditionally, the race is connected with the biological nuances and color of one's skin, generally pigeonholed as whites and non-whites (Richeson and Sommers, 2016). A discussion on racial discrimination is a global topical issue on the account of colonization and has led to disparities in health, living standards, education, and employment (Marimuthu and Kolaindasmy 2009). Within the context of the Nigerian banking industry, the findings of the study reveal that racial diversity suggests a social paradigm, which connotes a positive perception in the minds of the general public. Racial diversity implies a fair representation of various races in the management of a firm and it is considered the bedrock of firm performance because it promotes innovation, and creativity (Ahmed and Bukth, 2019). According to Amin and Nor (2019), diverse races in a firm bring in different perspectives as far as the decision is concerned. Racial diversity in countries with a history of diverse ethnic backgrounds and segregation but unique transformation initiatives and regulations produces different results in firm performance (Rutledge, Karim and Lu, 2016). For example, a study by Ntim (2015) in South Africa revealed a positive relationship between racial diversity and firm performance, and racial diversity yielded better performance than gender diversity. The innovation creativity and diverse perspectives associated with racial diversity in corporate organizations imply that firm financial performance will be enhanced and therefore lessens the agency problem.

According to Cook and Glass (2014), racial diversity in a corporate organization is an indication of good corporate governance that is not mandatory but discretionary. However, in countries where there is a lower level of education and limited economic and employment opportunities, racial diversity discussions are regarded as a non-issue (Gyapong, Monem and Hu, 2016). In a

study by Shukeri, Shin and Shaari (2012) and Marimuthu and Kolaindasmy (2009) racial diversity has a significant impact on firm performance due to the convergence of multi-diverse backgrounds, intellectual capital, and competency thus leading to competitive advantage. In Nigeria, the racial diversity of corporate boards has been established as having a significant positive impact on firm performance (Ujunwa, 2012).

6.2 Diversity, Innovation, and Competitive Advantage

The results of the hypothesis testing using the SEM reveal that diversity and innovation are positively related. As a result, the findings of this study clearly show that human capital diversity is critical in determining a company's innovative capacities. It is encouraging to notice that the elements of diversity in this study show different influences on innovation than earlier studies that try to link diversity to innovation, e.g., the positive effect of gender diversity (Østergaard., Timmermans, and Kristinsson, 2011) and the negative and neutral effect of age diversity (Zajac et al. 1991).). This is reassuring because research concentrating on other performance indicators frequently shows mixed outcomes when it comes to diversity, with identical traits appearing to be favourable, negative, or insignificant. Since one sort of diversity composition may have a distinct influence on several types of performance indicators, it is difficult to link our work to studies that do not focus on innovation. Innovation, which is at the heart of every inventive process, necessitates a different engagement style than that which improves a company's effectiveness. Regarding the previous statement, the findings of the study show that diversity has a significant effect on competitive advantage via innovation. This finding is in line with previous studies (Liu, Chang, and Fang, 2019; Hwang, Choi and Shin, 2020; Obeidat, Obeidat, Alrowwad, Alshurideh, Masadeh, and Abuhashesh, 2021) mediates the relationship between the antecedents of competitive advantage on itself. Lastly, concerning the hypotheses testing, the findings of the study show that diversity has a significant effect on competitive advantage in the Nigerian banking industry.

6.3 Nature of Cultural diversity management

Organizations should design an overarching strategy for managing diversity that is integrated with other areas of the organization's strategy and supports overall business goals, according to popular cultural diversity management literature (CIPD, 2007). For the project to succeed, communication, training, employee involvement, and senior management backing are viewed as critical (CIPD, 2006). According to existing study findings, Nigerian banks analysed have reached this level in their cultural diversity management, whereas few western corporations have (CIPD, 2007). In general, the data revealed that Nigerian businesses have yet to adopt a systematic approach to human resource management (Budhwar and Bhatnagar, 2009; Rowley and Cooke, 2010). Nigerian bank line managers, in particular, have been highly involved in people management and are required to establish their own "policy" on an ad hoc basis to deal with individuals when situations arise. They prefer to grant requests to staff in a discreet manner. The line managers' approach is individual-based (typical of cultural diversity management perspective) rather than group-based from this perspective (characteristic of equal opportunity perspective).

The study reveals that indigenous managers' methods of coping with diversity are paternalistic to a considerable extent and that they frequently use a specific instance strategy. Paternalism, in particular, is a prominent feature of Nigerian culture (Pye, 1986; Aycan, 2006). It is a type of relationship that indicates the quality of the working relationship between employees and management. Authority, hierarchy, care, obedience, devotion, and reliance are all necessary ingredients for paternalism to work. Paternalism culture, according to Aycan (2006), is benevolent (dictatorship) in nature. It is concerned with the employees' well-being, whereas paternalism, which evolved in Western human resource policy as a technique of eliciting more employee dedication and performance, is exploitative. Cultural diversity management in the oriental environment, from this perspective, is relationship-driven and can be both a means and an end in itself. The western approach to cultural diversity management, on the other hand, is outcome-driven and hence a determining means to an end. Given the many motivations for cultural diversity management and levels of knowledge of the need to manage diversity, it's not

unexpected that Nigerian banks have made little effort to evaluate cultural diversity management.

According to CIPD (2007, p. 12), there are different methods of measuring diversity through a variety techniques. Employee attitude surveys, the number of complaints and grievances, labour turnover, employee performance appraisals, absenteeism, ability to recruit, the number of tribunal cases, impact assessment, customer satisfaction, employee engagement questionnaires, business results, balanced scorecard, client diversification, advancements to problem-solving and decision-making, and psychological contract issues are just a few examples. None of the people polled believe their company has a formal system in place to track the impact of cultural diversity management. This is unsurprising given the organizations' low priority for cultural diversity and the lack of a defined cultural diversity management policy.

6.4 Ways cultural diversity influences competitive advantage

The analysis of data analysis revealed cultural diversity has a statistically significant influence on competitive advantage. The findings also show that labour productivity, task and relationship conflict, organizational learning, knowledge management, promotes creativity and innovations are how cultural diversity influences competitive advantage and these are discussed below:

6.4.1 Labour productivity

Firm competitiveness is based on the competitive advantage that the firm has, but which is neither short-lived nor eternal (Goel, Agrawal and Sharma, 2017). Competitive advantage is the ability of a firm to achieve higher profitability than rivals in an industry (Sachitra, 2016). In recent times, one of the key drivers of competitive advantage at both the macroeconomic level and microeconomic or enterprise level is labor productivity (Volek, Novotná and Zeman, 2019). Labor productivity is the most important determinant of competitive advantage due to its ability to measure the output of the human resource base or workers. Bearing the highly volatile economic, social and technological nuances, there is a need for firms to submissively consider their labor requirements (Sainidis and Kolawole, 2019). To meet the labor requirements of firms,

two strategies namely external (i.e., numerical) or internal (i.e., functional) labour have been suggested (Preenen, Vergeer, Kraan and Dhondt, 2017). External labor requirement requires firms to use temporary and periodic workforce, short fixed-term contracts, lay-offs, agency labour, freelance work, subcontracting, and homework or outwork (Úbeda-García et al., 2017). On the other hand, internal labor requirement requires firms to reallocate or rotate jobs, change employees, institute flexible working schedules and redesign jobs within their organizations to meet the demands of the market (Felstead et al., 2019). Internal labor requirement reduces communication barriers, promotes working with different people, and encourages knowledge and information sharing in the organization.

According to Sainidis and Kolawole (2019), labor productivity is the ability of employees or workers to produce a given amount of goods or services within a certain period. Accordingly, it is on the bases of this output that a firm competitive advantage can be ascertained. Labor productivity as a basis of firm competitive advantage is influenced by factors such as physical capital stock, the availability of technology and innovations framework, the presence of economies of scale in the production process, and the spiraling of labor effort (Wang and Heyes, 2020). Additionally, other factors that influenced labor productivity are the nature of the industry, age of the business, size of the business, region, country, management style, and the business cycle (Dhiman and Sharma, 2019). But, largely innovation as a factor of labor productivity has been singled out by prior studies as the most important contributor to a firm competitive advantage (Kijek and Kijek, 2019). Innovation as the most important factor of labor productivity is attributed to the fact that it increases the flexibility of employees (Heng, 2020). All of these factors are significant in determining the labor productivity and competitiveness of firms, as firms are sources of economic growth, promotes development, and stimulates innovation.

6.4.2 Task and relationship conflict

Prior existing literature on intra-group conflict has been identified as being an outcome of cultural diversity in the workplace (Paulus, van der Zee and Kenworthy, 2016). It is the argument of Vodosek (2005) that when cultural diversity in the workplace is not managed well, it has the

propensity to breed intra-group conflicts which then negatively affect a firm competitive advantage. Intra-group occurs when group members realize differences, and irreconcilable wishes among them and it thus has detrimental effects on group or organizational functioning (Ayoko and Konrad, 2012). A perusal of the intra-group conflict literature revealed two types of conflict namely task-related and relationship conflict (Jehn, Bezrukova and Thatcher, 2008). According to Korovyakovskaya and Chong (2016), task-related conflict bothers on the disagreement among group members or the prevalence of differences in views and opinions relating to tasks being performed and interpretation of task-related information. This means that task conflict manifest based on disagreements among members of a group about how tasks are to be accomplished, especially using policy, procedures, and resources of the organization. In contrast, relationship conflict is the interpersonal mismatch among group members, including tension, animosity, and annoyance and it is stated to have a negative effect on the functioning and outcomes of groups (Curşeu and Schruijer, 2017).

The two types of conflict have diverse impacts on group performance or outcomes. For instance, task-related conflict incites group members to strive toward achieving the task at hand, in turn, enhancing group outcomes (Hu, Chen, Gu, Huang and Liu, 2017). It is also the case that task-related conflict ensures greater understanding of the task to be achieved because it generates constructive controversy, leading to greater team confidence and effectiveness. In a study by Jehn and Mannix (2001), it was revealed that high-performing groups are inundated with more task conflict. Also, task conflict shows to be beneficial to groups performing non-routine tasks, and harmful to those performing routine tasks (Ayoko and Konrad, 2012). In fact, task-related conflict allows group members to have a better understanding and elucidation while avoiding personal abrasion that could distract the focus of the group. On the other hand, a meta-analysis exploring the relationship and task conflict effects revealed that each of them may be negatively associated with both group performance and satisfaction outcomes (De Dreu and Weingart, 2003). As opined by Chuang, Church and Zikic (2004), relationship conflict largely has negative effects on the ability of groups to perform by way of limiting information, creating stress and anxiety, and resulting in antagonistic and hostile interaction, which in turn hinders firm performance.

6.4.3 Organizational learning

One of the significance of cultural diversity, when leveraged well, is that it promotes organizational learning, which in turn leads to superior performance and competitive advantage (Zhang, Tang and Qi, 2020). However, organizational learning does not automatically enhance business performance rather its ability is largely dependent on the interplay between the diverse perspectives of the organization members (Ayoko and Konrad, 2012). To achieve superior performance and sustain competitive advantage, organizational learning is regarded as very critical (Rose, Dee and Leisyte, 2020). Organizational learning is a vital dimension that accounts for superior performance. Organizational learning is defined by McGill and Slocum (1993;2) as “the process by which managers become aware of the qualities, patterns, and consequences of their own experiences, and developmental models to understand these experiences.” A learning organization that is “skilled at creating, acquiring, and transferring knowledge, and at modifying its behaviour to reflect new knowledge and insights” (Garvin, 1993; 81) possesses the qualities needed to effectively recognize and pursue new opportunities (Lumpkin and Lichtenstein, 2005). Additionally, Huber (1991; 126) explains that “an organization learns if any of its units acquire knowledge that it recognizes as potentially useful to the organization.”

Ely and Thomas (2001) state that three perspectives inform organizational learning diversity decisions, the fairness-and-discrimination, access-and-legitimacy, and integration-and-learning perspective. A diversity perspective can be overt through the use of formal policies and guidelines, or covert using leadership behavior (Curşeu and Schruijer, 2017). In a study by Ely and Thomas (2001), the three perspectives were acknowledged among three professional service firms and related to their effect on group processes and outcomes. The perspective with the most profound impact on firm performance was the integration-and-learning approach. Accordingly, firms with integration-and-learning fused policies and practices that directly tied cultural diversity to work processes thus are creating a high value for cultural identity as a resource for learning. But then, the direct relationship between organizational learning and competitive advantage has well been established (Hsu, 2014; Poór et al., 2018). Therefore, organizational learning can be a crucial factor in examining a firm’s sustainability and competitive advantage.

6.4.4 Knowledge management

Ensuring workforce diversity is an important strategy that organizations use to enhance their available knowledge resources (Gondo, Kolawole and Mbaiwa, 2019). In other words, workforce diversity helps to exploit the knowledge resources of employees from diverse backgrounds and thus improve employee creativity and competitive advantage (Syed and Ozbilgin, 2019). As a point of emphasis, knowledge is an important source of creativity and competitive advantage. Accordingly, firms put in place robust knowledge management strategies to stimulate the culture of creativity among employees. This indicates that managing knowledge is as important as managing other tangible assets of an organization (Bogilović, Černe and Škerlavaj, 2017). For firms to be successful and achieve a competitive advantage, they must depend on knowledge just as they depend on other types of resources at their disposal. As argued by Lopez-Cabrales, Pérez-Luño and Cabrera (2009), the significance of knowledge is dependent on effective knowledge management in an organization bringing many benefits that lift the organization to the horizon of success. Also, Ogbeibu, Senadjki, and Gaskin (2018) opine that when knowledge is managed well, it promotes continuous innovation and success.

For effective knowledge management, knowledge sharing is considered as a key contributor because it guarantees efficient exploitation of organizational knowledge resources (Ali, Musawir and Ali, 2018). Knowledge sharing is defined by Damodaran and Olphert (2000) as the process whereby employees exchange knowledge resources to generate new knowledge. Two dimensions namely knowledge donating and knowledge collecting are used to operationalize knowledge sharing (Van Den Hooff and Van Weenen, 2004). Whereas knowledge donating is communicating personal intellectual capital to other team members, knowledge collecting encompasses consulting other members to share their intellectual capital (Ogbeibu et al., 2018). Issues such as knowledge as personal property, different interpretations of knowledge, lack of trust among team members, and a limited capacity to absorb and share knowledge are regarded as barriers to knowledge sharing (Maravilhas and Martins, 2019). That notwithstanding, knowledge sharing as an important element in knowledge management in a culturally diverse workforce environment can yield better knowledge outcomes than it can in a less diverse workforce scenario (Ali et al., 2019). A study by Ali et al. (2019) found that diversity in the

workplace provides greater knowledge resources for workers, which can increase individual and team creativity, which in turn leads to competitive advantage.

6.4.5 Promotes creativity and innovation

Diversity in the workplace offers diverse benefits that enhance employee creativity and innovation (Hughes, Lee, Tian, Newman, and Legood, 2018). Creativity and innovation are two separate concepts but are largely interwoven or closely related and overlapped concepts. In its simplistic form, creativity focuses on idea generation, while innovation is concerned with both idea generation and eventual implementation (Potočnik and Anderson, 2016). However, creativity is broadly defined as the production of novel, appropriate ideas in any domain, whereas innovation is defined as the introduction and application of processes, products, or procedures new to the relevant unit of adoption (Anderson, Potočnik and Zhou, 2014). Even though innovation involves a convergent process of idea implementation, both creativity and innovation emphasize a divergent process of idea generation that can benefit from a broad pool of perspectives supplied by diversity in multicultural teams. Safeguarding cultural diversity at the workplace is possible to create an atmosphere where information sharing can be guaranteed, implying that employees exchange, discuss, and integrate ideas, knowledge, and insights critical to the group task (Ramos, Anderson, Peiró and Zijlstra, 2016). These benefits explain why workplace diversity enhances team creativity and innovation.

6.5 Managing Cultural Diversity

Globally, workplaces have generally been labeled as cultural melting pots where facets of cultural diversity and inclusion initiatives must be inculcated into a corporate strategy for effective business management which in turn leads to competitive advantage. Based on the analysis of the interview conducted, five approaches to managing cultural diversity are discussed below;

6.5.1 Process, structure, and operation philosophy

The starting point of addressing and managing cultural diversity at the workplace is by making sure the processes, structures and operational philosophy of the organization capture and make for inclusion and diversity. In doing so, the organizational development approach (OD) to diversity is suggested by Trenerry and Paradies (2012) because it presents an integrated, planned, system-wide and long-term process of change. In short, the organizational development (OD) approach entails a rudimentary examination of the present state of the organization within the context of diversity and its vision of where it wants to be in the future. Broadly, this calls for a non-cosmetic approach but instead a strategic decision where inclusion and diversity initiatives are reflective of the organization's values, vision, marketing plans, public image, and also in the technology and operative methods of the organization (Leveson, Joiner and Bakalis, 2009). Additionally, the diversity strategy must factor in all elements and departments of the organization. It shouldn't just be an HR (human resource) led initiative but rather an initiative that is deeply rooted in the DNA of the organization – spearheaded by the top echelons of the organization (Vangen and Winchester, 2014). Furthermore, there is a need for a long-term plan to capture cultural diversity in all spheres of the organization. The true essence of the diversity strategy will be appreciated when the organization understands that to improve the bottom line of the organization and thus achieve competitive advantage, in the long run, is a function of diversity policies and investments.

6.5.2 Diversity management training programs

Diversity should be a major concern in any organization and valuing diversity in all aspects of operations should be a top priority. Accordingly, training management's executives and employees of the organization in order to embrace and promote diversity in the workplace is perhaps the most important consideration in the diversity strategy of managing cultural diversity in workplace (Sanchez and Medkik, 2004). The relevance of diversity management training program is anchored on anecdotal evidence that suggests that middle management and the sometime top leadership of organizations are not receptive and supportive of a diverse work group which makes it challenging to implement any strategy amongst the larger workforce

(Torres, and Hanashiro, 2017; Wilkinson, 2017). The consent of leadership in investing time and resources on training/sensitization becomes an impossible task. It must be emphasized however that mindset can only be changed with education, awareness, and cultural sensitivity training. The human resource department must invest in training managers, leaders, and everyone in an organization to develop an inclusive mindset and the behavior and attitude that one should demonstrate while working with people from different backgrounds (Alhejji et al., 2016). Diversity training activities such as lectures, role-playing exercises, discussions, and group experiences seek to provide a vehicle for increasing awareness and examining stereotypes. When done well, everyone in the organization appreciates individual differences, increases their cross-cultural understanding, and confronts stereotypes (Madera, Kapoor and Lee, 2018).

6.5.3 Employee involvement and engagement

The relevance of workforce diversity in promoting innovation and creativity to accomplish personal and as well organizational objective cannot be overemphasized. Organizations that effectively take advantage of the strengths of all employees and capitalize on their differences and unique values have the most engaged employees (Nowacka, 2017). Thus, employee involvement and engagement in managing workforce diversity are paramount. The philosophy of “involvement and engagement” seeks to achieve what is known as the inclusion of “all workforce” but not “some” or “select few” (Tanikawa, Kim and Jung, 2017). Achieving involvement and engagement requires a holistic change in the organizational structure, human resource policies, operational procedures, style of leadership, and altogether the culture of the organization (Duehr and Bono, 2006). According to Ahmed (2019), employee involvement and engagement in managing workforce diversity is a total culture change at the individual, group, and the organizational levels. Employee involvement and engagement develop positive attitudes and behavior toward the job and organization (Sanyang and Othman, 2019). Employee involvement and engagement transform the attitude of the workforce towards organization and its values. Without employee involvement and engagement, companies are in contempt of the idea of diversity and inclusion in their business strategy thus promoting a disengaged workforce.

6.5.4 Monitor, measurement, and evaluation

Quite frankly, one of the major challenges impeding diversity management is associated with implementation (Sanyang and Othman, 2019). Diversity management on paper is always right but in most cases, implementation turns out different. Many organizations find it extremely difficult to implement strategies that seek to promote workforce diversity (Tanikawa, Kim and Jung, 2017). Therefore, organizations must develop robust and practicable strategies for implementation, monitor measure, and evaluate the result continuously if they are to meet organizational needs and aspirations (Li et al., 2020). Monitoring, measurement, and evaluation of the workforce diversity strategy are imperative such that it cannot be discounted. This element of the process of managing workforce diversity means that the implementing company continuously monitor, measure, and evaluate the progress and results of the diversity or inclusion strategy being implemented (Verma, 2020). Measuring the results of the diversity initiatives that have been implemented is important. Measurement indicators such as enhanced employee retention, and public recognition, such as employer awards or social media accolades, can also indicate how an organization is performing in its diversity and inclusion initiatives (Duehr and Bono, 2006). While some efforts may seem imperceptible, some measures can show the success rate of the diversity strategy. For example, a diversity strategy implemented to promote increased employee retention, employee retention can be tracked over time, and employees can be surveyed to determine if the strategy was a factor.

6.5.5 Reward

Having a robust and time-relevant diversity management strategy in organizations encourage and rewards employees and also the organization as a whole in a new way. Employees reap the rewards of being functionally diverse because team members can share their views in ways that uncover differences and, equally important, uncover them in collaborative, collective ways (Tanikawa, Kim and Jung, 2017). Also, a workforce diversity management strategy ensures retention and promotes cognitively diverse talent and organizations should put in place reward programs for employees who tolerate diversity and also represent different thinking styles (Odhiambo et al., 2018).

6.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter presents the discussion of the findings from the study. From the discussion of the findings, the study shows that there is a relationship between cultural diversity and competitive advantage in the Nigerian banking industry. The dissertation shows that existing research backs up the findings, which show that, except for ethnicity, all parts of cultural diversity are linked to a competitive advantage in a significant way.

CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSION, CONTRIBUTIONS, IMPLICATIONS, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE

7.1 Chapter Seven

This section of the thesis presents the outline of the key findings from the investigation as well as the conclusions. The section also presents suggestions that will help improve the ways cultural diversity is implemented and managed. Furthermore, the section included the contribution, the limitations of the research, and the direction for future research.

7.1 Summary of Key Findings

The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between cultural diversity and competitive advantage in the banking industry. The study also examined the role of innovation in the relationship between cultural diversity and competitive advantage. Specifically, the study first examines the influence of diversity on performance in the Nigerian banking industry. Next, the study assessed the influence of service innovation on the relationship between diversity and performance in the Nigerian banking industry. The study also explored the nature of cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry. The study also sought to understand how cultural diversity results in competitive advantage and how Nigerian banks manage cultural diversity. The findings of the study revealed that gender, culture, age, religion, language, and race are grounds for cultural diversity in the banking industry. The findings of the study also recognised that cultural diversity affects the competitiveness of Nigeria banks by promoting labour productivity, task and relationship conflict, organizational learning, knowledge management and promotes creativity and innovation. The findings also showed that in the case of individual effect on cultural diversity, except ethnicity, all the elements of cultural diversity have a significant relationship with competitive advantage. The finding also showed that age diversity has the most significant effect on competitive advantage.

Gender diversity has a significant effect on competitive advantage, particularly because an appropriate degree of women's involvement with a proficient instinct for satisfying and

delighting unstable customers' needs may contribute to achieving a competitive advantage in the highly competitive banking industry (Kang et al. 2007). Moreover, since ladies are probably going to be autonomous from "men" network and proficient in fostering harmony, in line with agency theory, females may play out a significant and vital job of observing supervisors alongside giving special viewpoints that encourage an improvement of official supervisors' strategic choices (Farrell and Hersch, 2005). Furthermore, another possible benefit of gender diversity in an organization is to attract and retain progressively qualified female laborers. That is, as the serious extent of gender diversity comes to light, it might cause an improvement in corporate image in the community and serve as a potential driver to attract more skillful female workers. Also, organizations anticipate that females may provide more emotional and touching services to customers who are critical partners in banks' operational achievement, which brings about customer satisfaction, loyalty, and retention (Fondas, 2000).

7.2 Contributions of the Research

This study provides some contribution to the business literature by examining the relationship between cultural diversity and competitive advantage in the Nigerian banking industry. This study found the positive effect of cultural diversity on competitive advantage, which confirms the relevant theories, including cognitive diversity theory, the market-based view (MBV), the resource-based view (RBV), the knowledge-based view (KBV), the capability-based view, and the relational view of strategy, enhancing the external validity of the relationship. Theoretically, this supports the hypothesis of the influence of cultural diversity on innovation and competitive advantage. Thus, diversity is viewed as an organizational resource (which supports the MBV, RBV, and KBV) that leads to innovation and competitive advantage for firms that posit it. Nonetheless, the study also shows that there are some challenges associated with cultural diversity, confirming the application of the similarity-attraction paradigm and social identity theory, while the justification-suppression model justifies the need to manage these challenges.

In relation to the cognitive diversity theory, the study confirms the argument that various points of view coming from cultural differences between individuals in an organization bring about creative problem solving and innovation. This results in competitive advantage and member

diversity is seen as a resource, capability, or competence, affirming the MBV, RBV, and KBV, the capability-based view, and relational view of strategy theories. The findings of the study also show that since the similarity-attraction paradigm and social identity theory state that individuals feel more contented working with others who are similar to them, there would be challenges working with individuals from a diverse cultural background. The justification-suppression model argues for the need to manage cultural diversity since, if not managed, individuals would act based on their prejudiced expressions and experience. Hence, based on the findings, a framework is provided for the management of cultural diversity.

The findings of this study have a lot of managerial ramifications. First, Nigerian banks must take a more systematic approach to managing diversity, treating it as a social justice issue rather than a popular debate. The research finds significant gaps in management understanding and expertise when it comes to diversity management and the areas that need to be controlled. Managing diversity is a gentler approach to human resource management that has yet to be adopted by Nigerian banks as a human resource management strategy. While diversity management has been a popular topic in management research in the West, Nigerian executives are still unfamiliar with the concept. The majority of the time, diversity management is done informally by Nigerian bankers who make sense of their managerial job by reflecting on the social expectations of their staff. The enforcement of laws aimed at achieving greater social equality in these countries is sometimes uncertain.

Second, for managers and organizations, the study provides a 2-stage approach to managing cultural diversity in the Nigerian banking industry. The first stage is considered the pre-stage approach. Thus, before an organization decides to diversify, first the process, structure, and operation philosophy should align to support diversification of the workforce; hence second, management training programs for top-level management, since for it to be successful, it has to start from the top. Next, the idea has to be sold to existing employees because they would implement it. There could be complex ramifications that cultural diversity management can have for an organization focusing mainly on its objectives. The findings, therefore, recommended, first, the need to build a cultural diversity management policy. Such arrangements have the benefit of helping banks to play a progressively self-assured job in the administration of a decent

variety of related functions of human resources management. The findings also suggested that Nigerian banks, just like all associations with staff that are enhanced on cultural grounds, should take the organization of such a preparation workshop seriously. Notwithstanding the instruction on various cultures, staff ought to be prepared to value the nitty-gritty and specialized complexities of having and working with culturally separated associates. Such preparation should concentrate on giving workers practical teamwork, adjustment, and joint effort aptitudes to enable them to incorporate and oblige others from different societies for the improvement and prosperity of their organizations. Now, when it is implemented, monitoring, measurement, evaluation, and reward are required to ensure success. There might be inevitable attitudes and activities that wind up separating the workforce, causing a few gatherings to feel unwanted. These should be used to keep up decent variety in the workforce. The specialist suggests that associations consider using representative overviews to check how workers feel on these subjects as a way to find issues before these issues cause workers to leave. Advancing a comprehensive culture is one key measure aimed at ensuring that administration of social decent variety and its rated issues can be sustained and not just be a passing fad.

In particular, the Nigerian banks should pay special attention to building diversity in their interactions with each employee. Furthermore, it is crucial to understand that cultural diversity among their staff has a favorable effect on innovation. Separately, Ozgen, Nijkamp, and Poot (2011) examined the direct impact of cultural diversity on creativity, which was confirmed by the results above and can be proposed for carrying out the reorganization in the future. Thus, innovation is indirectly influenced by diversity management through strategic leadership. Innovation benefits from cultural variety when there is a strategic leadership plan for managing diversity. As demonstrated by earlier studies that discovered cultural diversity accumulates in different groups and races, diversity management also fosters creativity through cultural diversity. As was already mentioned, cultural diversity has a direct impact on creativity, but despite the importance of the outcome, diversity management is rarely discussed in the literature. Through diversity management, bank management is responsible for creating a workplace that is helpful and supportive, where people can talk, give feedback, and share what they know with others.

7.3 Limitations of the research and directions for future research

This study discovered that if issues of cultural diversity are managed well in an organization, it would result in an organization's competitiveness. Despite the contributions of this study, there are some limitations to the study. As is the case with most business research, the current study used one-time data, which might not capture the well-thought-out views of the respondents. If responses could be gathered occasionally and extended over a longer period, additional data regarding how cultural diversity drives organizational competitiveness could be gathered. Also, taking into consideration that the study sample consisted of respondents from two banks in a developing country, there is the possibility that the finding may differ when using respondents from developed countries and other banks. Future studies could therefore expand the sample units to provide generalisation. Future studies should also look at longitudinal data to see if persistently inventive organizations grow more diverse or if a diverse business becomes more innovative. It may also be beneficial to target specific businesses based on their skill set and organizational structure, as the impact of diversity may differ between companies focused on interaction modes versus more science-based ones. Similarly, in positions with a high degree of routine, diversity is less crucial than in jobs that require interaction and problem-solving. The impact of organizational modes and innovation strategies should also be considered in future research.

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	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
	1	2	3	4	5
Diversity	1	2	3	4	5
<i>In this office, there is diversity in</i>					
..... age	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... gender	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... work experience	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... educational qualification	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... marital status	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... cultural	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... ethnicity	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... Disabilities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... Class	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... language	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Service innovation	1	2	3	4	5
<i>In recent years, our bank has</i>					
..... developed new service processes	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... improved existing services	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... repackaged existing services	<input type="checkbox"/>				
..... introduced totally new services that competitors do not offer in the market	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Competitiveness	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Our company</i>					
... exploitation of all market opportunities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
... full exploitation of market opportunities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
... neutralization of all competitive threats	<input type="checkbox"/>				
... full neutralization of all competitive threats	<input type="checkbox"/>				

THANK YOU FOR PARTICIPATING IN THIS SURVEY

